

**PERSONAL AND SOCIO-ENVIRONMENTAL PERSPECTIVE
ON CHALLENGES OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN
INDIA**

BY

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Declaration

I, Khushboo Deraiya, declare that this thesis, ‘Personal and socio-environmental perspective on challenges of female entrepreneurship in India’, is the result of my own work and does not include anything which is the outcome of work done in collaboration except where specifically indicated in the text. It has not been previously submitted, in part or whole, to any university or institution for any degree, diploma or other qualification. I understand the ethical implications of my research, and this work meet the requirements of the Business and Creative Industries and Research Ethics Committee. Any work taken from another source has been appropriately referenced and acknowledged.

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Abstract

Entrepreneurship is an important activity in the economy as it facilitates the creation of employment, the development of innovative products, societal development, and the generation of government revenue. However, a prevalent challenge in developing countries like India is that female entrepreneurs are often not as successful as their male counterparts due to various underlying factors. The under-representation of female entrepreneurs in entrepreneurial activities in India underscores a need to understand these factors to encourage more females to venture into entrepreneurship to support their families and promote the growth of society. This research examines perceptions of female entrepreneurs in India on the personal and socio-environmental factors influencing entrepreneurial success and the relationship of those perceptions with longevity in business (years in business) as a proxy for success. An online questionnaire was developed and administered to female entrepreneurs in India, and the resultant data was analysed using multinomial logistic regression to predict female entrepreneurial success. Findings show female entrepreneurs' perceptions of personal factors such as business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence, predicted female entrepreneurial longevity in India. In addition, perceptions of family support and government policies significantly predict the longevity of female entrepreneurs in India. Perceptions of both traditional and modern challenges as factors significantly influence female entrepreneurial longevity in business. This study contributes to knowledge by providing an understanding of the relationship between perceptions of female entrepreneurs in India and their longevity in business. It introduces a conceptual framework, grounded in the theory of planned behaviour, which provides an initial understanding of the role of perceptions in the complex dynamics of female entrepreneurship in the Indian context. The study's conceptual framework and findings offer actionable insights to provide support to female entrepreneurs in India, informing efforts to create a more inclusive entrepreneurial ecosystem in India. The study highlights the role that perceptions play in the entrepreneurial success of female entrepreneurs in India. Based on the findings, the study makes recommendations to develop and promote a comprehensive entrepreneurial programme, to strengthen support systems and emotional intelligence development for early-stage entrepreneurs, and to improve perceptions of government policies through awareness and accessibility of government policies.

Keywords: India, female entrepreneurial success, perceptions, factors, challenges

Table of Contents

Declaration	I
Acknowledgement.....	II
Abstract.....	III
Table of Contents	IV
Glossary of the terms	X
List of Tables	XII
List of Figures	XIII
List of Abbreviations	XIV
Chapter 1 Introduction.....	1
1.1 Introduction.....	1
1.2 Overview of female entrepreneurs	2
1.2.1 Defining female entrepreneurs.....	2
1.2.2 Defining female entrepreneurial success in India.....	3
1.3 Research context	4
1.3.1 Overview of the entrepreneurship context in India.....	4
1.3.2 Specific barriers faced by female entrepreneurs in India	8
1.3.3 Impact of COVID-19 on female entrepreneurs	12

1.3.4 Female Entrepreneurs in India	14
1.3.5 Rationale and justification for this study in India.....	16
1.4 Problem Statement.....	17
1.5 Research Aims	18
1.6 Research Objectives	20
1.7 Research Questions	20
1.8 Research Hypothesis	21
1.9 Study significance.....	22
1.10 Research scope and boundaries	24
1.11 Overview of the methodology.....	25
1.12 Organisation of the study.....	26
Chapter 2 Literature Review	28
2.1 Introduction.....	28
2.2 Background information.....	28
2.2.1 The concept of entrepreneurship	29
2.2.2 Significance of female entrepreneurship.....	33
2.2.3 Complexity in female entrepreneurship	37
2.2.4 Problems facing female entrepreneurs in developing countries.....	39
2.3 Factors that influence the success of female entrepreneurs.....	47
2.3.1 Personal factors	47

2.3.2 Environmental factors	52
2.3.3 Traditional challenges and modern challenges as factors	58
2.4 Theoretical framework	62
2.4.1 Overview of the theory of planned behaviour (TPB)	63
2.4.2 Strengths and weaknesses of the TPB.....	70
2.4.3 Justification of the use of the TPB in the current study	72
2.5 Research gaps for female entrepreneurship.....	73
2.5.1 Need for studies in an Indian context.....	73
2.5.2 Limited empirical findings from India	75
2.5.3 Need for conceptual frameworks	76
2.5.4 Need for practical solutions for female entrepreneurs in India	77
2.6 Hypothesis development for personal factors	78
2.7 Hypothesis development for environmental factors	82
2.8 Hypothesis development for challenges.....	88
Chapter 3 Methodology	91
3.1 Introduction.....	91
3.2 Research philosophy	91
3.3 Research strategy	97
3.4 Research design.....	99
3.5 Research variables	100

3.5.1 Outcome variable.....	100
3.5.2 Predictors	101
3.6 Research hypotheses	106
3.7 Population and sampling	107
3.7.1 Research population	107
3.7.2 Sampling strategy and sample size.....	109
3.8 Data collection tools	113
3.8.1 Self-administrated questionnaire	113
3.9 Research validity and reliability	118
3.9.1 Validity of the questionnaire.....	118
3.9.2 Questionnaire reliability	120
3.10 Pilot Study	121
3.11 Distribution of the questionnaire	122
3.12 Data analysis techniques	123
3.13 Ethical considerations	126
3.14 Chapter Summary.....	126
Chapter 4 Results and Analysis.....	127
4.1 Data preparation	127
4.1.1 Data cleaning	127
4.1.2 Missing data.....	128

4.1.3 Data reliability analysis	129
4.2 Testing the hypotheses.....	131
4.2.1 Verifying assumptions for multinomial regression analysis	131
4.2.2 Hypothesis testing.....	135
4.3 Chapter Summary.....	148
Chapter 5 Discussion	149
5.1 Introduction.....	149
5.2 Research hypotheses and results	151
5.3 Theory of planned behaviour and study findings	166
5.4 Limitations of the research	170
5.5 Future research directions	172
5.6 Chapter summary	174
Chapter 6 Conclusion	175
6.1 Introduction.....	175
6.2 Research questions and study findings.....	175
6.3 Implications of the findings	177
6.4 Contribution to Knowledge	177
6.5 Practical contributions.....	179
6.6 Recommendations based on study findings.....	182

6.6.1 To develop and promote comprehensive entrepreneurial education programmes.....	182
6.6.2 To strengthen family support systems and emotional intelligence development.....	183
6.6.3 To improve awareness and accessibility of government policies.....	184
References	188
Appendix A: Tables	220
Appendix B: Participant Information Sheet	230
Appendix C: Ethical Approval Letter.....	233
Appendix D: Research Questionnaire.....	234

Glossary of the terms

Female entrepreneurial success - In the context of this research, female entrepreneurial success is defined as being in business and keeping their businesses operational over time (Author). The success of female entrepreneurs is measured by the number of years they have been in business.

Entrepreneurship - In the context of this research on female entrepreneurs, entrepreneurship refers to the readiness and ability to organise, develop, and run an enterprise, being cognisant of the potential uncertainties, with the goal of sustaining the business over a long duration (adapted from Gaddefors and Anderson, 2017).

Female entrepreneurship is the process by which females take the initiative to start businesses, mobilise resources and take risks, overcome challenges, create job opportunities, and manage their ventures independently (Tiwari, 2022).

Barriers to female entrepreneurs - Barriers imply the obstacles and hindrances that females in business face while running their businesses (Author).

Personal factors - These include factors that are intrinsic to female entrepreneurs and within their control. It include factors such as business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence (Author).

Environmental factors - These include factors that are external and beyond the control of female entrepreneurs. It includes factors such as family support, social support, gender stereotypes, technological advancements, and government policies (Author).

Social development - Social development is used to imply the social empowerment of females to enhance equality and equity in engaging in entrepreneurial activities (Author).

Economic growth and development - While economic growth and development mean the overall growth in an economy's main indicators, such as gross domestic product (GDP) and national income, in this context, it further implies empowering females economically or financially as equal development partners in the economy (Author).

Sustainable development - The term sustainable development refers to promoting the economic welfare of females alongside men in society with the aim of realising global sustainable development goals (Author).

List of Tables

Table 1.1 Perceptions of factors list	19
Table 1.2 Research Hypotheses.....	21
Table 2.1 Distinguishing Traditional Challenges and Modern Challenges	61
Table 3.1 Demographic Profile of Participants	112
Table 4.1 Reliability Statistics.....	130
Table 4.2 Tolerance and VIF Values	133
Table 4.3 Means and Trimmed Means.....	134
Table 4.4 Hypothesis Tests Summary	147
Appendix A: Table 3. 1 Questionnaire Constructs and Items	220
Appendix A: Table 3. 2 Factor analysis	223
Appendix A: Table 3. 3 Total variance for all the factors.....	226
Appendix A: Table 4. 1 Likelihood ratio tests	228
Appendix A: Table 4. 2 Goodness of fit tests	228
Appendix A: Table 4. 3 Pseudo R-Square.....	228
Appendix A: Table 4. 4 Parameter Estimates (Reference Category, ‘More than 5 years’)	228
Appendix A: Table 4. 5 Parameter Estimates (Reference Category, ‘Less than 5 years’)	229

List of Figures

Figure 1.1 Dissertation Structure (Author).....	27
Figure 2.1 Impact of Entrepreneurship on Employment (Kritikos, 2020).....	34
Figure 2.2 Survival of New Firms (Helmets and Rogers, 2010).....	35
Figure 2.3 Ajzen’s Theory of Planned Behaviour.....	63
Figure 2.4 Conceptual Framework, Source (Author’s Illustration)	78
Figure 3.1 Research Process (Author).....	91
Figure 4.1 Boxplot for all the Variables (Author).....	134
Figure 4.2 Model 1 Results of Personal Factors (Author).....	139
Figure 4.3 Model 2 Results of Environmental Factors (Author).....	143
Figure 4.4 Model 3 Results of Challenges (Author)	146

List of Abbreviations

BK	Business Knowledge
RB	Risk-taking Behaviour
EI	Emotional Intelligence
FS	Family Support
SS	Social Support
GS	Gender Stereotypes
TA	Technological Advancements
GP	Government Policies
TC	Traditional Challenges
MC	Modern Challenges
YIB	Years in Business
FE	Female Entrepreneurs
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
AI	Artificial Intelligence
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
MBA	Master of Business Administration
MSME	Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise
SPSS	Statistical Package of Social Sciences
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
NPDA	Non-Profit Development Agency
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development

Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Entrepreneurship has garnered significant interest recently in the past few decades. It has evolved globally as a catalyst for economic progress through the promotion of innovation, employment creation, and facilitation of economic expansion. This growing interest can be attributed to entrepreneurship's potential to drive economic progress by improving efficiency and increasing overall economic output (Audretsch and Thurik, 2001; Shane, 2009). The examination of entrepreneurship, particularly among females, presents a crucial field of economic and social investigation given entrepreneurship's capacity to stimulate growth, innovation, and societal change. In particular, the rise of female entrepreneurs from traditional gender roles and challenging long-standing socio-economic norms stands out as a compelling phenomenon.

In India, which is renowned for its vibrant entrepreneurial ecosystem, the emergence of female entrepreneurs has been particularly noteworthy, reflecting both the opportunities available and the barriers they confront. The nation's distinct obstacles and hindrances can influence female entrepreneurs' businesses' commencement, sustainability, and expansion. Studying the perceptions of female entrepreneurs in India regarding these factors and the influence of these perceptions on female entrepreneurial success is beneficial both for the female entrepreneurs themselves and for policymakers, educators, and support groups striving to cultivate a more comprehensive entrepreneurial environment. Thus, this study aims to investigate the perceptions of the key factors that

influence the success of female entrepreneurs in India and to provide recommendations to female entrepreneurs, the government, and other organisations interested in empowering females.

This introductory chapter is split into 12 main subsections: introduction, overview of female entrepreneurs, research context, problem statement, research aims and objectives, research questions and hypotheses, significance of the study, research scope and boundaries, overview of the methodology, and organisation of the study.

1.2 Overview of female entrepreneurs

1.2.1 Defining female entrepreneurs

Female entrepreneurs in developing countries, including India, are defined through various lenses that reflect their multiple roles and the challenges they face in the entrepreneurial journey. The Government of India defines female entrepreneurs as those owning and controlling an enterprise with a minimum financial interest of 51% of the capital and providing at least 51% of employment generated in the enterprise to females, highlighting a formal acknowledgement of their economic independence and contribution (Kaviarasu, Ruban and Francis, 2018). Beyond the legal definition, in broader terms, academic studies conducted in India have defined female entrepreneurs as females who initiate, organise, and operate business enterprises to meet personal needs and achieve economic independence (Rajamani, 2022).

The definition of female entrepreneurs in India covers a wide range of business activities, from single-person startups to family businesses, partnerships, and corporations (Aggrawal *et al.*, 2022). In this study, female entrepreneurs are females who start,

manage, and actively run businesses in India as sole traders, self-employed workers, or partners in any sector.

1.2.2 Defining female entrepreneurial success in India

Success is subjective, and the definition of success varies considerably. The definition of female entrepreneurial success in India is influenced by economic, social, cultural, environmental, and personal dimensions. According to Sachdeva (2023), success for female entrepreneurs in India is not solely measured by financial gains but also includes the empowerment and economic independence that come with owning and managing a business (Sachdeva, 2023). It involves the ability to overcome traditional societal barriers and gender-specific challenges and assert a position in the male-dominated business world (Devi, 2023). Furthermore, the government's role in promoting female's entrepreneurship through various laws and programmes indicates a broader definition of success that includes leadership roles in economic, social, and political organisations (Saranya and Chandrasekar, 2023).

The ability of female entrepreneurs to contribute to economic development by leading successful businesses based on their specific characteristics and overcoming societal and cultural hurdles is a testament to their success (Abrar ul Haq, Victor and Akram, 2020). Specific characteristics refer to certain inherent and developed qualities that female entrepreneurs typically possess. These characteristics include resilience, innovation, strong networking skills, adaptability, and empathy, which help them overcome societal and cultural hurdles and contribute significantly to economic development (Rosa and Hamilton, 1994; Still and Timms, 2000; Eagly and Carli, 2003; De Bruin, Brush and Welter, 2006; Robinson and Stubberud, 2009). Moreover, successful female

entrepreneurs in India are those who can sustain and strive for excellence in their businesses amidst the challenges of global marketplaces (Sahoo, 2020). Given the variety of dimensions to defining female entrepreneurial success in India, success is a complex construct that goes beyond economic achievements to include empowerment, societal contribution, innovation, and the overcoming of gender-specific barriers.

In the context of this research, female entrepreneurial success is defined as a woman being in business and keeping her business operational over time; the greater the amount of time the business has been operational, the greater the success. Surviving in business, keeping one's activity operational and active, and overcoming barriers and challenges are also an achievement for female entrepreneurs. The success of female entrepreneurs is measured by the number of years they have been in business. Years in business are used as a proxy for entrepreneurial success due to their simplicity and the availability of data. This measure assumes that the longer a business survives, the more successful it is, reflecting an entrepreneur's ability to navigate barriers and challenges effectively. Longevity can indicate stability and growth, which are signs of business health and entrepreneurial adeptness (Robb and Watson, 2012).

1.3 Research context

1.3.1 Overview of the entrepreneurship context in India

The study is based in India, so it is necessary to provide an understanding of the entrepreneurial context of the country. Entrepreneurship in India is multifaceted and reflects the vast diversity of the country's dynamic economic landscape. The entrepreneurship ecosystem and innovation in India are expanding on the global

landscape, indicating significant integration in technology, skilled workforce, funding, and governance (Bhagavatula, Mudambi, and Murmann, 2019). This indicates that the Indian entrepreneurship ecosystem and innovation are becoming more important on the global stage, and this global relevance highlights the necessity of addressing India's diverse landscape. Given the country's diverse landscape, which includes multiple languages, religions, and socio-economic disparities, a contextualized approach to entrepreneurship education and support is essential to address the needs of diverse communities (Venkataramany and Jayachandran, 2023).

As explained by Ansari (2016), India is the seventh-largest country in the world and probably the second most populated. In 2019, the population of the country was estimated to be 1.38 billion (Ughetto *et al.*, 2020). It is estimated that a sixth of the world's population resides in India. Its population consists of highly diverse ethnic groups speaking hundreds of languages. In addition to its diverse religions and sects, the country is home to many castes and tribes (Rabbani and Chowdhury, 2013).

India's entrepreneurial landscape reflects a blend of tradition, diversity, and technological advancement, making it a dynamic hub for startups and innovative ideas. Many new types of entrepreneurship have emerged from the traditional entrepreneurial landscape. According to Katakwar (2022), agribusiness entrepreneurship has emerged as a crucial area, highlighting the transition from traditional agriculture to agribusiness as important for the economy. It addresses equitable wealth distribution and unemployment. The significance of social entrepreneurship addressing socio-economic and environmental needs not fulfilled by market or state efforts has also emerged, which plays a particularly important role in the context of India (Pandey and Sahay, 2022). Social entrepreneurship

plays a crucial role in India as it addresses intricate societal issues, including poverty, disparities in income, environmental pollution, and the limited availability of crucial services like healthcare and education (Chauhan and Ghai, 2023).

The entrepreneurial landscape is currently evolving in India and is influenced by a skilled workforce and socially learnt stereotypes, particularly among females. Joshi, Pandit and Tiwari's (2022) study of entrepreneurial intentions among Master of Business Administration (MBA) students underscores this. Additionally, the venture capital industry in India has experienced a boom, supported by the institutional and technological capabilities of the country's innovation system and the entrepreneurial ecosystem (Gonzalo and Kantis, 2021). Although entrepreneurship is significant and evolving in India and therefore providing opportunities, it also presents challenges, particularly for female entrepreneurs. Initiatives like 'Make in India' and 'Digital India' foster entrepreneurship and innovation, enabling females to participate actively in the economy. The 'Make in India' initiative encourages local manufacturing and entrepreneurship. This initiative helps entrepreneurs with an opportunity to start their own businesses, access financial assistance, and benefit from various government schemes aimed at supporting startups. The initiative includes various skill development programmes that help females acquire the necessary skills for manufacturing and entrepreneurship. This enhances their employability and ability to start and sustain businesses. 'Make in India' facilitates better market access both domestically and internationally. Female entrepreneurs can benefit from this by expanding their businesses and getting a more extensive customer base in the domestic and international markets (Kumar, 2023).

'Digital India' focuses on increasing digital literacy across the country. Females in rural regions have the opportunity to utilise digital technologies, which enable them to participate in online economic activities. This programme advocates for utilising online platforms to sell goods and services, offering females a channel to market their products without a physical store. This reduces the entry barriers for female entrepreneurs. With the digitisation of government services, females can now easily access various schemes, grants, and loans to support entrepreneurship and economic participation. 'Digital India' has expanded the possibilities for remote work. This is particularly beneficial for female who may face cultural or familial restrictions on working outside the home (Ghosh, 2022; Patil, 2023)

The 'Make in India' and 'Digital India' initiatives have opened up new opportunities for female economic participation by promoting entrepreneurship, skill development, and digital literacy. Nevertheless, various challenges, including adopting digital technology in rural areas, restricted capital availability, societal and cultural obstacles, and insufficient infrastructure, impede their entrepreneurial efforts (Ghosh, 2022; Kumar, 2023; Patil, 2023). However, despite these opportunities, female entrepreneurs in India face many barriers and challenges that restrict their entrepreneurial success. India's unique challenges, including wealth inequality, gender bias, and unemployment, require a contextualised approach to address the needs of diverse communities (Venkataramany and Jayachandran, 2023). Female entrepreneurship has gained attention among scholars and researchers, revealing historical and contemporary challenges and opportunities. However, female entrepreneurs have remained under-represented in technology, highlighting the need for a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities in

this area (Shrivastava, 2021). Entrepreneurship in India has gained momentum, prompting a push for harmonised indicators to guide policymakers and foster a self-sustaining economy. Harmonised indicators are standardised metrics used to assess and compare the performance of entrepreneurship across different regions, sectors, or demographics. These indicators help policymakers and stakeholders measure progress, identify challenges, and develop targeted strategies to promote entrepreneurship effectively. In the context of India, the momentum in entrepreneurship has led to the need for such harmonised indicators. These indicators provide a consistent framework to evaluate entrepreneurial activities, to track growth, to understand the impact of policies, and to identify areas needing improvement (Shrikrishna and Ramdas, 2022).

1.3.2 Specific barriers faced by female entrepreneurs in India

1.3.2.1 Lack of financial access

One of the challenges hindering the success of Indian female entrepreneurship is the lack of financial access. The ventures of female entrepreneurs in India are susceptible to diverse risks, including the lack of formal financing and increased margins in formal markets (Mukherjee and Pathak, 2023). As a result, female entrepreneurs struggle to advance their businesses due to restrictions on accessing the necessary finances for their ventures. The use of non-profit development agencies (NPDAs) could be one way to address these restrictions, as they provide support to females and enhance their business survival (Mukherjee and Pathak, 2023). Greater financial accessibility can bring about positive personal changes in female themselves, such as self-dependence, increased self-confidence, and inner strength, thereby promoting female's entrepreneurial activities (Mukherjee and Pathak, 2023).

Many Indian female entrepreneurs have been excluded from financial initiatives by the government, reducing their intention to engage in entrepreneurship (Goel and Madan, 2019). However, the financial inclusion schemes that do exist under the Indian government have encouraged more females to venture into entrepreneurship (Goel and Madan, 2019). Thus, measures to broaden the financial inclusion of female entrepreneurs in India through government schemes and NPDAs are integral to supporting the overall success of female-led ventures. Although Mukherjee and Pathak (2023) as well as Goel and Madan (2019) reported mixed findings on the lack of financial access and measures adopted by various institutions to support female entrepreneurship, their arguments are central to the present investigation regarding possible solutions to entrepreneurial challenges.

1.3.2.2 Gendered stereotypes and family obligations

The existence of gendered stereotypes and family obligations further hinders the success of female entrepreneurs in India. When taking an institutional theory perspective, pull factors, such as the desire for innovation, self-identity, independence, and social service, are the primary reasons for female entrepreneurs to start ventures in India (Shastri, Shastri, and Pareek, 2019). Thus, bottlenecks encountered by female entrepreneurs seemingly originate from informal institutions such as social networks, cultural contexts, and family roles. In addition, cultural norms related to gender roles can lead to work-family conflicts. In a patriarchal society like India, entrepreneurial roles are viewed as more masculine than feminine, and gender roles create challenges in work-life balance (Shastri *et al.*, 2021). Thus, the socio-cultural expectations of females within India lead to

high burdens and family obligations, thereby hindering their capacity to participate in entrepreneurship.

However, social support, role involvement, and core self-evaluation have been shown to work in tandem to drive enrichment and diminish conflict (Sehgal and Khandelwal, 2020). Family involvement and support enable family-to-work satisfaction, suggesting family-work synergies could favour female entrepreneurship. Within Tamil Nadu, a state in the south of India with many female entrepreneurs, successful female entrepreneurs who are driven by opportunity highlight the importance of service, wealth generation, innovation, and employment within entrepreneurial activities (Rastogi, Baral, and Banu, 2022). Despite the context-specific limitations of the cited studies, which limit wider generalisation, they still provide insight into the entrepreneurial dynamics females face in diverse structural, social, economic, and cultural contexts.

The family-entrepreneurial link is critical to understanding venture patterns and management trends among female entrepreneurs. In this regard, highly educated Indian female entrepreneurs also adopt strategies integrating their family and work roles as opposed to creating boundaries between their roles (Banu, Baral, and Kuschel, 2023). For example, females adopt flexible work schedules where they work fewer hours closer to their homes (Banu, Baral, and Kuschel, 2023). When females are supported by their families at home, they feel motivated and work harder to benefit their families. Thus, there is a need for work-family role upgrading to support ventures led by females and reduce conflicts due to work-life balance. Additionally, perceptions of the support received play an important role in entrepreneurial success. The perceptions are female entrepreneurs' beliefs about the support gained, and these perceptions are more

influential than the actual existence of support because of the psychological and motivational impact of the perceived support. Reinforcing this, Barnir, Watson, and Hutchins (2011) found that belief in support systems enhances self-efficacy among female entrepreneurs, which is crucial for their success. Similarly, Aldrich and Cliff (2003) highlighted that perceived support motivates entrepreneurs to pursue opportunities more strongly, leading to better outcomes. Moreover, Manolova *et al.* (2007) suggested that perceived support reduces psychological barriers, making challenges appear more surmountable. However, certain support can be perceived as good by one person but poor by another. This subjective perception of support can significantly influence the outcome for female entrepreneurs and considerably impact motivation, confidence, and business success. For example, Powell and Eddleston (2008) discussed how the same support structure can be empowering for some and detrimental for others, influencing motivation and business success. Consequently, these subjective perceptions of support can lead to different outcomes among female entrepreneurs, highlighting the importance of personalised and context-sensitive support structures.

1.3.2.3 Lack of business knowledge and entrepreneurship skills

The third challenge to the success of female entrepreneurs in India encompasses the lack of business knowledge and entrepreneurship skills. While females in India possess entrepreneurial ambitions, success is often elusive due to various difficulties (Korreck, 2019). Female entrepreneurs have low business skill confidence, difficulty accessing networks and finances, a lack of childcare options and family support, and inadequate safety in public and workspaces (Korreck, 2019). These difficulties highlight the crucial role of intellectual capital, which refers to intangible assets and resources such as

knowledge, skills, and experience, in effectively managing and owning a business venture. On the other hand, opportunity perception and social legitimacy perception are significantly associated with entrepreneurial intentions. Opportunity perception refers to the entrepreneur's ability to identify and evaluate business opportunities, such as trends and gaps in the market. Social legitimacy perception refers to how much an entrepreneur perceives that their business idea or venture will be embraced and supported by society, including family, peers, and the broader community (Arafat *et al.*, 2020). Thus, the perceived capabilities of female entrepreneurs influence their decisions to engage in entrepreneurship activities, and female entrepreneurs succeed in India when they are provided with family support and have access to advanced skills and abilities (Rastogi, Baral, and Banu, 2022). Therefore, providing support to Indian female entrepreneurs so that they are able to advance their knowledge and skills as well as perceptions of these abilities is clearly important to their entrepreneurial success.

1.3.3 Impact of COVID-19 on female entrepreneurs

The COVID-19 pandemic adversely affected businesses and contributed to diminished returns (Sahi, Modi, and Mantok, 2023). Female entrepreneurs were found to have leveraged socio-psychological resources like resilience, entrepreneurial orientation, and networking to innovate services and products during the pandemic (Sahi, Modi, and Mantok, 2023). In addition, networking assisted consumer firms in introducing new and innovative products during the COVID-19 period. Female entrepreneurs in Uttarakhand experienced opportunities and challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic (Srinivasu, Bhatia, and Gupta, 2022). Female entrepreneurs were able to sustain their ventures by switching to online business, adjusting their promotional approach, and conducting work

from home. However, female entrepreneurs also faced the challenge of a lack of funds and significantly relied on past savings to finance business expenses (Srinivasu, Bhatia, and Gupta, 2022); this example highlights how COVID-19 affected female entrepreneurs in Uttarakhand and provided opportunities as well as challenges.

Further effects of COVID-19 were seen among female entrepreneurs in New Delhi who faced challenges from both the COVID-19 pandemic and gender-based issues in the Indian market (Kumar and Singh, 2021b). In this context, Indian female entrepreneurs faced challenges in running their ventures due to the global recession. However, Kumar and Singh's (2021b) findings have been challenged by others who observed that many Indian female entrepreneurs were able to use innovative activities to ensure survival, including shifting their businesses to digital platforms and introducing new products to address consumer needs (Sahi, Modi, and Mantok, 2023), thereby allowing them to advance their entrepreneurial skills (Mishra, 2021). Businesses used digital technologies to reach customers and the adoption of innovation to survive the crisis during the pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic disproportionately affected Indian female entrepreneurs, where some leveraged the crisis to develop more entrepreneurial ventures, and some businesses were badly affected. For example, Indian female entrepreneurs ventured into the production of face masks to address a current need and simultaneously increase their revenue (Mishra, 2021). Whereas some businesses, like tourism and transport, were badly affected due to the reduced demand for the services during the pandemic (Salamzadeh and Dana, 2020).

1.3.4 Female Entrepreneurs in India

Female entrepreneurs in India have continued to experience numerous challenges and opportunities, like their female counterparts in most parts of the world. Several researchers have highlighted that there has been an increase in the number of female entrepreneurs in India, and there are many opportunities for them. Babu (2012) argued that there are considerable efforts globally to elevate the position of females in business, but challenges persist. Nevertheless, a study by Mahajan (2013) examined the position of female entrepreneurs in India in the 21st century and revealed that there has been a shift, and the business potential of females is significantly improving. Mahajan (2013) described the transformative impact of efforts in both developing and developed countries, leading to a considerable increase in female entrepreneurs' participation in business. This change is attributed to shifts in attitudes, increased risk-taking abilities among females, evolving conservative mindsets to embrace gender-inclusive trends in modern society, the implementation of uplifting schemes for female entrepreneurs, particularly in India, and the enactment of policies at governmental and economic levels. Mahajan (2013) described several success stories, including that of Hina Shah, a woman who demonstrated a unique approach in the plastic and packaging industry as the founder and chief executive officer of her company.

However, others claim that female entrepreneurs in India continue to face challenges, their development is slow, and they need more support to transform their societal positions and succeed in their entrepreneurial journey. Goyal and Jai (2012) suggested that females' transformation of their societal positions towards becoming business leaders is occurring at a slow rate in India. Ansari (2016) echoed this opinion, maintaining that

when comparing India with other countries, the rate at which female entrepreneurship is developing in India is extremely slow, particularly in rural areas. Tiwari (2017) likewise observed that although females make up more than half of the Indian population, their participation in business is highly limited.

Based on the above arguments, there are mixed claims about the participation and development of female entrepreneurs in India. Some claim that there are many opportunities and an increase in the number of female entrepreneurs in India, while others claim that they continue to face challenges and need more support to develop and transform their societal positions. These mixed claims highlight the need for more empirical enquiries examining the position of female entrepreneurs in India and the factors that influence their success. Ansari (2016) argued that the main obstacle for females in India is that they are not eager to change their positions due to social expectations of gender roles, which affect many middle- and lower-class females. If this is the case, instead of examining the factors that influence female entrepreneurs' success, it is essential to examine female entrepreneurs' perceptions of the factors and the influence of these perceptions on their entrepreneurial success. Additionally, due to the evolving nature of the entrepreneurial landscape in India, there is also a need to examine perceptions of both traditional and modern challenges and their influence on entrepreneurial success. Traditional challenges are the traditional practises that limit the activities of female entrepreneurs. Modern challenges are the challenges that female entrepreneurs face due to modernisation, globalisation, evolving work and family roles, and other challenges that make it difficult for them to focus solely on their businesses (Santos *et al.*, 2019).

1.3.5 Rationale and justification for this study in India

The rationale behind investigating this subject lies in the notable difference observed in the distribution of male and female entrepreneurs within the Indian context. The under-representation of female entrepreneurs in entrepreneurial activities, despite females comprising approximately half of the population, underscores the need to study female entrepreneurship in India. A considerable gender gap persists, notwithstanding the equal importance of female entrepreneurs with their male counterparts, as females contribute significantly to economic growth and societal advancement. Female entrepreneurs encounter gender-specific obstacles in India, leading to variations in entrepreneurial involvement between men and women.

Female entrepreneurs in India comprise a lower portion of the population compared to male entrepreneurs, highlighting a substantial gender disparity in the country. Although females form half the population, only 26% of the 63 million Indian Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are owned by females, according to the MSME Ministry's Annual Report 2020-21 (Fegade, Gupta, and Rai, 2023). Female entrepreneurs trail behind male entrepreneurs by 7%, and they represent only 33 % of early-stage entrepreneurs (Rajamani, 2022). India ranks 70th out of 77 nations in the Female's Entrepreneurship Index, which underscores the nation's significant gender disparity in entrepreneurship (Sachdeva, 2023). This entrepreneurial gap is not only a numerical difference but is also rooted deeply in educational, economic, and societal factors. According to Dixit *et al.* (2022), along with patriarchal and societal norms, Indian females also face limited access to entrepreneurial training and education that disadvantages them and positions them behind men.

Female-led businesses are growing due to globalisation and liberalisation (Tiwari, 2022), and there are societal and economic benefits due to the emergence of female entrepreneurs (Kumar and Singh, 2021a). Despite this, the journey of female entrepreneurs is fraught with gender-specific challenges (Joshi, Pandit, and Tiwari, 2022), such as patriarchal beliefs hindering their progress (Chaudhuri, Arora, and Muduli, 2018), gender discrimination in pay and responsibilities (Singh, 2018), and societal norms restricting their freedom and opportunities (Mukherjee and Sen, 2006). Although the Indian entrepreneurial ecosystem is growing, there is a significant difference in the entrepreneurial engagement of men and women (Singh and Singh, 2022). Hence, there is an urgent need to create an environment conducive to female entrepreneurs in India to reduce the gender gap and foster economic empowerment (Khan, 2022). By analysing the key factors influencing female entrepreneurial success, this research aims to 1) uncover the significant factors impacting female entrepreneurs' growth and success as well as how these entrepreneurs perceive these factors, and 2) propose effective policies and interventions for creating a more conducive environment for female entrepreneurs in India.

1.4 Problem Statement

Although many studies have aimed to demystify females in entrepreneurship, with particular emphasis on opportunities and challenges, the underlying challenges continue to exist and attract empirical enquiries into the reasons they have not been dealt with.

Although female entrepreneurs make significant contributions to overall economic growth and development globally, the many challenges they face hinder their progress, including gender bias, social pressure, cultural pressure, and financial constraints

(Aggrawal *et al.*, 2022; Bilgrami, Purohit and Tanwar, 2022; Baral *et al.*, 2023; Gupta and Kaur, 2023).

There is a lack of context-specific studies focusing on the factors that influence the success of female entrepreneurs in India and other developing countries, where social and economic conditions significantly influence the journey of female entrepreneurs (Anandhi, 2022). Suchitra and Pai (2022) noted that there are few context-specific studies on the barriers to female entrepreneurs and few studies with a theoretical basis. Although studies have identified the obstacles to female's growth as entrepreneurs and acknowledged barriers such as lack of family support and gender biases, comprehensive research is still required in this field (Goyal *et al.*, 2022). Literature on female entrepreneurs indicates that females are limited in their participation in entrepreneurship because of social, psychological, environmental, and economic barriers. This highlights a crucial need to investigate the factors responsible for such obstacles and to propose corrective measures (Rajamani, 2022). Hence, this study aims to address this research gap by examining the perception of specific factors that influence the success of female entrepreneurs in India and making corrective recommendations.

1.5 Research Aims

The main aim of this study is to examine the Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of the key factors influencing the success of Indian female entrepreneurs and to provide recommendations for improving the situation. Female entrepreneurial success is measured using a proxy, namely years in business. In addition to the perceptions of personal and environmental factors, perceptions of traditional and modern challenges are also studied as separate constructs/factors influencing female entrepreneurial success.

Each factor represents a distinct set of barriers that women entrepreneurs face. By treating traditional and modern challenges as different factors, the aim is to determine which factor has a greater influence on entrepreneurial success, as measured by a proxy variable—longevity in business (years in business). This approach helps in identifying whether older or newer challenges play a more significant role in predicting longevity in business. Traditional challenges refers to the traditional role of females in the family and the traditional perceptions of people about females in business (Giusta, Marina, and Razzu, 2019). Modern challenges are newer challenges that refer to the challenges associated with globalisation, modernisation, evolving work and family roles, social media perceptions, the high cost of living, increasing expenses towards child education, and recent government policies (Hossain and Rahman, 2018; Kabote, 2018; Kikula, 2018). Analysing these factors separately allows better understanding of their individual contributions and interactions with longevity in business. The perceptions of all the factors are classified as shown in the following Table 1.1:

Table 1.1 Perceptions of factors list

Perceptions of Personal Factors	Perceptions of Environmental Factors	Perceptions of Challenges
1. Perceptions of Business Knowledge	1. Perceptions of Family Support	1. Perceptions of Traditional Challenges
2. Perceptions of Risk-taking Behaviour	2. Perceptions of Social Support	2. Perceptions of Modern Challenges
3. Perceptions of Emotional Intelligence	3. Perceptions of Gender Stereotypes	
	4. Perceptions of Technological Advancements	

	5. Perceptions of Government Policies	
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1.6 Research Objectives

1. To examine perceptions of personal factors of Indian female entrepreneurs, such as business knowledge (BK), risk-taking behaviour (RB), and emotional intelligence (EI), that influence their success as measured through years in business (YIB).
2. To examine perceptions of environmental factors of Indian female entrepreneurs, such as family support (FS), social support (SS), gender stereotypes (GS), technological advancements (TA), and government policies (GP) that influence their success as measured through years in business (YIB).
3. To examine perceptions of challenges of Indian female entrepreneurs, including traditional challenges (TC) and modern challenges (MC), that influence their success as measured through years in business (YIB).

1.7 Research Questions

1. Do perceptions of specific personal factors such as business knowledge (BK), risk-taking behaviour (RB), and emotional intelligence (EI) related to female entrepreneurial success predict years in business for female entrepreneurs in India?
2. Do perceptions of specific environmental factors such as family support (FS), social support (SS), gender stereotypes (GS), technological advancements (TA),

- and government policies (GP) related to female entrepreneurial success predict years in business for female entrepreneurs in India?
3. Do perceptions of specific traditional (TC) and modern challenges (MC) related to female entrepreneurial success predict years in business for female entrepreneurs in India?

1.8 Research Hypothesis

The study tests three hypotheses and their sub-hypotheses using data collected from female entrepreneurs in India. A list of research hypotheses based on the research questions is provided in Table 1.2 below.

Table 1.2 Research Hypotheses

Research Question 1: Do perceptions of specific personal factors (BK, RB, EI) related to female entrepreneurial success predict years in business (YIB) for female entrepreneurs in India?	
H1: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of personal factors (BK, RB, and EI) significantly predict years in business.	
H1a	Perceptions of business knowledge (BK) significantly predict years in business.
H1b	Perceptions of risk-taking behaviour (RB) significantly predict years in business.
H1c	Perceptions of emotional intelligence (EI) significantly predict years in business.
Research Question 2: Do perceptions of specific environmental factors (FS, SS, GS, TA, and GP) related to female entrepreneurial success predict years in business (YIB) for female entrepreneurs in India?	
H2: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of environmental factors (FS, SS, GS, TA, and GP) significantly predict years in business.	
H2a	Perceptions of family support (FS) significantly predict years in business.
H2b	Perceptions of social support (SS) significantly predict years in business.
H2c	Perceptions of gender stereotypes (GS) significantly predict years in business.
H2d	Perceptions of technological advancements (TA) significantly predict years in business.
H2e	Perceptions of government policies (GP) significantly predict years in business.

Research Question 3: Do perceptions of specific traditional and modern challenges related to female entrepreneurial success predict years in business (YIB) for female entrepreneurs in India?	
H3: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of business challenges (TC and MC) significantly predict years in business.	
H3a	Perceptions of traditional challenges (TC) significantly predict years in business.
H3b	Perceptions of modern challenges (MC) significantly predict years in business.

1.9 Study significance

This research is founded on existing empirical evidence and seeks to bridge the knowledge gaps concerning female entrepreneurship in India. The significance of the study is summarised as follows.

This study addresses a research gap and provides a more nuanced understanding of the female entrepreneurial landscape. It focuses on female entrepreneurs in India from diverse backgrounds and their perceptions of the specific factors of and challenges to their success. There is currently a lack of focused research on their perceptions of these factors and challenges.

Female entrepreneurs who continue to face challenges, anticipate engaging in entrepreneurial activities, and are already established entrepreneurs will benefit from this research, which seeks to provide a platform for their voices and experiences.

Not many studies have used quantitative techniques and particularly regression modelling to identify perceptions of barriers and challenges for female entrepreneurs in India (Arora and Agarwal, 2019; Amrita *et al.*, 2022; Chhabra, Singh, and Mehdi, 2022; Agrawal *et al.*, 2023; Baral *et al.*, 2023). For instance, the study on women entrepreneurs in India by Amrita *et al.* (2022) has used an integrated model based on fuzzy AHP and fuzzy

TOPSIS to recommend the strategies for the development of female entrepreneurs and overcoming the barriers. While some research has addressed these issues using systematic literature reviews, such as the study by Baral *et al.* (2023), there is a noticeable gap in applying statistical methods to provide a clearer, data-driven understanding. This research collects primary data from female entrepreneurs in India using a survey questionnaire and measures their success through years in business as a proxy. This study is a pioneering attempt in this regard, and this methodological contribution provides a foundation for further research by offering more robust analyses and conclusions.

This research provides a framework for future studies and sets a precedent. Its methodology and findings can be a practical model for similar studies in India and other developing nations. More empirical studies are needed to understand female entrepreneurial obstacles and success comprehensively, and this research offers tangible insights that can inform policymakers and support structures.

Though the study focuses on India, its insights can advance discussions on female entrepreneurship globally by identifying trends, patterns, and answers that can inform strategies in various contexts in other developing countries.

Practical recommendations on policy formulation can help to develop strategies for governmental and non-governmental organisations and institutions that work for female's empowerment, education, and training.

Overall, this study makes valuable academic and practical contributions to comprehending perceptions of factors that influence the success of Indian female entrepreneurs.

1.10 Research scope and boundaries

The research scope and boundaries are important for providing a clear focus and delimiting the research. The scope and boundaries are as follows.

The primary demographic limitation is gender; this study focuses specifically on female entrepreneurs. Second, this research is restricted to India, narrowing it geographically and providing insights that are particularly relevant to the Indian context.

Within the broad category of female entrepreneurs, this study further narrows its focus to those females who are active entrepreneurs running their business in India. However, the study does not restrict them in terms of sectors, industries, or any specific region. The reason for this broader scope is to obtain a comprehensive understanding of perceptions of the challenges faced by female entrepreneurs from diverse backgrounds. Most of the studies in the literature are sector-specific or region-specific, which restricts understanding of the barriers and challenges they face and limits results in terms of generalisability. Hence, this study includes female entrepreneurs who are self-employed or actively running a business with any number of employees for any duration within the formal or informal sector at any location within India.

The choice of a quantitative methodology using surveys to gather data limits the study to quantitative data. This offers measurable and statistically analysable insights, but it does not delve into qualitative aspects such as in-depth personal experiences or case studies.

This study does not encompass all the barriers and hurdles that female entrepreneurs encounter but instead concentrates on their opinions regarding key barriers like personal and environmental factors, along with challenges like traditional and modern obstacles. By establishing these specific boundaries, the study seeks to offer a concentrated and comprehensive understanding of the identified factors and challenges, presenting significant perspectives on the realm of female entrepreneurship in India.

Overall, the scope and boundaries of the research are limited by gender, country, methodology, status, and specific factors and challenges.

1.11 Overview of the methodology

This study employs a quantitative research design and a survey strategy for data collection. This is well-suited to statistical analyses and collecting data from a larger sample of female entrepreneurs in India to understand their challenges and barriers. Factor analysis was conducted on the initial questionnaire to validate the survey questionnaire, ensure its effectiveness, and capture the required data. The research focuses on active female entrepreneurs in India, with eligibility criteria including being self-employed or running a business and being actively involved in its operation. This ensures a comprehensive understanding of the female entrepreneurial landscape in India. Data was collected using online platforms and then analysed using statistical tests such as multinomial logistic regression to predict the outcome variable 'Years in Business', which is a proxy used to measure female entrepreneurial success and derive meaningful conclusions and insights.

1.12 Organisation of the study

The research document is divided into six chapters that encompass an introductory section, a review of relevant literature, the methodological techniques used, an analysis of the primary data and findings, a discussion of the results, and a conclusion.

The first chapter introduces readers to the research study by describing and outlining elements such as a brief introduction of the entrepreneurial landscape in India, followed by an overview of female entrepreneurs and defining female entrepreneurial success for this study. It also provides the research context, including an overview of the entrepreneurship context in India, specific barriers faced by female entrepreneurs in India, and the impact of Covid-19 on female entrepreneurs in the country. Furthermore, it discusses the female entrepreneurs in India and presents the justification and significance of the investigation. The chapter also introduces the problem statement, outlines the aims and objectives to be met, questions to be addressed, and introduces the hypotheses for the research. Additionally, the chapter defines the scope and boundaries of the research. It also gives an overview of the methodology and explains how the study is organised.

In the second chapter, the researcher presents a comprehensive review of both theoretical and empirical literature on the topic. The chapter also covers the development of a conceptual framework and hypothesis to be tested and identifies the main gaps in the literature.

The third chapter focuses on describing and justifying the choice of methodology.

The fourth chapter presents and interprets the empirical investigation results based on the adopted methodology.

The fifth chapter presents a comprehensive discussion of the results, their implications, and contributions, followed by limitations and future research directions.

The last chapter presents the conclusion and practical recommendations of the study.

The list of references used, and appendices are attached in the subsequent sections, as outlined in Figure 1.1 below.

Figure 1.1 Dissertation Structure (Author)

Chapter 2 Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This literature review provides an in-depth examination of the multifaceted aspects of female entrepreneurship, with a particular focus on the Indian context. Beginning with a section providing background information on the concept of entrepreneurship, it highlights the significance of female entrepreneurs and the unique challenges they face. The chapter delves into the complexity of female entrepreneurship by discussing the specific problems female entrepreneurs encounter, particularly in India. It further discusses the various factors influencing their success, including personal and environmental factors and challenges. The theoretical framework section offers an overview of the theory of planned behaviour and its strengths and weaknesses and justifies its application in this context. The chapter then identifies research gaps, emphasising the need for more studies in the Indian context, the scarcity of empirical findings, and the necessity for conceptual frameworks and practical solutions tailored to female entrepreneurs in India. Hypothesis development related to personal factors, environmental factors, challenges, and the impact of COVID-19 is also discussed. Finally, the chapter concludes with a brief summary of the key points covered.

2.2 Background information

This background section helps to contextualise the research and provides an understanding of the topic, starting from the broader concept of entrepreneurship; this establishes a foundation for this research as well as helps to elucidate how entrepreneurship is defined by different scholars globally and its evolution over time.

Furthermore, it briefly elaborates on the primary benefits of entrepreneurship. The significance of female entrepreneurship is then discussed, emphasising its impact and crucial role in the economy and societal development on a global level. Lastly, the section outlines the challenges faced by female entrepreneurs in developing countries.

2.2.1 The concept of entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship has many definitions but can be viewed primarily as identifying new and profitable opportunities and organising resources to undertake such ventures. In the view of Gaddefors and Anderson (2017), entrepreneurship refers to the readiness and ability to organise, develop, and run an enterprise while being cognisant of potential uncertainties regarding making significant profits. However, in the context of this research on female entrepreneurs, entrepreneurship refers to the readiness and ability to organise, develop, and run an enterprise, being cognisant of the potential uncertainties, with the goal of sustaining the business over a long duration (adapted from Gaddefors and Anderson, 2017). By focusing on the goal of sustaining the business over a long period of time, this definition underscores the importance of stability and longevity. This is particularly relevant in the context of female entrepreneurs in India, who may prioritise creating resilient businesses that endure despite various challenges rather than solely focusing on immediate profit.

In economics, entrepreneurship is based on combined factors or resources for production towards profit-making, including land, labour, capital, and natural resources (Yetisen *et al.*, 2015). Entrepreneurship is the most important aspect of economic development in society. A common form of entrepreneurship is when new businesses are founded on innovative ideas. However, Diochon and Anderson (2011) noted that entrepreneurship is

mainly about value addition, in which case it goes beyond economics to include changes in society. Diochon and Anderson (2011) agreed with Gaddefors and Anderson (2017) that the most important aspect of entrepreneurship is the ability to assume the risks associated with starting a business, which often starts as a small venture with the desire to generate profits. Whether it entails a new business venture or developing an existing business idea, the individuals involved in such ventures are entrepreneurs, irrespective of gender or other societal statuses.

Entrepreneurship dates back to the 17th and 18th centuries, when it consisted of the art of buying a product and reselling it at uncertain prices. This involved decision-making on using and obtaining resources and the ability to accept enterprise-associated risks (Stevenson and Jarillo, 2007). This dynamic emphasises the entrepreneur's willingness to accept risk as a way of dealing with uncertainty, stressing the difference between an owner who provides funds for business and an entrepreneur (Stevenson and Jarillo, 2007). Later, Jean-Baptiste Say identified entrepreneurs as the drivers of economic growth and development due to their role in mobilising the factors of production and allocating scarce resources to more productive areas (Lowe and Marriott, 2006). This view concurs with Yetisen *et al.* (2015). It is impossible to separate entrepreneurship from other factors of production in economics.

Despite assertions about entrepreneurship that have been expressed since the 17th and 18th centuries, a fundamental shift in the concept occurred in the 20th century based on studies carried out by Joseph Schumpeter (Schumpeter, 1976). According to Schumpeter (1976), an individual might be regarded as an entrepreneur if they transformed an invention or idea into an efficacious product by employing the power of inventive

destruction. For Schumpeter, the most important trait distinguishing entrepreneurs from others in society is the ability to eliminate inferior offerings from the market, creating new disruptive products and new models (Jones and Murtola, 2012). Through this destructive innovation, sustainability in business operations is achieved. Schumpeter (1976) thus differed from previous scholars due to his emphasis on new productions and markets and his theory of destructive innovation. 18th-century authors opined that if an individual could pay a consideration or price towards a service or product and then resell it later by charging a specific margin for profitability, such a person is an entrepreneur. Schumpeter, however, disagreed with that definition (Jones and Murtola, 2012).

Another management guru named Israel Kirzner contributed to the debate on definitions in 1930 by asserting that entrepreneurs need not establish an idea from scratch but may attain their goals through incremental improvements in innovations. This notion required no particular or special qualities except bringing into existence more value for what had already been invented (Jones and Murtola, 2012). In this view, entrepreneurship is mainly about progressive creativity to enhance the value of existing products and to improve efficiency in meeting social demands. Contrary to Schumpeter's definition, where entrepreneurship often results in new markets, products, and innovations, Kirzner did not envisage new industries as the necessary result of entrepreneurship. Rather, Kirzner argued for better solutions to social problems as a result of entrepreneurship (Jones and Murtola, 2012).

Schumpeter did not consider an entrepreneur to be one who incurred risks because risks were borne by capitalists in economics. The Schumpeterian perspective is strongly rooted in the idea that the business environment always provides sufficient and new information

that can create equilibrium in the allocation of resources for profitability (Schumpeter, 1934). Schumpeter (1934) believed that individuals can gain new information ahead of others and take advantage of this by combining resources to attain profits as entrepreneurs.

In the 21st century, a new facet of entrepreneurship has been introduced that has shifted the focus from profitability to social entrepreneurship, where pursuing business goals is accompanied by other concerns, such as the environment, social welfare, and political interests (Shane, 2000). Entrepreneurs are leaders who are willing and capable of taking significant risks. They demonstrate high levels of creativity by taking advantage of market opportunities and organising, deploying, and planning resources—often in an innovative manner—to ensure the creation of new products or an improvement of existing products (Johnson, 2005). The major benefits of entrepreneurship are the same across the different categories, although there could be slight differences in purposes and goals (Carlen, 2016). Entrepreneurship is an important societal concept due to its impact on economic growth and development and also offers other benefits, such as creating employment opportunities, enhancing innovation, promoting community and society developments, increasing the standard of living, and promoting research and development (Chaudhary, 2015). Even in a developing country like India, despite challenges such as government instability and policy changes, entrepreneurship is a key contributor to economic development, suggesting a focus on enhancing the quality of entrepreneurship (Golden and Regi, 2018).

2.2.2 Significance of female entrepreneurship

Female entrepreneurship holds immense significance within the realms of economic progress, empowerment, and gender parity (Brush, de Bruin, and Welter, 2009; World Bank, 2019). Female entrepreneurs often bring unique perspectives and approaches to business, influenced by their experiences, challenges, and societal roles. They play a vital role in societal development and global economic growth, with significant contributions in various aspects (McKinsey Global Institute, 2015; International Labour Organisation, 2016). First, female entrepreneurs often invest in their communities, promoting social cohesion and development. According to a study by the International Labour Organisation (2016), females are more likely to reinvest profits into their families and communities, enhancing education, health, and social services. Second, enterprises run by females play a crucial role in fostering economic diversification and generating employment opportunities. Research by the McKinsey Global Institute (2015) indicates that advancing female equality through entrepreneurship could add \$12 trillion to global GDP by 2025. To explain the impact of how female enterprises can generate employment opportunities, the following Figure 2.1 evaluates the impact of entrepreneurs on the

economy based on employment creation.

Figure 2.1 Impact of Entrepreneurship on Employment (Kritikos, 2020)

According to Figure 2.1, as presented by Kritikos (2020), the S-shaped curve that emerges as the impact of a new business establishment on employment is a matter of debate, based on data from the United States and European countries. In the first phase, new entrants, due to increased entrepreneurship among males and females, introduce new capacities. This is evident within the first year of operation. In the second phase, such capacities place pressure on existing firms, whose competitiveness is reduced, resulting in the new firms gaining a large proportion of the market share. Two effects are experienced: the creation of jobs by the new firms and the loss of job opportunities in the existing firms. The third-most important phase is when the new products introduced to the market create increased demand, meaning that production volume must be increased, thus creating more job opportunities. Kritikos (2020) argued that the long-term effects of entrepreneurship on the economy are positive, as more job opportunities imply a better living standard, increased revenue for the government, and overall economic growth and

development. These arguments coincide as well as diverge with the views of Helmers and Rogers (2010). The following Figure 2.2 presents the survival scenario of new entrants, especially for the first five years.

Figure 2.2 Survival of New Firms (Helmers and Rogers, 2010)

Helmers and Rogers (2010) asserted that the survival rate of new firms established by new entrepreneurs in the first five years is higher than in the later period, implying that few firms can persist beyond the first five years. As seen in Figure 2.2, less than 40% of new companies in the United Kingdom survive beyond the first five years. In the early years, new firms introduce more employment opportunities, but when they fail and close, the workforce initially developed by such firms remains unemployed. Helmers and Rogers's argument places Kritikos's assertions (2020) in perspective. As Figure 2.2 shows, overall employment opportunities drop since existing firms fail to match up to the new competition and close, creating disequilibrium in the economy for employment opportunities. However, this reduction of employment is often corrected by the few firms that persist beyond five years, whose new products are in demand, and who eventually absorb the jobless population in society. This suggests that female entrepreneurs can be

among the few starters who go beyond five years and can significantly impact the economy by creating job opportunities.

While these insights highlight the significance of female entrepreneurs and their impact on the economy, it is important to note that much of our knowledge comes from the Western context, and therefore there is a need to conduct studies in the Indian context, as the Western perspective may not fully capture the factors that influence female entrepreneurial success in other contexts. In the Western context, aspects like financial accessibility, market prospects, and the balance between work and personal life are frequently emphasised as crucial for the success of females in entrepreneurship (Brush *et al.*, 2009). However, in the Indian context, additional obstacles such as societal norms, gender prejudices, familial obligations, and restricted educational and networking opportunities can have a significant impact on shaping the entrepreneurial environment for females (De Vita, Mari, and Poggesi, 2014). These contextual variations indicate that the determinants influencing the success of female entrepreneurs in India may be unique and necessitate localised examination to formulate effective support mechanisms.

Female entrepreneurs' growth and development also help reduce gender disparities and empower females, aligning with the Sustainable Development Goals Report on gender equality and economic growth (United Nations, 2019). Moreover, female entrepreneurship promotes innovation and resilience. Females are innovative and creative and can thus introduce new products and services, contributing to market expansion and diversity (Elam *et al.*, 2019). These points underscore the critical importance of female entrepreneurship globally.

Females have become increasingly involved in other areas of society, such as leadership and politics, policy formulation, research, and development, especially since the 20th century. With developments and changes in society, such as increased access to education, training, and employment, more females have become business owners in sectors ranging from small to large professional enterprises (Tinkler *et al.*, 2015). The desire to own properties and businesses has drastically grown among females just as it has for their counterparts, raising an international conversation on the importance, relevance, and potential challenges female entrepreneurs face in the modern environment (Orser and Elliott, 2015). With the evolution of the business environment and other areas, such as technology, the increasing number of female leaders in business and entrepreneurship have faced a fundamental change in the problems they experience (Alsos and Ljunggren, 2016). These problems are discussed in the next section in the context of developing countries.

2.2.3 Complexity in female entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is a socially embedded area that must be appreciated not simply as an economic process but as a social process that yields economic outcomes (Ojediran and Alistair, 2020). Moreover, entrepreneurship supports social empowerment for those involved, including females (Ojediran and Alistair, 2020). Unfortunately, many institutions globally have created a gender divide, whether informal or formal, political, social, or cultural, leading to an overall situation where female entrepreneurship is perceived as second-class, inferior, and subjugated. The main factors that have subordinated the efforts of females in business and reduced opportunities for them are patriarchy, culture, and tradition. Contrary to this claim of reduced opportunities for

female entrepreneurs, Sujit (2014) argued that although entrepreneurship is an old phenomenon, female entrepreneurship is relatively new in many economies, indicating that there are tremendous opportunities in the current environment, yet Sujit (2014) suggested that little or no effort has been made to stabilise the concept of female entrepreneurship, leading to its slow growth rate and success. In this regard, Sujit (2014) clarified that the main opportunity existing for female entrepreneurs is founded in motivation factors and individual choices, as these form the basis of a favourable environment and furnish the necessary support for success.

One of the greatest drivers of economic growth and opportunities in society is entrepreneurship, as observed by numerous policymakers and researchers (Meyer, 2018). Although studies have been undertaken on the issue of entrepreneurial opportunities, efforts have not been made to make the research gender-specific. Conducting gender-specific research is important because of the notable gender gap and under-representation of females despite their significant contributions to the economy and society. Females have continued to face numerous challenges and have fewer opportunities than their male counterparts (Meyer, 2018). In particular, Meyer (2018) highlighted issues related to cultural beliefs and gender roles, asset ownership, lack of confidence, and perceptions of capability. A clear focus on the barriers facing female entrepreneurs could be a much-needed opportunity to demystify the issue and lead to improvements and developments in female entrepreneurship. One recommendation to promote opportunities includes deliberate efforts to formulate and implement policies that are gender-specific (Meyer, 2018).

Opportunities for female entrepreneurs have long been limited by social formation and environment (Santos, Roomi, and Linan, 2018). Social legitimacy for entrepreneurship continues to reinforce male entrepreneurial intentions while discouraging those of females (Santos, Roomi, and Linan, 2018). Santos *et al.* (2018) and Meyer (2018) both asserted that these limitations hold for almost all regions globally, which could explain why entrepreneurship is not felt as an attractive career for females around the world, not just in India. Mending the social and cultural dimensions of female entrepreneurship would create an enabling environment for female leaders in business.

2.2.4 Problems facing female entrepreneurs in developing countries

Although female entrepreneurs play a significant role in the economy (check section 2.2.2 Significance of female entrepreneurship), their entrepreneurial journey is not easy, and they face numerous barriers to commencing and growing successful businesses. Examining the challenges they face is important to unlock female entrepreneurs' potential and foster inclusive growth, innovation, and societal well-being.

Lack of access to financing is one of the barriers that females often encounter. They often face more difficulties in obtaining loans and investment capital than men. According to a report by the World Bank (2019), female entrepreneurs are 20% less likely to secure financing compared to men due to gender biases and stricter collateral requirements. This financial exclusion limits their ability to start and grow businesses, ultimately impacting their economic empowerment and business sustainability. The constraints facing female entrepreneurs make it difficult for them to access finance, but more importantly, they contribute to conflicts between family and work responsibilities, a lack of management skills and education, difficulties in sourcing raw materials, and networking challenges

(Sumaira, Madiha, and Wasim, 2013; Mauchi, Mutengezanwa, and Damiyano, 2014). In addition to economic problems, other limitations faced by females include political, social, and family problems, and these limitations persist despite the enormous benefits brought about by female entrepreneurs, such as the creation of job opportunities and enhancing female empowerment (Nayef, 2016).

Additionally, traditional norms and family responsibilities often discourage females from pursuing entrepreneurship, leading to a lack of support from family and communities.

The International Labour Organisation (2016) highlights that in many regions, females are expected to prioritise household responsibilities over business activities, which restricts their entrepreneurial ambitions and opportunities. Motherhood and household responsibilities were among the key issues affecting female entrepreneurship success, in addition to the lack of finances and entrepreneurship skills (Ogundana *et al.*, 2021).

Ogundana *et al.* (2021) suggested that the overburdening of female entrepreneurs by family obligations reduced their time to venture into business. Agrawal *et al.* (2023) echoed Ogundana *et al.* (2021) in a study examining challenges faced by female entrepreneurs in South Asian developing countries, where insights revealed that the high load of familial responsibilities affected their success in entrepreneurship. This burden reduces the time females can dedicate to their businesses, often forcing them to abandon their entrepreneurial goals to focus on their familial responsibilities.

Although the role of female entrepreneurs is integral in the post-modern era in growing economies nationally and internationally, several challenges have significantly reduced the success rates achieved (Chinomona and Maziriri, 2015). Females continue to face challenges including gender discrimination, lack of financial accessibility, inadequate

resources, lack of training and education, and negative attitudes among females (Chinomona and Maziriri, 2015; Nayef, 2016). Further challenges include gendered stereotypes and limited support networks that discourage females from engaging in entrepreneurship. Females face gender stereotypes that question their capabilities as entrepreneurs. Limited access to networking and mentorship opportunities further exacerbates this challenge. These limitations hinder females' ability to gain valuable advice and support essential for business growth (Elam *et al.*, 2019). Such stereotypes and social expectations contribute to stress and burnout, making it difficult for females to sustain their business ventures (Petterson, 2019).

The entrepreneurial ecosystem and business environment in many developing countries remain male-dominated, creating an unfavourable environment for females (Cheng, 2018; Naina, 2018). An online publication on Indian female entrepreneurs by Naina (2018) observed that it is challenging for female business leaders to coordinate effectively with their male counterparts, and in some countries a male partner is required to finalise business deals (Cheng, 2018). This dynamic further marginalises female entrepreneurs, limiting their opportunities and reinforcing gender inequality. Mauchi, Mutengezanwa, and Damiyano (2014) posited that there are few female entrepreneurs despite numerous efforts to promote societal recognition of female entrepreneurs, particularly in the economic development role. Their work suggests that female-owned business growth has remained relatively subdued, partly due to gender role challenges. Such challenges lower female's work efficiency and performance in the establishment of business entities compared to male entrepreneurs.

In India, the modern environment offers business opportunities for females, yet the male-dominated culture poses problems such as balancing family and career, socio-cultural barriers, low education levels, a lack of financial support, and low self-confidence (Gaur, Vijay, and Ravi, 2018). Despite social and political advancements, government support, and increased awareness, female entrepreneurship in India is still underdeveloped due to the male-dominated culture (Gaur, Vijay, and Ravi, 2018). Additional challenges Agrawal *et al.* (2023) highlighted included the lack of entrepreneurship education, management skills, and infrastructural support.

A relationship exists between gender and entrepreneurial culture, and for a long time females have not been considered as resolute as men in implementing entrepreneurial ideas (Seenivasan, 2014). However, societal norms and culture have played a major role in this trend, suggesting that further research should demystify the issue of cultural and gender perceptions of entrepreneurship (Seenivasan, 2014). The main limitation is founded on the premise of the motivations, characteristics, and obstacles that appear in society that make females reluctant to embrace business opportunities, namely, accessibility to external funding and resources (Belwal, Belwal, and Fatema, 2014).

Females can be disadvantaged in the business arena because of cultural diversities, especially in developing countries where ownership of important resources and assets, such as land, is restricted to men, making it challenging for females to mobilise resources to implement their envisaged business ideas (Kikula, 2018); this leads to the challenge of a lack of capital and applies to start-ups and already existing ventures because capital is important in enhancing the expansion and growth of business entities (Kikula, 2018).

There is a need to explore alternative strategies that can change perceptions of the role of

females and promote capacity-building. Cultural differences and beliefs that give rise to challenges to female-owned businesses and are founded on male dominance, mobility, competition, and risk-bearing capacity should be minimised to allow for the establishment of female-owned businesses (Basit *et al.*, 2020).

While there is a shift concerning gender roles in business activities, much still needs to be done to promote females in business leadership. Although females have made tremendous progress, the 21st century has also introduced new challenges, including globalisation, social media influence, and technological developments (Zainuddin *et al.*, 2017). Zainuddin *et al.* (2017) recommended that future research study the causal relationship between new challenges and female entrepreneurs.

Contrary to the general view of familial obligations hindering female entrepreneurs, Jaim (2022) found that in Bangladesh, females received help from family members to facilitate their business activities. This support challenges the assumption that family responsibilities universally restrict female's entrepreneurial success and suggests that cultural variations exist within developing countries. Chinomona and Maziriri (2015) observed a slow but positive cultural shift, arguing that modern societies are gradually moving towards shared responsibilities without a strict focus on gender roles. While acknowledging that the pace of change is slow, they highlighted that efforts are being made to reduce gender inequalities, suggesting a potential future where females can engage in entrepreneurship without disproportionate domestic burdens. Nonetheless, females who have been successful entrepreneurs have been motivated by an urge to balance work and life, an intention to utilise an opportunity to take advantage of a

potential market niche, and the desire to search for better or more stable work (Belwal, Belwal, and Fatema, 2014).

While seeking to understand the specific challenges slowing the rate at which females engage in business activities, little focus has been placed on the role played by the government in supporting female entrepreneurs (Vijayakumar and Jayachitra, 2013). In many developing countries, governments could buffer the entrepreneurial challenges centred on gender disparity by promoting vocational training and education targeting female empowerment (Vijayakumar and Jayachitra, 2013). However, there needs to be an acknowledgement that governments have several duties and responsibilities, and female entrepreneurial development and training are not the only responsibilities of the government in India. Other non-governmental stakeholders are key to supporting various programmes aimed at eliminating the bottlenecks that females face while exploring their business ambitions.

Female entrepreneurship needs to be a priority as the proportion of females to men is, in general, greater, creating a need to empower females for sustainable economic development (Hossain and Rahman, 2018). The inclusion of females in business would result in multiple benefits for society, including cost efficiency, improved access to information, enhancement of network-building, product development and improvement, work-life balance, technical adaptability, and entrepreneurial opportunities (Gaur, Vijay, and Ravi, 2018; Hossain and Rahman, 2018).

Basit *et al.* (2020) argued that the success of female entrepreneurs depends on factors ranging from policies in place to females' personality types. Key aspects include work experience attained in terms of developing skills, competencies acquired over time, and

overall industrial know-how (Basit *et al.*, 2020). As a result, aspiring female entrepreneurs should be involved in continuous learning to attain relevant competencies or skills, industrial know-how, and knowledge that can potentially sharpen their competitive advantage in promoting growth and development and enhancing the sustainability of business enterprises (Basit *et al.*, 2020). Despite the challenges, many females have succeeded in entrepreneurship, serving as role models. Fernandes and Sanfilippo (2020) pointed to successful female entrepreneurs like Oprah Winfrey and Sheryl Sandberg as illustrations that societal norms are not impossible barriers. These success stories inspire and pave the way for other females to pursue entrepreneurial ventures. While significant barriers such as lack of access to finance, traditional norms and family responsibilities, gender stereotypes, limited support networks, and a male-dominated business environment persist, there are counterarguments and evidence of positive changes as well as successful female entrepreneurs who have overcome these hurdles.

Classification of problems facing female entrepreneurs in the literature

These problems impacting female entrepreneurs are classified into several broad factors in the literature to understand their impact on the female entrepreneurial landscape. Naina (2018) and Cheng (2018) proposed that female difficulties in business can be categorised as social, economic, political, cultural, and leadership-based. With this in mind, three main categories of challenges for female entrepreneurs have been proposed: technical, social/personal, and business challenges (Sumaira, Madiha, and Wasim, 2013). Technical problems include shortages of electricity, working capital, skills, and raw materials. Social or personal problems include role conflict, lack of education, lack of community,

lack of related field experience, and an unfavourable market. Lastly, business problems include problems with finance, management, marketing, and hiring. Fernandes and Sanfilippo (2020) suggested that beyond societal and economic barriers, psychological factors significantly impact female's entrepreneurial success. Issues like lack of self-confidence and internal motivation are crucial. However, some females have overcome these challenges, indicating that personal resilience and determination can lead to success despite external obstacles. As mentioned by Fernandes and Sanfilippo (2020), there are psychological factors that are personal and internal to female that significantly affect female's entrepreneurial success. This implies that to understand the factors that impact the success of female entrepreneurs, it is important to understand female's own perceptions of these factors and how their success is influenced by them. Addressing this requires a nuanced understanding of the varied opinions of females across different contexts. This research focuses on the Indian context and aims to examine female entrepreneurs' perceptions of the key factors impacting the success of female entrepreneurs in India.

Based on the background information, we can make the following assumptions. First, entrepreneurship is crucial for societal development and economic growth, regardless of gender involvement. Second, the importance of females in the economy and society is understated. Third, females have historically encountered numerous problems that their male counterparts have not faced. These problems have been classified into various factors in the literature to understand their impact on female entrepreneurship (Sumaira, Madiha, and Wasim, 2013; Cheng, 2018; Naina, 2018). Examining the factors that impact the success of female entrepreneurs is crucial. To examine these factors, it is

necessary to understand the perceptions of female entrepreneurs regarding these factors and how these perceptions influence their success.

2.3 Factors that influence the success of female entrepreneurs

Perceptions of specific factors influencing the success of female entrepreneurs in India are classified into three types in the current study: personal factors, environmental factors, and challenges. Each factor and the literature related to it are discussed in the following section.

2.3.1 Personal factors

2.3.1.1 Business knowledge

The government of India has implemented various schemes to assist female entrepreneurs, emphasising the need for skills training, vocational education, and entrepreneurial development to empower females economically (Sachdeva, 2023). However, despite these efforts, female entrepreneurs face several challenges, including a lack of appropriate training, skills development, and literacy, which are key obstacles to their development (Sayeed, 2023). Though the participation of females in entrepreneurial activities has increased in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in India, the economic position of females remains difficult, underscoring the need for specific training facilities to help females overcome these challenges and develop their skills (Rajamani, 2022). The entrepreneurial environment in India continues to exhibit limited progression in female entrepreneurship in contrast to other nations, underscoring the importance of ongoing education and skills enhancement to empower females to succeed in business administration and decision-making procedures (Abrar ul Haq, Victor, and Akram, 2020;

Devi, 2023). Research indicates that motivational influences, perceived viability, and entrepreneurial ability significantly impact the actions of female entrepreneurs. Training designed to address these areas has yielded significant results, suggesting that targeted educational initiatives can enhance female's entrepreneurial intentions and success (Goyal, 2021).

Financial and marketing problems, such as shortage of working capital and difficulty in selling goods, are prominent among startup female entrepreneurs (Sathiyabama *et al.*, 2021). These insights collectively underscore the critical need for business knowledge and support systems tailored to the unique challenges and opportunities faced by female entrepreneurs in India. To provide tailored support, it is essential to study the perceptions of female entrepreneurs in India regarding business knowledge and its influence on their success.

2.3.1.2 Risk-taking behaviour

One of the components influencing success and entrepreneurial activities is risk-taking, and entrepreneurs must be willing to bear substantial risks if greater success is to be achieved (Oluwatoyin, 2012). Oluwatoyin (2012) observed that the number of females in business increased drastically after the economic recession, but their range of activities is limited even in contemporary society. The reason for low growth rates among female entrepreneurs can be associated with an unwillingness to take risks. These assertions are upheld by Boermans and Willebrands (2017), who posited that the level of firm performance reflects the extent of the risks and that risk behaviour among females in business is closely associated with their skills and personality types.

Risk-taking behaviour derives from the attitude an individual develops towards the returns of an investment or effort (Yoopetch, 2021). Yoopetch (2021) reinforced the assumptions of Boermans and Willebrands (2017) that in a situation where an attitude developed supports the adoption of higher risks, success or failure rates are likely to be higher and commensurate to the risk type and magnitude. This is the foundation on which females' behaviours towards risks are shaped, depending on the magnitude of the risks anticipated. Risk-taking should be justified by the anticipated economic benefits and opportunity costs, depending on the individuals' attitudes.

Furthermore, females' risk behaviour is influenced by their perceptions of opportunities and barriers within the business landscape. This perception shapes their willingness to engage in risk-taking, as females may weigh the potential economic benefits against perceived obstacles more cautiously. Female's perceptions and their assessment of these variables are crucial in shaping their entrepreneurship decision-making processes, consequently impacting their business outcomes (Giusta, Marina, and Razzu, 2019).

Therefore, risk-taking behaviour is a crucial component impacting entrepreneurial success, but gender differences significantly influence this behaviour. Female's lower growth rates in entrepreneurship can be attributed to a more cautious approach to risk, driven by their skills, personalities, and perceptions of the business environment.

2.3.1.3 Emotional intelligence

Emotional intelligence (EI) is essential for entrepreneurial success, although its exact impact is still debated. EI enhances resilience and innovation, both of which are crucial for navigating the challenges of entrepreneurship (Ngah and Salleh, 2015). Entrepreneurs equipped with EI are believed to demonstrate greater confidence, empathy, and social

skills, facilitating better business and interpersonal relations (Ranjitha, 2017). This argument extends to gender dynamics, with claims that females, due to their ability to manage multiple responsibilities, exhibit higher EI, which translates into business success through strong interpersonal skills (Ranjitha, 2017). Supporting this, Gautam and Khurana (2018) posited that social skills and knowledge, as antecedents of EI, are foundational for enterprise growth and start-up stimulation. They predicted that entrepreneurs integrating EI into their business practises are more likely to achieve higher success levels. Additionally, research indicates that workplaces fostering EI experience higher employee performance, indirectly boosting entrepreneurial outcomes (Kannaiah and Shanthi, 2015; Kaur and Sharma, 2019). Kaur and Sharma (2019) maintained that successful entrepreneurs need leadership skills underpinned by EI, further supporting its importance in entrepreneurial development.

However, the direct impact of EI on entrepreneurial success is contested. Swift (2013) hypothesised that establishing a direct link between EI and entrepreneurship is challenging due to difficulties in measuring the effects of emotional intelligence on business outcomes. Despite this critique, Khatoon (2013) noted that EI significantly enhances social effects, which are integral to individual and business performance, thus reinforcing its relevance to entrepreneurial success. This view is supported by Ngah and Salleh (2015) and Ranjitha (2017), who held that EI is crucial for flourishing entrepreneurship.

Furthermore, EI's influence on success is also notable. Papoutsis, Drigas, and Skianis (2019) highlighted that EI boosts self-efficacy, a critical factor for entrepreneurial success, while Foo (2011) pointed out that high EI enhances decision-making and

problem-solving under pressure. Goleman (2001) emphasised EI's role in effective leadership and team management, and Ciarrochi, Deane, and Anderson (2002) identified EI as essential for stress management and resilience. Baron and Markman (2003) also underlined the importance of EI in building the strong interpersonal relationships and networks vital for entrepreneurial success.

Empirical studies further bolster these arguments. Shah-Zhou and Bojica (2017) found that entrepreneurs with higher EI tend to perceive their success more favourably across various dimensions, including employee satisfaction, social responsibility, and business performance. The self-perceived ability to regulate the emotions of other people is most strongly linked to and is a significant predictor of entrepreneurial success. This finding underscores the complexity of EI and its diverse effects on entrepreneurial outcomes, indicating that different dimensions of EI impact how entrepreneurs perceive and achieve success.

While there are challenges in directly linking EI to entrepreneurial success due to measurement issues (Swift, 2013), the consensus among scholars highlights its critical role. EI enhances resilience, innovation, social skills, and leadership, all of which are essential for entrepreneurship. Moreover, perceptions of EI further reinforce its importance, suggesting that emotionally intelligent entrepreneurs are more likely to achieve both tangible business outcomes and higher levels of personal and professional satisfaction.

2.3.2 Environmental factors

2.3.2.1 Family support

While demonstrating the need for social capital and support for female entrepreneurs, Osama *et al.* (2019) identified one of the key determinants of female entrepreneurial growth and success as family support. Emotional and practical assistance that helps female entrepreneurs balance work and family responsibilities and support from family members, particularly husbands and fathers, is crucial for female entrepreneurs (Rastogi, Baral, and Banu, 2022; Banu, Baral, and Kuschel, 2023). This support is especially important in the early stages of business and motherhood, where flexible scheduling and proximity to the workplace are essential for managing work-life balance (Aggrawal *et al.*, 2022). The presence of family support can mitigate the negative impact of market hostility and encourage females to adopt more entrepreneurial strategic postures, thereby enhancing competitive performance (Chhabra, Singh, and Mehdi, 2022). Government and institutional support, although limited, along with family backing, can further enhance females' entrepreneurial capacity by providing necessary resources and reducing socio-cultural barriers (Arora and Agarwal, 2019). Overall, female entrepreneurs who have been successful in India highlight the transformative power of family support in fostering a conducive environment for female entrepreneurship, enabling them to thrive and contribute significantly to the economy (Singh and Singh, 2023).

However, according to a study by Basit *et al.* (2020) in Malaysia, family support is essential for female entrepreneurs in Malaysia, but there is no significant impact of this support on the success of Malaysian female entrepreneurs. The reasons family support is not significant include changing family dynamics due to modernisation and cultural shifts

in norms and values; instead, other factors like work experience and industry knowledge are more influential than family support (Basit *et al.*, 2020). Although Basit *et al.*'s (2020) research was conducted in another context, it nevertheless reveals a need to further investigate the role of family support in female entrepreneurial success; examine the significance of family support to see whether other factors are more influential; and determine if there has been any cultural shift in traditional Indian society, where family plays an important role. This necessitates examining the perceptions of female entrepreneurs in India regarding family support and other factors to determine the changing dynamics and shifts in norms and values.

2.3.2.2 Social support

Social support from family, friends, and entrepreneurial communities also positively impacts entrepreneurial orientation, boosting self-confidence, self-efficacy, and resilience among female entrepreneurs (Sehgal and Khandelwal, 2020). Social support is also one of the key determinants of female entrepreneurial growth and success (Osama *et al.*, 2019). Social support, which comprises family, friends, mentors, and entrepreneurial communities, significantly impacts female's entrepreneurial orientation and success by providing emotional, informational, and financial resources (Harshitha, Chidananda, and Varghese, 2023). Female entrepreneurs can identify the types of social support they need to minimise dual-role conflicts and develop strategies to enhance their business performance through the support they receive. Female entrepreneurs should assess their personal and professional needs, seek feedback from peers and mentors, and utilise community resources to identify the type of social support required (Prabawanti and Rusli, 2022). Thus, in addition to family support, female entrepreneurs also rely on social

support to deal with the barriers and challenges in their entrepreneurial journey, and there is a need to examine female entrepreneurs' perceptions of family and social support as they evolve due to modernisation.

2.3.2.3 Gender stereotypes

Indian female entrepreneurs are challenged by gender role expectations where work-life conflicts and expectations to fulfil domestic and household responsibilities discourage their participation in entrepreneurship (Baral *et al.*, 2023). Disparities exist between men's and women's participation in entrepreneurship, with females often opting for business ventures in various sectors, underscoring the necessity to combat prevailing gender biases associated with business selections (Rajamani, 2022). Females bear the burden of agricultural tasks, household chores, and childcare, constraining their economic prospects and perpetuating traditional gender norms, and female entrepreneurs face significant challenges due to societal expectations and stereotypes (Rajamani, 2022).

However, Hamdani *et al.* (2023) also highlighted that gender stereotypes can shape how females see themselves and their abilities, which can either boost or hinder their confidence in starting and running a business. Moreover, these stereotypes can have a positive impact on female's self-efficacy and indicate that awareness of such stereotypes may propel female to strive harder to disprove them and have greater belief in their competencies. Thus, societal perceptions regarding gender roles can either motivate or discourage females from considering entrepreneurial pursuits (Hamdani *et al.*, 2023).

Gender equality is crucial for economic development, indicating that overcoming gender stereotypes can lead to better economic outcomes for females and society as a whole (Rajamani, 2022). The stronger influence of gender stereotypes on female entrepreneurial

aspirations is due to high self-efficacy, which highlights the role of self-belief in overcoming negative stereotypes (Hamdani *et al.*, 2023). Providing specific training can help females overcome these barriers and develop their skills and talents (Rajamani, 2022). Contrasting views on gender stereotypes necessitate further empirical research to reveal the positive or negative influence they may have on female's entrepreneurial journey.

2.3.2.4 Technological advancements

According to Mivehchi (2019), the rapid development of technology is the most essential feature of the contemporary world as Information and Communication Technology (ICT) continues to provide an enabling environment for economic and social development. The progress in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) witnessed in the 21st century is an opportunity for business ideas for entrepreneurial ventures. Many tech-savvy entrepreneurs are leveraging these advancements to develop innovative business ideas and solutions that cater to the evolving digital landscape. Technological advancements have become an important source of empowerment for females to participate in business innovatively and creatively. According to Mivehchi (2019), ICT has become a major concern for entrepreneurship as it provides accessibility to the market through the sales and marketing of services and products as well as the creation of job opportunities for economic empowerment. In support of these arguments, Ughetto *et al.* (2020) stated that ICT has introduced many opportunities that female entrepreneurs can take advantage of in building their business ideas. However, Ughetto *et al.* (2020) also commented that, despite developments in ICT infrastructure, females have difficulty assessing technology and finances in many societies, which imposes a barrier to their

successful involvement in entrepreneurship. Kaushik (2013) also observed that many female entrepreneurs in India faced challenges in accessing finance for their businesses, with only a few relying on loans from financial institutions while the majority received financial assistance from their relatives and money lenders. These insights underline the difficulty of female entrepreneurs in accessing financial support, which in turn complicates their entrepreneurial activities.

Westhuizen and Goyayi (2019) maintained that there are many risks and higher levels of volatility in business start-ups due to rapid developments in technology. Westhuizen and Goyayi (2019) argued that there is an urgent need for entrepreneurs to develop and adopt rapid adaptability and response to build confidence among female entrepreneurs.

However, Ughetto *et al.* (2020) contradicted Westhuizen and Goyayi (2019) and instead suggested a need for studies to establish the impact of digital transformation on female entrepreneurship due to frequent developments and changes. These contradictions indicate that more work is needed to understand how technological advancements influence the success of female entrepreneurs.

2.3.2.5 Government policies

The literature on government policies influencing female entrepreneurship emphasises the crucial role of the governmental and non-governmental sectors in promoting female entrepreneurship. Charulakshmi and Thaiyalnayaki (2019) proposed that the primary challenges to female entrepreneurs' stem from the laxity of organisations responsible for developing and implementing appropriate policies. Rabbani and Chowdhury (2013) sustained this view, suggesting that proper policy formulation can address most challenges and significantly increase the chances of entrepreneurial success. This

perspective is further supported by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development OECD (2019), underscoring the necessity of comprehensive policy frameworks and legal and financial support for aspiring entrepreneurs.

Sucia and Achsania (2018) contended that strong government support through policy frameworks is crucial for the success of female entrepreneurs. They stressed that access to financial resources and policy initiatives promotes fairness and contributes to economic growth. Similarly, Madurawala *et al.* (2014) asserted that tailored programmes and policies for female entrepreneurs can lead to significant economic transformation.

Effective policy formulation is key to overcoming the challenges entrepreneurs face (Rabbani and Chowdhury, 2013; Charulakshmi and Thaiyalnayaki, 2019). The OECD (2019) report supports this by advocating for comprehensive policy frameworks and financial support to ensure a level playing field. Sucia and Achsania (2018) provided evidence that support and access to financial resources can significantly boost female entrepreneurial success.

Madurawala *et al.* (2014) highlighted the higher dependence of females on government policies, suggesting that tailored support is crucial for their success. Successful policy interventions include the Indian government's various schemes and policies aimed at fostering female entrepreneurship; these include skills training, vocational education, and entrepreneurial development programmes that have expanded economic opportunities for female (Sachdeva, 2023). Government support, such as training and educational support, has helped females overcome traditional barriers (Kruthika, Arifulla, and Jain, 2023). In the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise (MSME) sector, the Indian government has emphasised developing female entrepreneurship, although Saranya and Chandrasekar

(2023) evidenced the ongoing need for robust strategies to overcome external and internal hurdles. Financial support from banks and financial institutions is also crucial (Feng, Ahmed, and Zheng, 2023).

Despite government support, overreliance on government policies might not be sustainable, and market forces and individual capabilities should be the primary drivers of entrepreneurial success. Corruption and bureaucratic inefficiencies can prevent resources from reaching their intended beneficiaries (Dar, Kaur, and Singh, 2021). Literature underscores the role of governmental and non-governmental support in promoting female entrepreneurship. While government support through financial, educational, and motivational initiatives is indispensable, the actual impact of these policies depends on their effective implementation and the ability to balance support with fostering individual entrepreneurial capabilities.

2.3.3 Traditional challenges and modern challenges as factors

Besides the factors mentioned above, this research also studies traditional and modern challenges as factors influencing female entrepreneurial success and the perceptions of female entrepreneurs about how these factors impact their success.

2.3.3.1 Traditional challenges

Traditional challenges are the traditional role of females in the family and the traditional perceptions of people about females in business. In India, the traditional role of females has predominantly centred around household responsibilities, childcare, and supporting the family; this role has often limited their participation in economic activities outside the home (Katakwar, 2022; Rajamani, 2022). This deeply ingrained traditional setup,

whereby the family and society expect females to prioritise domestic duties, acts as a significant barrier to female entrepreneurship (Katakwar, 2022; Sachdeva, 2023). The lack of appropriate training, skills development, and education further makes it difficult for females to compete effectively in the market (Sayeed, 2023). Females in family businesses often contribute, but their roles are minimised, and their contributions are undervalued (Devi, 2023). Despite these challenges, the increasing educational status and aspirations for a better life among Indian females have prompted a shift, enabling more females to venture into entrepreneurship (Singh, Shekhawat, and Singla, 2022). However, females' socio-cultural embeddedness within the household can still constrain their business ownership, as seen in rural South India, where factors like a husband's occupation and income play a crucial role in enabling or limiting female entrepreneurial activities (Pandey, 2022). Additionally, government initiatives and policies aimed at fostering female entrepreneurship have been instrumental, but the impact of skills training and vocational education is often hindered by societal and economic disparities (Gupta and Kaur, 2023). Female entrepreneurs in India have demonstrated resilience in succeeding in male-dominated business environments, and their further development is essential for economic and societal growth (Gaur, Vijay, and Ravi, 2018; Panda, 2018; Eib and Siegert, 2019). This necessitates continuous support and training to help females overcome traditional barriers and thrive as entrepreneurs. To support females in overcoming these barriers, it is essential to examine their perceptions of traditional challenges and the influence these challenges have on their entrepreneurial journey.

2.3.3.2 Modern challenges

Modern challenges such as globalisation, modernisation, evolving work and family roles, negative social media perceptions, the high cost of living, increasing expenses towards child education, and recent government policies significantly impact female entrepreneurs. Evolving work and family roles add to the complexity as females struggle with multiple responsibilities, making it harder to focus solely on their businesses (Santos *et al.*, 2019). The high cost of living and increasing expenses for child education add financial strain, complicating females' capacity to allocate funds for business growth (Singh and Singh, 2022). Unequal pay remains a persistent issue and limits the financial resources available to females for business investments (Parmar *et al.*, 2022). Recent government policies, although aimed at promoting female entrepreneurship, often fall short of addressing the unique challenges females face, such as access to finance and legal constraints (Suriyamurthi *et al.*, 2009; Kharlamova and Stavytsky, 2020).

Although globalisation and modernisation have opened new markets, they have also intensified competition, requiring females to constantly innovate and adapt to stay relevant (Khalid *et al.*, 2022; Saranya and Chandrasekar, 2023). Negative social media perceptions can undermine their credibility and affect their mental health, further complicating their entrepreneurial journey (Simon and Marathe, 2022). Females face more barriers today than in the past because of rapid technological advancements and the need for continuous upskilling. Nevertheless, female entrepreneurs have still emerged as a significant economic force, contributing to the global economy and driving social change (Singh and Britto, 2022). However, to sustain this momentum, there is a need for

collective actions, including supportive government policies, financial assistance, and societal change, to address gender biases and identify how perceptions of these modern challenges shape female entrepreneurs' journeys.

To better understand the differences between traditional and modern challenges faced by female entrepreneurs, a comparison of these factors is presented in Table 2.1. This table provides the summary of both the challenges and highlights the key differences between them.

Table 2.1 Distinguishing Traditional Challenges and Modern Challenges

Aspect	Traditional Challenges (TC)	Modern Challenges (MC)
Definition	Perceptions of traditional practices and roles that limit female entrepreneurship.	Perceptions of contemporary conditions in the business environment that hinder female entrepreneurship.
Relevance	Reflects traditional, static challenges predominantly in conservative contexts.	Represents contemporary challenges that require dynamic responses from female entrepreneurs to thrive in competitive environments.
Key Sources	Katakwar (2022); Rajamani (2022); Singh, Shekhawat, and Singla (2022); Devi (2023); Gupta and Kaur (2023); Sachdeva (2023)	Hossain and Rahman (2018); Kabote (2018); Kikula (2018); Santos <i>et al.</i> (2019); Parmar <i>et al.</i> (2022); Singh and Singh (2022).
Examples of Challenges	Traditional gender roles prioritizing domestic responsibilities. Societal undervaluation of women's roles in family businesses.	Stiff market competition and globalization. Balancing evolving work and family roles. High cost of living and child education expenses.

Nature	Rooted in socio-cultural norms and historical inequalities, which change slowly.	Dynamic and shaped by technological advancements, globalization, and policy changes.
Impact on Entrepreneurs	Creates structural barriers that limit women's participation in entrepreneurial activities, especially in rural areas.	Demands adaptability to new technologies and financial pressures while managing evolving family and societal roles.
Government Role	Support exists but is hindered by societal and economic disparities (Gupta and Kaur, 2023).	Policies are often insufficient in addressing unique barriers like access to finance and legal constraints (Suriyamurthi <i>et al.</i> , 2009).

2.4 Theoretical framework

Given the current study's focus on female entrepreneurs' perceptions of the factors and challenges to their entrepreneurial success, application of a psychological theory may provide a clearer explanation of the processes under investigation. People's underlying perceptions and attitudes are known to influence behaviour (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975); thus, female entrepreneurs' prevailing perceptions have the potential to influence behaviours that drive female entrepreneurial success. Whilst multiple theories attempt to understand entrepreneurial behaviour, the theory of planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) has been selected as the theoretical framework in this study due to its focus on how an individual's perceptions are related to their behaviour. Thus, within this study, the theory is used to explain how female's perceptions of personal and environmental factors, including traditional and modern challenges as factors, impact their entrepreneurial success. By utilising the theory of planned behaviour, this framework provides a unique and structured approach to examining the cognitive processes that drive entrepreneurial intentions and behaviours, thereby predicting success.

2.4.1 Overview of the theory of planned behaviour (TPB)

The theory of planned behaviour (TPB), developed by Icek Ajzen, posits that an individual's intention to engage in a behaviour is influenced by three key components and their antecedents, which are beliefs related to these components (Ajzen, 1991):

Attitude: The individual's positive or negative evaluations of performing the behaviour.

Subjective norms: The perceived social pressure to perform or not perform the behaviour.

Perceived behavioural control: The perceived ease or difficulty of performing the behaviour as influenced by past experiences and anticipated obstacles

Figure 2.3 Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour

These components interact to form behavioural intentions, which are considered the immediate antecedents of actual behaviour. The TPB has been widely used to predict various types of behaviours, including health behaviours, consumer behaviours, and, importantly, entrepreneurial behaviours. Figure 2.3 elucidates the components of TPB and its antecedents. The antecedents, behavioural beliefs, normative beliefs, and control

beliefs of the components of the TPB directly address the entrepreneur's perceptions of factors and challenges, making it particularly suitable for studies focusing on challenges and facilitators in entrepreneurship (Ajzen, 1991). Empirical studies have supported the application of this theory in the entrepreneurial context, demonstrating its effectiveness in understanding the formation of entrepreneurial intentions and the transition from intention to actual entrepreneurial activity (Kautonen, Van Gelderen, and Fink, 2015).

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) provides a robust framework for understanding and predicting behaviours based on three key components: attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. In this study, TPB has been utilised to examine the factors influencing the behaviour, Years in Business, which represents female entrepreneurs' longevity in business. However, only two components of TPB, attitudes and subjective norms, have been employed to explain this behaviour. The exclusion of the perceived behavioural control component is deliberate and aligns with the nature of the research focus. By narrowing the framework to attitudes and subjective norms, this study prioritises the personal and socio-environmental dimensions influencing longevity in business, acknowledging that external factors and unpredictability limit the applicability of perceived behavioural control in this context (Ajzen, 2005; LaMorte, 2022). This refined application of TPB ensures that the model remains relevant and appropriately tailored to the focus of this research.

Given its strengths in explaining and predicting behaviour based on a range of personal and environmental factors, the TPB offers a valuable theoretical framework for examining the challenges and barriers faced by female entrepreneurs. It provides a strong

basis for exploring how various factors converge to influence the success of female entrepreneurs.

2.4.1.1 Relevance of TPB to entrepreneurship

The TPB is particularly relevant to entrepreneurial behaviour as it provides a comprehensive framework for understanding how beliefs and perceptions shape entrepreneurs' intentions and actions. Previous research in the context of India has demonstrated the applicability of TPB in predicting entrepreneurial intentions and actions, making it a robust framework for this study (Srivastava and Misra, 2017; Khan *et al.*, 2020; Ali, Shabir, and Shaikh, 2021; Tapas, Sharma, and Virani, 2022). By applying the TPB, the theory's components (attitudes and subjective norms) related to personal factors, environmental factors, and challenges influencing female entrepreneurial success can be uncovered.

2.4.1.2 Understanding perceptions of personal factors through the lens of the TPB

In theory of planned behaviour, attitudes (TPB's component) towards behaviour pertain to an individual's extent of having a favourable or unfavourable assessment of the behaviour. Similarly, within female entrepreneurship, perceptions of various factors towards entrepreneurship pertain to an individual's extent of having a favourable or unfavourable assessment of the entrepreneurship. For instance, perceptions of female entrepreneurs regarding their business acumen towards entrepreneurship. Those females who view themselves as knowledgeable in business are inclined to hold a positive stance towards initiating and overseeing a business. The possession of entrepreneurial knowledge has a positive impact on attitudes towards entrepreneurship, consequently nurturing entrepreneurial aspirations (Koellinger, Minniti, and Schade, 2013). Females

who strongly believe in their business knowledge are more likely to exhibit positive attitudes towards entrepreneurship, demonstrating confidence in their capability to excel in business pursuits (Koellinger, Minniti, and Schade, 2013).

Subjective norms (TPB's component) encompass the perceived societal pressures dictating the execution or avoidance of a particular behaviour in TPB. Within female entrepreneurship, anticipation and backing from family, friends, and society can shape female's perceptions of their risk-taking abilities. Additionally, prevailing societal norms and support networks can either motivate or deter females from involvement in entrepreneurial endeavours. Social norms and the perceived backing from their immediate surroundings significantly influence females' entrepreneurial intentions (Shinnar, Giacomini, and Janssen, 2012). Subjective norms impact female's inclination towards risk-taking. A supportive social environment bolsters their confidence in undertaking calculated risks, a vital element for entrepreneurial success (Shinnar, Giacomini, and Janssen, 2012).

2.4.1.3 Understanding perceptions of environmental factors through the lens of the TPB

Perceptions of environmental factors such as family support, social support, gender stereotypes, technological advancements, and government policies influencing female entrepreneurial success can be explained through the attitudes and subjective norms components of the TPB towards the behaviour (Years in business). These components help clarify how external influences and their perceptions shape the actions of female entrepreneurs. Taken together, these components offer a comprehensive view of the environmental factors affecting female entrepreneurial success. Recognising and

addressing these factors through supportive policies, societal changes, and resource provision can significantly enhance the entrepreneurial ecosystem for females.

In the theory of planned behaviour, attitudes, a component of the TPB, towards the behaviour refer to the overall positive or negative evaluations of performing the behaviour. Within female entrepreneurship, positive perceptions of family support can significantly enhance female entrepreneurs' attitudes towards starting and sustaining a business. Research shows that strong family support provides emotional, financial, and logistical assistance, which fosters positive attitudes towards entrepreneurship (Shelton, 2006). Similarly, positive perceptions of technological advancement can enhance female entrepreneurs' attitudes by making business operations more efficient and scalable (Ifinedo, 2011).

Female entrepreneurs' perceptions of social support and gender stereotypes play a crucial role and can be explained using the subjective norms component of the TPB. Social support from peers, mentors, and the wider community positively influences entrepreneurial intentions, creating a supportive entrepreneurial environment (Shinnar, Giacomini, and Janssen, 2012). Strong social networks and community support can positively influence subjective norms, making entrepreneurship a more socially accepted and encouraged endeavour (Shinnar, Giacomini, and Janssen, 2012). Negative stereotypes have the potential to impede subjective norms and perceived behavioural control, consequently dissuading females from engaging in entrepreneurial endeavours (Gupta *et al.*, 2009). The presence of negative gender stereotypes can impact female entrepreneurial involvement, leading to females feeling less capable or accepted when performing entrepreneurial activities (Gupta *et al.*, 2009).

2.4.1.4 Understanding perceptions of challenges through the lens of the TPB

For female entrepreneurs, perceptions of traditional gender roles and societal expectations can significantly impact their attitudes towards entrepreneurial activities. Traditional gender roles often dictate that female entrepreneurs prioritise family responsibilities over business ventures, leading to a negative attitude towards entrepreneurship (Brush, 1992). Females who perceive traditional gender roles and societal expectations negatively may develop unfavourable attitudes towards entrepreneurship. Furthermore, modern challenges such as high costs of living, modernisation, globalisation, negative social media influence, and increasing childcare expenses can also shape attitudes towards their entrepreneurial behaviour. For instance, high cost of living and childcare expenses can deter females from pursuing entrepreneurship due to perceived financial instability (Jennings and Brush, 2013).

Societal norms and cultural expectations strongly influence female entrepreneurs' perceptions regarding traditional challenges. In many cultures, particularly culturally diverse countries like India, females may face discouragement from their immediate social circles due to traditional gender roles. This discouragement negatively impacts their entrepreneurial intentions (Shinnar, Giacomini, and Janssen, 2012). Modern challenges such as globalisation and negative social media influence can also impact subjective norms. Globalisation may lead to increased competition, which can either motivate or deter female entrepreneurs based on their perceived support from their networks (Welter, 2011). Negative social media influence can create unrealistic expectations and societal pressures, further complicating entrepreneurial endeavours (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010).

2.4.1.5 The intention-behaviour gap

In the TPB, behavioural intentions are the most immediate antecedents of actual behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). However, a gap often exists between intention and behaviour, particularly in complex phenomena like female entrepreneurial success. This gap is critical in understanding the factors and challenges influencing female entrepreneurs, as strong entrepreneurial intentions do not always translate into successful entrepreneurial actions (Sheeran, 2002). This discussion explores the reasons behind this gap in the context of the perceptions of personal factors, environmental influences, and the traditional and modern challenges female entrepreneurs face.

Behavioural Intention and Actual Behaviour

Behavioural intention refers to an individual's motivational readiness to perform a particular behaviour. Female entrepreneurship involves the desire and plan to manage and grow a business venture. However, actual behaviour encompasses the execution of these intentions through tangible entrepreneurial activities such as successful business management and implementing growth strategies (Kautonen *et al.*, 2013).

The intention-behaviour gap highlights the disparity between intending to engage in entrepreneurship and successfully performing entrepreneurial activities (Sheeran, 2002). This gap is influenced by various factors in the literature, such as lack of access to finance (Kaushik, 2013; Baral *et al.*, 2023), lack of family and social support (Welter *et al.*, 2018), the role of government and its support in terms of policies and procedures, lack of technological support (Panda, 2018), and socio-cultural factors that require females to take care of household and domestic duties (Baral *et al.*, 2023). These factors facilitate or hinder the translation of intentions into actions.

The gap between behavioural intention and behaviour is a significant challenge in the context of female entrepreneurship. Personal factors, environmental influences, and traditional and modern challenges all contribute to this gap. The TPB explains the cognitive processes underlying entrepreneurial intentions and identifies strategies to bridge this gap. Fostering supportive subjective norms, developing resilient attitudes, and addressing structural barriers are critical for enabling female entrepreneurs to successfully translate their intentions into entrepreneurial actions (Ajzen, 1991; Kautonen, Van Gelderen, and Fink, 2015). Addressing these factors comprehensively can promote gender equality in entrepreneurship and contribute to broader economic and social development goals (Jennings and Brush, 2013).

2.4.2 Strengths and weaknesses of the TPB

Strengths

The TPB is valuable for understanding complex behaviour like entrepreneurship because it accounts for multiple factors, such as attitudes, norms, and perceived control (Ajzen, 1991). Additionally, it explains how these factors are influenced by entrepreneurs' beliefs, particularly in the context of current research on female entrepreneurs' perceptions of the key factors and challenges impacting their entrepreneurial success.

The TPB predicts behaviour in many areas, including health, environment, and business, which is important for researchers studying current and future behaviours (Armitage and Conner, 2001). The TPB is useful in the context of predicting female entrepreneurial success based on their perceptions of factors and challenges and providing practical recommendations to this group.

This theory is highly adaptable, allowing for the inclusion of additional predictors when the basic model does not fully explain a particular behaviour. This makes it useful in complex settings where unique factors may influence behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). For example, in addition to the personal and environmental factors examined in the current study, any additional factors, such as political or legal factors, that need to be examined in future studies can be included in the framework because of TPB's adaptability.

Weaknesses

Behaviour is not always under volitional control, especially in entrepreneurship. External factors, like market changes or economic crises, can significantly influence outcomes. The static model of the theory poses a limitation as it accounts for factors influencing behaviour but fails to capture changes in attitudes or contexts over time (Sniehotta *et al.*, 2014), which are particularly important in the dynamic context of female entrepreneurship. The TPB only provides a snapshot of the factors influencing behavioural intentions and actual behaviour at a specific moment. This static approach means that it does not account for how these factors might evolve as individuals gain experience, encounter new challenges, or adapt to changing environments. In the TPB, attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control are considered stable predictors. The model does not incorporate mechanisms for these predictors to change in response to new information, experiences, or shifts in context, which are crucial in the entrepreneurial journey. The entrepreneurial journey is dynamic and characterised by continuous learning, adaptation, and the evolution of factors and challenges; to accurately capture these dynamics, it is essential to integrate longitudinal approaches, feedback

mechanisms, and context-specific modifications (Ajzen, 1991; Krueger *et al.*, 2000; Kautonen, Van Gelderen, and Fink, 2015).

Additionally, this theory overemphasises rational choice and may neglect spontaneous or unconscious influences on behaviour (Conner and Armitage, 1998). The TPB assumes that individuals make decisions based on rational choices, considering advantages and disadvantages before forming intentions and taking action. This assumption implies that behaviour is primarily the result of conscious, planned processes. However, human behaviour is often influenced by spontaneous, habitual, and unconscious factors. These influences include emotions, automatic responses, social conditioning, and implicit biases, which are not fully accounted for in the TPB framework (Sheeran, Gollwitzer, and Bargh, 2013). For example, high levels of stress and the need for quick decision-making in critical situations can lead to behaviour that is more reactive than planned. These coping mechanisms may be driven by unconscious processes rather than rational thought (Bargh and Chartrand, 1999). To overcome this limitation, it is crucial to consider both rational and non-rational influences on behaviour. This includes acknowledging the role of spontaneous, habitual, and unconscious factors (Wood and Neal, 2007).

2.4.3 Justification of the use of the TPB in the current study

Despite the weaknesses of this theory, it is highly relevant and beneficial in this study of female entrepreneurs' perceptions of factors influencing their success. This theory provides a holistic understanding of influences by analysing how personal factors such as business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence, combined with environmental factors such as family support, social support, gender stereotypes, technological advancements, and government policies, influence intentions and

behaviours leading to entrepreneurial success. This is crucial to understanding how these various elements interact to affect years in business as a proxy for success. The TPB component and its antecedents, which are the beliefs related to these components, directly address entrepreneurs' perceptions of factors and challenges, making it particularly suitable for studies focusing on perceptions of female entrepreneurs' challenges and facilitators in entrepreneurship (Ajzen, 1991).

Given its strengths in explaining and predicting female entrepreneurial success impacted by the perceptions of personal and environmental factors, the attitudes and subjective norms components of TPB offer a valuable theoretical framework. It provides a strong basis for exploring how the perceptions of various factors converge to influence the longevity and success of females' entrepreneurial journeys.

2.5 Research gaps for female entrepreneurship

2.5.1 Need for studies in an Indian context

The review of empirical literature on the opportunities and challenges of female entrepreneurship and the brief explanation provided in the introduction revealed the unique challenges faced by Indian female entrepreneurs due to the conflicts arising from patriarchal culture, the challenges faced in obtaining education, and gender inequalities.

The insight from Gaur, Vijay, and Ravi (2018) indicated that although India provides numerous opportunities for the success of female entrepreneurship, entrepreneurs continue to face challenges that hinder their success. Baral *et al.* (2023) and Kaushik (2013) argued that Indian female entrepreneurs lack access to financing to start their businesses and subsequently seek assistance from self-help groups, family, and their

savings. Lack of family support, social support, and socio-cultural factors in India further limit female entrepreneurs, who are required to take care of their households and domestic duties (Welter *et al.*, 2018; Baral *et al.*, 2023). The arguments from these studies showcase that Indian female entrepreneurs face unique challenges. As such, this study's concentration on Indian female entrepreneurs allows the researcher to examine the various issues hindering their success based on their own perceptions of the unique personal and environmental factors and challenges they face. The generated findings facilitate comparison with other developing countries to understand the barriers to female entrepreneurship in such regions.

The second justification for selecting India as the research context is that it facilitates identification of the diverse enabling factors that lead to the success of female entrepreneurship. The literature review revealed the role of different stakeholders, such as the Indian government and private financial institutions, in supporting female entrepreneurship. Government policies play an important role in the success of female entrepreneurs in India (Madurawala *et al.*, 2014; Górány and Mura, 2021; Baral *et al.*, 2023). However, gaps remain regarding the role of the government and its support in terms of policies and procedures, as well as regarding the perception females have of these policies. Thus, this research addresses these gaps and facilitates understanding of whether the perception of government policies as an environmental factor significantly predicts the success of female entrepreneurs in India.

India was chosen for this study because it extends the scope of current research on female entrepreneurship in developing countries. This research examines how perceptions of personal and environmental factors, as well as both traditional and modern challenges,

impact the success of female entrepreneurs in India. Based on the literature, many female entrepreneurs in India have been slow in adopting technology (Belwal, Belwal, and Fatema, 2014; Boermans and Willebrands, 2017; Giusta, Marina, and Razzu, 2019). Some studies, such as Panda (2018), have argued that Indian female entrepreneurs struggle due to the lack of technological support, hindering its use in their businesses. As such, examining female entrepreneurs' perceptions regarding technological advancements can provide insight into whether these perceptions can predict their success.

2.5.2 Limited empirical findings from India

Minimal studies have comprehensively examined the diverse factors influencing the success of female entrepreneurs in India. However, empirical studies have shown that various factors affect the success of female entrepreneurs in both developing and developed countries. For instance, emotional, financial, and family support have been reported to motivate female entrepreneurs and enhance their success (Chhabra, Singh, and Mehdi, 2022). Additionally, Charulakshmi and Thaiyalnayaki (2019) emphasize the critical role of social support in promoting female entrepreneurship. Technological advancements also play a significant role, as demonstrated by Gautam and Khurana (2018), who found that females were leveraging advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) to meet customer needs. Conversely, Panda's (2018) study contradicted these findings by showing that some female entrepreneurs struggled to use these technologies, leading to lower success rates.

However, minimal work has been done to elucidate perceptions of the factors and challenges and statistically predict female entrepreneurial success using the predictors,

which are Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of the factors and challenges. The current research bridges this research gap by studying the influence of perceived factors and challenges on female entrepreneurial success in India. This will contribute to enhancing insights regarding the perceptions of diverse factors and the success of female entrepreneurs in India.

2.5.3 Need for conceptual frameworks

Few studies have developed conceptual frameworks for perceptions of the factors and challenges influencing female entrepreneurial success in the Indian context. Gupta and Mirchandani (2018) created a framework that highlights the social and cultural barriers impacting the entrepreneurial activities of Indian female entrepreneurs, such as family expectations and societal norms. Their study underlined the importance of understanding these unique socio-cultural dynamics to develop effective support systems for female entrepreneurs. Similarly, Singh and Raina (2019) proposed a model that identifies financial constraints, a lack of mentorship, and inadequate access to networks as critical challenges female entrepreneurs face. This framework underscores the necessity for targeted interventions to mitigate these barriers. Agarwal and Lenka (2016) highlighted that self-efficacy and resilience are crucial elements in overcoming entrepreneurial obstacles by examining the impact of psychological and motivational factors on female's entrepreneurial success. These conceptual frameworks provide valuable insights but also indicate a need for more comprehensive studies that integrate various dimensions of the perceptions of challenges faced by female entrepreneurs in India. Accordingly, this study considers the perceptions of personal factors such as business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence and environmental factors such as perceptions of

family support, social support, gender stereotypes, government policies, and technological advancements in terms of their influence on the success of female entrepreneurs in India. The developed conceptual framework is vital to understanding perceptions of key factors and challenges in relation to the success of female entrepreneurs in the Indian context.

2.5.4 Need for practical solutions for female entrepreneurs in India

Practical solutions to help female entrepreneurs succeed in India are needed to capture the economic and social benefits of female-owned businesses, but thus far, few studies offer practical toolkits for the development of practical solutions. The proposed conceptual framework at the end of this chapter aims to guide entrepreneurship among females in India. The conceptual framework categorises the determinants of female entrepreneurship success into three categories: perceptions of personal factors, perceptions of environmental factors, and perceptions of challenges. The conceptual framework showcases perceptions of various factors that are pivotal to the success of female entrepreneurship and guides females interested in building entrepreneurial ventures. The limited availability of clear roadmaps, such as recommendations that the government can adopt to enhance the success of female entrepreneurship in India, may be addressed through an empirical approach to understanding how perceptions guide the behaviour of female entrepreneurs in India. The recommendations can also be adopted by private institutions such as microfinance agencies, and organisations working on female empowerment to support female entrepreneurship in the Indian context. After reviewing the literature, the conceptual model depicted in Figure 2.4 is proposed for testing. The purpose is to demonstrate the precise predictions envisaged, based on past scholarly

works and theoretical assumptions, guiding the overall investigation to meet the specific objectives and aim of the study.

Figure 2.4 Conceptual Framework, Source (Author’s Illustration)

2.6 Hypothesis development for personal factors

H1: Indian female entrepreneurs’ perceptions of personal factors such as business knowledge (BK), risk-taking behaviour (RB), and emotional intelligence (EI) significantly predict years in business.

Baassiri (2018) explained that effective business management skills are essential for entrepreneurial success. However, Abu-Saifan (2012), Alsos and Ljunggren (2016), and Gaddefors and Anderson (2017) contended that many female entrepreneurs face challenges in developing these skills, which can hinder their success. Eib and Siegert (2019) also pointed out that most female entrepreneurs often lack sufficient business or work experience. This was further supported by Kikula (2018), who added that many

female entrepreneurs lack the industry-specific knowledge necessary to become effective business managers. These differing perspectives suggest that the absence of industry-specific knowledge and business management skills can impede female entrepreneurs from scaling their businesses and present significant obstacles to their entrepreneurial success.

According to Adel, Mahrous, and Hammad (2020), female entrepreneurs who run and manage small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and family businesses do not have sufficient prior work experience to become successful in their entrepreneurial activities. Similarly, Gaur, Vijay, and Ravi (2018) reported that female entrepreneurs tend to have fewer opportunities and capabilities to acquire sufficient human capital, which negatively affects their success. Chhabra, Singh, and Mehdi (2022) elaborated that business knowledge also encompasses financial knowledge, financial planning, financial awareness, and business managerial skills to enable engagement with different suppliers, competitors, and customers. Swarnalatha and Anuradha (2016) echoed Chhabra, Singh, and Mehdi (2022) and contended that female entrepreneurs ought to be supported through training on skills required for their businesses. Such knowledge and technical competencies are essential for the implementation of the vision and strategy of each entrepreneur.

Lack of education has also been named as a potential cause of the poor management skills exhibited by female entrepreneurs (Baassiri, 2018). However, according to Gaddefors and Anderson (2017), a lack of education is not a serious problem as many females are increasingly gaining education. At the same time, Komal and Sharma (2023) asserted that many female entrepreneurs lack the adequate education and industry

experience required to run their businesses effectively. Gaur, Vijay, and Ravi (2018) also contradicted Gaddefors and Anderson (2017) and argued that lack of self-confidence in skills, experience, and knowledge is another problem limiting female entrepreneurs' success. These contradictions indicate that the hindrances to female entrepreneurs' success arise from their lack of education and industry experience. The above outline leads to the following hypothesis concerning the role of knowledge and skills:

H1a: Perceptions of business knowledge (BK) significantly predict years in business.

According to Basit *et al.* (2020), female entrepreneurs tend to be more risk-averse, and their risk-taking behaviour (RB) could have a direct relationship with their entrepreneurial success. Gautam and Khurana (2018) also reported that female entrepreneurs tend to be more risk-averse compared to their male counterparts, implying that there is a substantial gender difference in how female entrepreneurs and male entrepreneurs approach business risks. For instance, according to Baassiri (2018), females tend to react more emotionally to uncertainties, which inhibits their RB. The evaluation and business decision-making of female entrepreneurs are therefore adversely affected. Boermans and Willebrands (2017) argued that the risk-averse behaviour of female entrepreneurs can be attributed to a tendency to have less confidence. Batool and Ullah (2017) added that RB has an impact on female entrepreneurs' competitiveness. Eib and Siegert (2019) followed Batool and Ullah (2017) and demonstrated that female entrepreneurs tend to perceive risk as a threat and often avoid taking challenges. Gehlot *et al.* (2022) also supported Baassiri's (2018) findings, positing that many Indian female entrepreneurs have a decreased capacity to bear risks and thus achieve less success. These insights indicate that a lack of confidence directly influences risk preferences in

entrepreneurial activities. In another study, Gaur, Vijay, and Ravi (2018) established a negative connection between high-risk propensity behaviour and business profits. However, Basit *et al.* (2020) contended that there is a positive connection between high-risk perception and business profits. These contradictions suggest that there is a need for female entrepreneurs in India to be less risk-averse to ensure success in their businesses. The above outline leads to the hypothesis that there is a connection between risk-taking behaviour and the success of female entrepreneurs:

H1b: Perceptions of risk-taking behaviour (RB) significantly predict years in business.

Emotional intelligence could be another factor responsible for the success of female entrepreneurs. Several past studies, such as Gautam and Khurana (2018) and Hossain and Rahman (2018), have provided empirical evidence indicating that females tend to be less optimistic and self-confident, which could directly affect their entrepreneurial ability. Abu-Saifan (2012) and Kaur and Sharma (2019) likewise claimed that female entrepreneurs are not only less self-confident but also characterised by a high fear of failure. Alison (2017) noted that a higher fear of failure is associated with reduced performance in business activities. Franzke *et al.* (2022) hypothesised that many female entrepreneurs lack self-confidence due to gendered norms related to their roles in society. The similarity between these studies indicates that a lack of emotional intelligence and self-confidence leads to high failure rates in entrepreneurship. However, Kabote (2018) contradicted Abu-Saifan (2012), Alison (2017), and Kaur and Sharma (2019) by arguing that there were no performance measurements directly associated with the level of emotional intelligence, particularly for female entrepreneurs. These contradictions

indicate that further work is required to establish the impact of emotional intelligence on the success of female entrepreneurs.

According to Gautam and Khurana (2018), the entrepreneurial self-efficacy of an individual is improved by their ability to effectively regulate and utilise their emotions. Their results suggest that emotional intelligence (EI) is an essential skill for the success of female entrepreneurs. Kaur and Sharma (2019) also argued that EI has a strong impact on entrepreneurs' level of innovativeness and their success. Chaudhary (2015) asserted that the possession of sufficient EI makes entrepreneurs more competitive, especially in business negotiations, and Gautam and Khurana (2018) observed that EI helps entrepreneurs develop their leadership skills and customer relations. Górány and Mura (2021) added that women who attained self-realisation were also able to achieve satisfaction in their ventures, thereby enhancing overall success. Thus, EI has the possibility of influencing women's business decisions. Effective business decision-making requires self-management and self-motivation, which are key elements of EI. The outline above leads to the next hypothesis:

H1c: Perceptions of emotional intelligence (EI) significantly predict years in business.

2.7 Hypothesis development for environmental factors

H2: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of environmental factors such as family support (FS), social support (SS), gender stereotypes (GS), technological advancements (TA), and government policies (GP) significantly predict years in business.

Past studies have provided a range of evidence indicating the different challenges that female entrepreneurs face, including family conflicts (Abu-Saifan, 2012; Charulakshmi and Thaiyalnayaki, 2019). Alison (2017) posited that female entrepreneurs face difficulties in balancing their family and work lives, while Giusta, Marina, and Razzu (2019) noted that female entrepreneurs are unable to spend enough time with their families due to work-related tasks and responsibilities. Agustoni (2019) also revealed that in most societies, females have substantial family responsibilities and household chores. Swarnalatha and Anuradha (2016) postulated that in India, females are unable to engage in entrepreneurial activities due to conflicts with family roles, with men instead being poised to take up entrepreneurial activities. Household chores greatly reduce the amount of time that females can commit to their entrepreneurship and work-related activities and, along with child education and childcare, represent just some of the burdens faced by female entrepreneurs. Chaudhary (2015) asserted that female entrepreneurs are often faced with family-work conflicts that add to their challenges. All the above factors are detrimental to the success of female entrepreneurs.

Hence, for female entrepreneurs to develop high-growth ventures, there is a need to create a balance between work and family life. Charulakshmi and Thaiyalnayaki (2019) suggested that for a balance to be realised, female entrepreneurs need encouragement and moral support from their friends and family members. Chhabra, Singh, and Mehdi (2022) likewise posited that family support, which can be offered either emotionally (intangible) or financially (tangible), influences the success of female entrepreneurship. These insights indicate that female entrepreneurs who receive family and social support are more likely to succeed in their entrepreneurial ventures due to having a social network

support. Family support likely has a significant influence on the success of female entrepreneurs with start-up activities, leading to the following research hypotheses:

H2a: Perceptions of family support (FS) significantly predict years in business.

H2b: Perceptions of social support (SS) significantly predict years in business.

Several authors, including Alsos and Ljunggren (2016), Hossain and Rahman (2018), and Ellemers (2018), have argued that female entrepreneurs are less successful in business compared to their male counterparts. Alison (2017) highlighted that females are less successful because they are faced with challenges and constraints related to human capital and start-up capital. However, Charulakshmi and Thaiyalnayaki (2019) claimed that the lack of female success in entrepreneurship is due to constraints associated with inadequate business experience. The highlighted challenges and constraints derive from the patriarchal social structure, which limits the success of female entrepreneurs. In a patriarchal society, females are often confined to household chores and child-rearing, depriving them of opportunities to develop their entrepreneurship and business skills.

Gender stereotypes have also been linked to the low success of female entrepreneurs in India. Adel, Mahrous, and Hammad (2020) maintained that, compared to men, female entrepreneurs tend to be less ambitious. Chaudhary (2015) elaborated that this lack of ambition is due to gender differences in competitiveness, risk propensity, and social preferences. Male rigidity in Indian society has led to the consideration of females as weaker, leading to a lack of support for engaging in entrepreneurship activities (Chaudhary, 2015; Adel, Mahrous, and Hammad, 2020; Gehlot *et al.*, 2022). Alsos and Ljunggren (2016) and Ellemers (2018) also proposed that female entrepreneurs tend to be

risk-averse, whereas male entrepreneurs are risk-takers. Risk profile influences the extent to which an individual is willing to undertake a given entrepreneurial activity. However, Amrutha, Santhi, and Nalini (2022) claimed that females in India no longer have the traditional mentality that only men can earn a living to support their families, and as a result, many females have ventured into entrepreneurial activities. These contradictions suggest that female entrepreneurs are beginning to be more risk-averse and challenging existing traditional gender stereotypes relegating them to domestic chores.

Lack of confidence has been identified as an additional challenge to the success of female entrepreneurs. According to Alsos and Ljunggren (2016), females are less confident in business compared to men. Chaudhary (2015), Ellemers (2018), and Kabote (2018) further argued that confidence, passion, resilience, and leadership skills are essential for entrepreneurial success. Therefore, for females to be successful in entrepreneurship, they need to be confident, passionate, resilient, and have effective leadership skills. The above are examples of gender stereotypes (GS) and differences between females and men that need to be addressed for females to be successful in entrepreneurship. Hence, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2c: Perceptions of gender stereotypes (GS) significantly predict years in business.

There could be a direct relationship between technological development and the success of female entrepreneurs. Agustoni (2019) indicated that the adoption of new technologies enhances the flow of creative entrepreneurship ideas. In another study, Boermans and Willebrands (2017) established that technological advancement is responsible for effective idea generation, which has the potential to enhance female entrepreneurs'

success. However, in most cases, female entrepreneurs are reluctant to adopt new technologies, which could limit their chances of success.

According to Batool and Ullah (2017), many female entrepreneurs are reluctant to embrace technology. As explained by Belwal, Belwal, and Fatema (2014), technological advancement has significant, positive implications for the development of female entrepreneurs' skills. New technology entrepreneurs enhance their business models and generate new ideas that improve business processes and operations. According to Gautam and Khurana (2018), technological advancement also helps build a customer base, which leads to business growth. For example, when used effectively, tools such as automatic transactions, apps, and artificial intelligence attract more customers to the business.

However, other studies have identified drawbacks to technology, such as slow adaptation processes, misuse for wrong purposes, and misleading information (Belwal, Belwal and Fatema, 2014; Boermans and Willebrands, 2017; Giusta, Marina, and Razzu, 2019).

Panda (2018) also challenged Gautam and Khurana (2018) by revealing that many female entrepreneurs in developing countries, including India and Pakistan, lack technological support, which hinders their networking opportunities and firm performance. These contradictions imply that more resources should be directed to female entrepreneurs to ensure they have the right infrastructure to conduct their businesses. The above points indicate that there is a relationship between technological advancements and the success of female entrepreneurs, leading to the following hypothesis:

H2d: Perceptions of technological advancements (TA) significantly predict years in business.

In each country, the government establishes policies and regulations that have a direct impact on businesses and entrepreneurship. For instance, as explained by Agustoni (2019), a government sets policies that have a direct impact on interest rates and taxation. Adel, Mahrous, and Hammad (2020) also observed that businesses can increase interest, which leads to a rise in borrowing, negatively affecting female entrepreneurs. Batool and Ullah (2017) revealed that higher interest rates decrease consumer spending and lower the success of female entrepreneurs. However, Kikula (2018) pointed out that some rules and policies established by governments, such as the minimum wage, may influence the business and success of female entrepreneurs indirectly. Such policies and rules may be set at the national, state, or municipal level.

Conversely, as explained by Belwal, Belwal, and Fatema (2014), governments can implement policies that encourage the success of female entrepreneurs by creating positive social behaviours and business environments. According to Gautam and Khurana (2018), good policies on tax and duty exemptions for female entrepreneurs can encourage their success and growth. Basit *et al.* (2020) argued that businesses often adapt their operations to various changes in government policies and regulations, as such policies may have a direct or indirect impact on profitability and the competitiveness of the business. Chhabra, Singh, and Mehdi (2022) echoed that government support is integral to fostering the entrepreneurial culture in a country by encouraging innovative initiatives among citizens. Gódnány and Mura (2021) hypothesised that the provision of financial support to female entrepreneurs would enhance their success. These insights underline the importance of government support in promoting entrepreneurial innovation activities. In almost every country, business owners are required to comply with various

government regulations and policies, which might greatly affect the success of female entrepreneurs. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2e: Perceptions of government policies (GP) significantly predict years in business.

2.8 Hypothesis development for challenges

In every society, there are several traditional practises that may directly affect the extent of female involvement in entrepreneurship. These traditional practises are deeply rooted in societal beliefs and therefore tend to vary from one place to another. As explained by Kikula (2018), India has long been characterised by gender discrimination. Females are traditionally not given equal opportunities in Indian society, and their roles have been mostly limited to household chores and child-rearing. Hossain and Rahman (2018) support Kikula (2018) and reported that there are some family restrictions, especially on females assuming some roles in society. Gautam and Khurana (2018) noted that in traditional Indian society, females were not given equal chances for education. Gehlot *et al.* (2022) further revealed that in the traditional setting, females were required to play less dominant roles, such as taking care of their families, and were hence discouraged from engaging in entrepreneurial activities. Komal and Sharma (2023) also reiterated Gehlot *et al.* (2022) and argued that many female entrepreneurs in India are under pressure to adhere to established gender roles involving domestic responsibilities and chores instead of venturing into business enterprises. Panda (2018) further argued that females are less likely to pursue entrepreneurship because it is considered contrary to traditional gender roles in patriarchal societies. Subsequently, many females in developing countries such as India are not adequately educated and are not allowed opportunities to engage in business. Boermans and Willebrands (2017) also observed that

in Indian culture, there is a low value attached to females' work and entrepreneurship. The confluence between the studies suggests that traditional challenges may impact the success of female entrepreneurs. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3a: Perceptions of traditional challenges (TC) significantly predict years in business.

In the contemporary business environment, females face several challenges that are likely to affect their entrepreneurial success. With evolving work and family roles, female entrepreneurs in India are facing a changing business environment (Gaur, Vijay, and Ravi 2018). Eib and Siegert (2019) support Gaur, Vijay, and Ravi (2018) and reported that the high cost of living in modern society, coupled with increasing expenses for child education and child-rearing, are mostly affecting female entrepreneurs. Likewise, Panda (2018) pointed out that in the modern world, female entrepreneurs are constrained by a lack of finances to facilitate their businesses due to high costs of living and limited savings. Thus, the high expenses incurred with modern life challenge female entrepreneurial activities.

Female entrepreneurs are negatively affected by the increasing cost of living, especially those who reside in urban areas. Giusta, Marina, and Razzu (2019) have cited the increasingly stiff competition that female entrepreneurs face in the business world. Gaddefors and Anderson (2017) argued that despite the stiff competition in business and professional life, females are still expected to handle children, cooking, family, and other social responsibilities. Chaudhary (2015) added that unequal pay for working females is a hindrance to their entrepreneurial growth. Therefore, all these studies suggest that

modern challenges may influence the success of female entrepreneurs and lead to the following hypothesis:

H3b: Perceptions of modern challenges (MC) significantly predict years in business.

Chapter Summary

This literature review serves as a foundational exploration of the problems facing female entrepreneurs in India, setting the stage for subsequent analysis and empirical investigation. By synthesising existing knowledge and identifying gaps in the literature, this chapter endeavours to contribute to a deeper understanding of female's entrepreneurship and the constructs that have been investigated in this study.

Chapter 3 Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the methods and approaches used to meet the study's aims of examining perceptions of the key factors influencing the success of Indian female entrepreneurs and providing recommendations. This chapter comprises 14 subsections: introduction, research philosophy, research strategy, research design, research variables, research hypotheses, population and sampling, tools used for data collection, research reliability and validity, pilot study, distribution of the questionnaire, data analysis techniques, ethical considerations, research limitations, and a summary. This chapter covers each component of the research process, as shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Research Process (Author)

3.2 Research philosophy

To highlight the selected philosophy, it is useful to restate the objectives of the study to critically establish the nature of the suitable philosophical stance. This study seeks to meet the following objectives:

1. To examine perceptions of personal factors of Indian female entrepreneurs, such as business knowledge (BK), risk-taking behaviour (RB), and emotional intelligence (EI), that influence their success as measured through years in business (YIB).
2. To examine perceptions of environmental factors of Indian female entrepreneurs, such as family support (FS), social support (SS), gender stereotypes (GS), technological advancements (TA), and government policies (GP) that influence their success as measured through years in business (YIB).
3. To examine perceptions of challenges of Indian female entrepreneurs, including traditional challenges (TC) and modern challenges (MC), that influence their success as measured through years in business (YIB).

Research philosophy deals with how researchers interpret the nature, source, and development of knowledge (Bajpai, 2011). Research philosophy in social science studies is founded on the assumption that although knowledge creation appears to be complex, there is a need to gather primary and secondary data to create new knowledge through data analysis to answer specific questions (Ramanathan, 2008). The data collected for developing knowledge should be relevant to the investigated phenomenon. How such data are synthesised should permit the making of relevant inferences. Saunders *et al.* (2012) identified three main considerations that must be put into perspective in justifying the selection of a research philosophy: type of philosophy, reasons behind the selection of the specific type, and the implications such a philosophical stance is likely to have on the research strategy and the choice of methods for collecting primary data.

Positivist philosophy is founded on the assumption that knowledge is obtained through observation and using the senses, including measurement, and can be considered trustworthy (Crowther and Lancaster, 2008; Littlejohn and Foss, 2009; Saunders *et al.*, 2012). Positivists argue that the researcher's role should be limited to gathering, synthesising, and interpreting outcomes instead of including their own interests. This implies that studies founded in a positivist context are quantifiable and observable, as argued by Littlejohn and Foss (2009). Crowther and Lancaster (2008) agreed with Littlejohn and Foss (2009) that the quantifiable observations on which positivism is founded lead to statistical analyses that establish associations and correlations among constructs. Researchers are often considered independent of their studies and adopt a deductive approach based on the view that it is important to concentrate on facts rather than meaning (Crowther and Lancaster, 2008).

Clarifications on the other types of paradigms are presented now, along with a brief discussion of why they do not suit the ongoing study. An interpretivist philosophy is founded on allowing researchers to integrate their judgement and knowledge into interpreting the phenomenon being studied (Myers, 2008; Collins, 2010). According to interpretive researchers, accessibility to reality, whether socially constructed or given, must be achieved through social creations such as instruments, shared meanings, consciousness, and language (Myers, 2008). A further critical assessment of the interpretivist stance reveals that it is founded on the critique of positivism. Interpretivism recommends the use of primary qualitative data as opposed to quantitative data, the use of an inductive research approach, biased axiology, and a subjective approach, rendering

it unsuitable for this research. According to Collins (2010), interpretivism is closely associated with an idealist stance, as both allow researchers to integrate their interests into the overall process of knowledge creation, which makes the whole process subjective as opposed to objective.

A realist philosophy supports reliance on the independence of mind in employing a scientific approach to developing knowledge. Realists believe that knowledge can be synthesised or developed through critical and direct realism (Wilson, 2010). Direct realism is considered naive since it assumes that what the mind conceives through the human senses is true. Such an assumption is criticised in the scientific development of knowledge in various fields. Critical realism is considered the most agreeable approach by scholars and researchers who acknowledge that human experiences and perceptions can be misleading and do not always portray the real world accurately (Novikov and Novikov, 2013). Irrespective of which form of realism is adopted, the general characteristics of these stances in research are that they allow the researcher to apply any form of reasoning, strategy, approach, and ontological belief (Wilson, 2010; Novikov and Novikov, 2013). This makes a study less replicable by future scholars and thus not suitable for current research.

A pragmatist philosophy accepts issues and concepts as relevant only when they are considered to support action. The pragmatists' main belief is that knowledge can be developed through multiple means and that there is no single standpoint that can be used to view and explain the world (Kara, 2015). Pragmatists consider their assumptions to be founded on the modified continuum of undertaking research. They propose using qualitative and quantitative data and analysis techniques, which can be achieved through

in-depth interviews or surveys, to gather sufficient primary data (Collis and Hussey, 2014). This philosophical stance is appropriate in studies employing mixed methods (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Despite pragmatism's suitability and strengths, this philosophical stance suffers a limitation in that it is founded on value-free axiology and a subjective or objective ontology, implying that it can use both inductive and deductive reasoning (Saunders *et al.*, 2012; Collis and Hussey, 2014; Kara, 2015).

However, as indicated earlier, the current research was founded on positivist philosophy rather than the other types. Positivist philosophy was chosen as it was most suitable for the problem addressed.

Deductive research approach

Positivist philosophy supports a deductive research approach based on objective ontology and value-free axiology and achieved through quantitative strategies (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Saunders *et al.*, 2012). In justifying the suitability of this philosophy, the researcher assumed that through the collection of quantitative data, it is possible to predict whether the perceptions of certain factors significantly influence the years in business of female entrepreneurs in India. For example, as presented in Figure 2.4 depicting the conceptual framework, the outcome (Years in Business), as a measure of success for female entrepreneurs, can be predicted through the predictors. To objectively test and determine this outcome variable, it is necessary to adopt a philosophy that supports statistical analyses in evaluating challenges facing female entrepreneurs, such as the positivist stance (Creswell, 2014; Neuman, 2014; Bryman, 2016). Therefore, adopting a deductive approach aligns well with a positivist philosophy and ensures a

scientific approach to understand the complex dynamics of female entrepreneurial success and thus was considered the most suitable research approach for this dissertation.

Mono method quantitative

In positivism, reality is external and can be measured and understood scientifically. Mono-method quantitative involves using only quantitative research method for data collection and analysis, such as structured quantitative surveys. This method is well-suited with the positivist philosophy for investigating perceptions of factors and challenges influencing female entrepreneurial success due to its emphasis on objectivity, empirical evidence, hypothesis testing, and generalisability (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Creswell, 2014; Neuman, 2014; Bryman, 2016). Positivism advocates for objective observation and measurement, which are essential to identifying perceptions of the factors examined in this research. By utilising surveys and quantitative methods, it is possible to gather data that is not influenced by personal biases or subjective interpretations (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The empirical data collected using a survey can be statistically analysed to draw valid and reliable conclusions (Creswell, 2014). This provides empirical evidence for identifying trends and patterns regarding the challenges female entrepreneurs face. Furthermore, positivism supports hypothesis-driven research. In the context of this study, hypotheses can be formulated and tested using quantitative data analysis to predict female entrepreneurial success (Neuman, 2014). Additionally, positivism supports the generalisation of findings, enabling the conclusions drawn from the sample of respondents to be applicable to a broader population of female entrepreneurs in India (Bryman, 2016).

3.3 Research strategy

The nature and types of research questions guiding the research are of great value in determining the specific strategy that should be adopted (Bhattacharjee, 2012). The research questions are as follows:

1. Do perceptions of specific personal factors such as business knowledge (BK), risk-taking behaviour (RB), and emotional intelligence (EI) related to female entrepreneurial success predict years in business for female entrepreneurs in India?
2. Do perceptions of specific environmental factors such as family support (FS), social support (SS), gender stereotypes (GS), technological advancements (TA), and government policies (GP) related to female entrepreneurial success predict years in business for female entrepreneurs in India?
3. Do perceptions of specific traditional (TC) and modern challenges (MC) related to female entrepreneurial success predict years in business for female entrepreneurs in India?

To answer these questions and align with the positivist philosophy discussed above, a quantitative-based survey strategy was adopted. The justification of the positivist approach stems from its objectivity in creating knowledge regarding the factors influencing years in business for Indian female entrepreneurs. The philosophy also advocates for the use of scientific methods to guide knowledge creation by examining empirical findings (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Saunders *et al.*, 2012; Creswell, 2014; Neuman, 2014; Bryman, 2016). The empirical findings were collected using a

quantitative survey strategy and analysed using statistical techniques. Figure 3.1 presents the research process adopted in organising the research. First, the positivist philosophy was selected to guide knowledge creation. The deductive research approach was justified, and a mono-quantitative methodological choice was adopted.

Given that this is a social science study as opposed to a scientific study, an experimental strategy was not considered appropriate. A suitable strategy should be actionable and entail traits such as being specific, attainable, realistic, and time-bound (Bryman, 2012). A survey strategy was highly actionable and realistic in answering the guiding research questions, as it facilitated statistical analyses Saunders *et al.*, 2012. Since the study focuses on female business leaders, they can provide insights into their challenges in entrepreneurship engagements. The survey strategy was justified as it captures and represents the various key elements of the study. This ensures that the data collected accurately reflects the broader study population and variables under consideration. The survey strategy was justified as it has low costs, offers convenient data gathering techniques, provides good statistical significance, has very little or no subjectivity by observers, and yields precise results (Fowler, 2013; Denscombe, 2014).

The survey strategy consisted of the researcher collecting quantitative data by administering questionnaires to a sample of the target population. A survey strategy was the most appropriate technique to adopt in this study as the survey allows access to participants' perceptions and is an efficient method for reaching a large sample, especially since primary data had to be obtained, as opposed to an archival strategy depending on secondary sources (Bryman, 2012; Saunders *et al.*, 2012; Fowler, 2013; Denscombe, 2014).

3.4 Research design

Research design entails techniques that make it possible to achieve the desired research outcomes (Claybaugh, 2020). Following the selected methodology, many designs can be applied to the current research, including causal, correlational, cohort, cross-sectional, exploratory, and descriptive designs (Wright *et al.*, 2016). However, based on the positivist research philosophy, the cross-sectional design was the most appropriate for this study, as it is based on statistical analyses. This design allows for drawing inferences and aligns well with the research objectives (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019).

Data collection from a large sample is crucial for obtaining a comprehensive understanding of the perceptions and experiences of female entrepreneurs. Since cross-sectional studies are conducted at a single point, they are less time-consuming and more cost-effective than longitudinal studies, which require data collection over extended periods. Given the researchers' limited time and resources, this design is efficient and cost-effective (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Second, cross-sectional surveys facilitate the systematic collection of quantitative data, allowing statistical analysis to identify significant factors and challenges to female entrepreneurial success (Babbie, 2020). This is crucial for generating insights to inform policy and support measures to enhance female entrepreneurship. Furthermore, the ability to generalise findings from a representative sample to the broader population of female entrepreneurs in India enhances the external validity of the study (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019). Overall, a cross-sectional research design aligns well with the research objectives and provides a practical and effective means of examining the key factors and challenges female entrepreneurs perceive.

3.5 Research variables

According to Ariyaratne (2017), a research variable is the item or object of interest the researcher measures for changes in value. In this research, one outcome variable and ten predictors are examined using different models and tested using multinomial logistic regression analysis. The outcome variable (Years in business) is used as the central focus of the study, while the ten independent variables are identified as predictors that may predict it. A more detailed explanation of the analytical techniques and the tests employed to examine them is provided in **Section 4.2.2 Hypothesis Testing** of the next chapter. The variables for the current study are listed and defined below.

3.5.1 Outcome variable

Years in Business – ‘Years in business’ is an outcome variable used as a proxy measure for female entrepreneurial success due to its simplicity and data availability. The number of years female entrepreneurs have been in business represents the longevity of their businesses. Business longevity is an important indicator of resilience and perseverance, which are critical attributes for entrepreneurial success. This measure assumes that the longer a business survives, the more successful it is, reflecting an entrepreneur's ability to navigate barriers and challenges effectively. Longevity can indicate stability and growth, which are positive signs of business health and entrepreneurial adeptness (Robb and Watson, 2012). Female entrepreneurs often prioritise stability and long-term sustainability, making longevity a suitable measure of their success (Brush *et al.*, 2009). Jennings and Brush (2013) highlighted that female entrepreneurial success should be measured beyond financial metrics due to the societal and personal barriers they must overcome.

3.5.2 Predictors

Perceptions of Family Support (FS) – In the current study, FS was operationally defined as the perceptions females have of the assistance offered to them by their close family members for their entrepreneurship activities; this support may include assisting with work and household responsibilities, offering affective connection, and providing information and resources needed for entrepreneurship activities. According to Agustoni (2019), this kind of support can also be companionship, such as a sense of belonging, informational, emotional, or tangible, such as financial support (Alison, 2017). FS was measured using various elements, such as perceptions of family and household responsibilities, balancing family and work life, help with the care for young children, encouragement and moral support from friends and family, and financial support from family.

Perceptions of Social Support (SS) – In the current study, SS was operationally defined as perceptions of assistance from other people, mostly from one's social network; this may include help from other female partners, subordinates, peers, and friends. This kind of support can be informational, emotional, affective, and tangible (Alison, 2017; Agustoni, 2019). Continuous support from social networks helps sustain business operations, particularly during challenging times. This sustained support is crucial for long-term business survival and growth (Renzulli, Aldrich, and Moody, 2000). This variable was measured using elements based on female's perceptions of how social support impacts their success.

Perceptions of Emotional Intelligence (EI) – Research indicates that female entrepreneurs possess an innate sense of EI, which enables them to build strong interpersonal skills,

boost confidence, and increase resilience to stress, thereby facilitating sound decision-making and organisational growth (Alotaibi and Badawi, 2023). The importance of EI is further highlighted in the context of modern business environments, where it helps in managing the emotional and social demands of entrepreneurship, thus promoting gender equality and reducing the gap in business participation (Oyeku *et al.*, 2023). Empirical studies have shown that EI impacts various dimensions of entrepreneurial success, including financial and non-financial performance measures, with specific EI dimensions like self-regulation and empathy having particularly significant effects (Pathak, Muralidharan and Jha, 2022). Moreover, EI is essential for ensuring employee satisfaction and retention, which are critical for business success, especially in challenging times (Dervić, Burić, and Dervić, (2020). Overall, the integration of EI into entrepreneurial practises not only enhances individual success but also fosters a supportive and thriving business environment, making it a critical component for female entrepreneurs (Karia, 2021). In the current study, this variable was measured using perceptions of the importance of interpersonal skills, confidence, emotional resilience, the ability to build better business and interpersonal relationships, and empathy.

Perceptions of Gender Stereotypes (GS) – Basit *et al.* (2020) defined GS as the overall notion of females being perceived in society as lacking management skills, business experiences, and overall abilities to establish and manage enterprises; this leads to difficulties in enhancing the growth and development of their businesses. Gender stereotypes often result in lower entrepreneurial intentions among females by affecting their self-efficacy and confidence, which are crucial for entrepreneurial success (Rajamani, 2022; Devi, 2023). Gender stereotypes also often cast men as more competent

and agentic, while females are seen as more communal, affecting their self-perception and societal evaluation (Hamdani *et al.*, 2023). In the current study, this variable was measured using perceptions of gendered stereotypes affecting business opportunities, perceptions of entrepreneurship as a masculine activity, challenges with finance and patriarchal society structure, and preferences for dealing with men rather than females.

Perceptions of Business Knowledge (BK) – In the current study, business knowledge was operationally defined as the perceptions of information, skills, capabilities, experiences, and expert insight that a woman entrepreneur requires to be successful in business. Per Basit *et al.* (2020), business knowledge and skills shape all entrepreneurial activities by a woman. This variable was measured using elements such as perceptions of the importance of business management skills, prior work experience, industry-specific knowledge, entrepreneurial training, and education.

Perceptions of Risk-Taking Behaviour (RB) – RB was operationally defined as perceptions around the willingness of a woman entrepreneur to undertake business activities that involve potential losses to achieve certain economic gains. According to Batool and Ullah (2017), the RB of female entrepreneurs reflect their business vision and leadership. In the current study, this variable was measured using elements such as perceptions of the importance of risk-taking ability, risk attitude perceptions towards new projects and approaches, and high market risks. According to Basit *et al.* (2020), RB is an inherent factor in the success of business entrepreneurship.

Perceptions of Government Policies (GP)– Government policy was operationally defined as perceptions of declarations by the government or leadership on plans and intentions for a certain course of action for entrepreneurship and business initiatives. As explained by

Belwal, Belwal, and Fatema (2014), policy guides how the government supports a community, business, institution, or group of individuals. In the current study, this variable was measured using elements such as perceptions of the importance of government support for funding and subsidies, government support in terms of laws and regulations, coordination between government departments, the regulatory environment protecting the investments of female entrepreneurs, and high rates of insurance, taxes, and duties.

Perceptions of Technological Advancements (TA) – In the current study, TA were operationally defined as perceptions of changes in the way a service or product is delivered or produced that reduce the needed resource inputs and enhance efficiency. As explained by Boermans and Willebrands (2017), change should be progressive. Basit *et al.* (2020) stated that innovation is fundamental in enhancing entrepreneurship growth and development, is a major challenge among females, and can be measured by technological skills and competencies. In this study, this variable was measured mainly by perceptions of technological advancements, their level of competencies in using new technologies, information and communication technology (ICT) tools, automatic transactions, and awareness of opportunities in the digital economy.

All the predictors mentioned above were classified into personal and environmental factors to measure their ability to predict the outcome variable of years in business (a proxy measure of female entrepreneurial success).

Personal factors are intrinsic to the individual and are shaped by their experiences, traits, and skills. These factors directly influence individual behaviour and decision-making.

Hence, the perceptions of business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence are classified as personal factors.

Environmental factors are external to the individual and encompass the broader social, economic, and cultural contexts. These factors are outside the individual's control but significantly impact their opportunities and constraints. Hence, perceptions of family support, social support, gender stereotypes, technological advancements, and government policies are classified as environmental factors.

In this study, traditional and modern challenges are classified as challenges and analysed independently as predictors to determine their impact on the outcome variable (years in business) and the explanation for these predictors is as given below:

Perceptions of Modern Challenges (MC) – This variable was operationally defined as the perception of conditions in the contemporary business environment hindering or limiting the operations and success of female enterprises. Several such conditions may include stiff market competition (Kabote, 2018), balancing of responsibilities (Hossain and Rahman, 2018), and an unfavourable business environment (Kikula, 2018). Modern challenges include factors such as the perceptions of high cost of living, increasing child education expenses, unequal pay, recent government policies, evolving work and family roles, perceptions of social media, and globalisation.

Perceptions of Traditional Challenges (TC) – In this study, this variable refers to the perceptions of traditional practices that directly limit female's entrepreneurial activities. They include perceptions of female gender roles and traditional perceptions about females in India. As explained by Giusta, Marina, and Razzu (2019), in many societies

(including India), many females are not afforded the same opportunities for education as men. Additionally, most business opportunities are offered to men, who tend to dominate most fields.

3.6 Research hypotheses

The study tests three hypotheses and their sub-hypotheses using data collected from respondents.

H1: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of personal factors such as business (BK), risk-taking behaviour (RB), and emotional intelligence (EI) significantly predict years in business (YIB)

H1a: Perceptions of business knowledge (BK) significantly predict years in business.

H1b: Perceptions of risk-taking behaviour (RB) significantly predict years in business.

H1c: Perceptions of emotional intelligence (EI) significantly predict years in business.

H2: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of environmental factors such as family support (FS), social support (SS), gender stereotypes (GS), technological advancements (TA), and government policies (GP) significantly predict years in business (YIB).

H2a: Perceptions of family support (FS) significantly predict years in business.

H2b: Perceptions of social support (SS) significantly predict years in business.

H2c: Perceptions of gender stereotypes (GS) significantly predict years in business.

H2d: Perceptions of technological advancements (TA) significantly predict years in business.

H2e: Perceptions of government policies (GP) significantly predict years in business.

H3: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of challenges such as traditional challenges (TC) and modern challenges (MC) significantly predict years in business.

H3a: Perceptions of traditional challenges (TC) significantly predict years in business.

H3b: Perceptions of modern challenges (MC) significantly predict years in business.

3.7 Population and sampling

3.7.1 Research population

According to Ariyaratne (2017), a research population is the collection of objects or individuals that an inquiry focuses on. The purpose of a research population is the provision of data about the phenomenon studied. This study focuses on establishing the challenges faced by female entrepreneurs and how these challenges can be addressed.

Thus, female entrepreneurs running businesses in India for any duration of time constituted the main research population for the current study. It includes females who already own or run small, medium, or large businesses in formal or informal sectors.

Females who are already in entrepreneurship were considered useful in providing information based on their perspectives and experiences concerning the specific challenges they have encountered.

Collecting data from the entire population of female entrepreneurs is not feasible. Hence, the researcher worked with a sample of the target population. According to Bajpai

(2011), a sample of the target population is the specific subset of the research population the researcher bases their study on to draw conclusions that can be generalised across the entire group. The target population is the specific group of individuals or objects that provide data for analysis (Bryman, 2012). According to Charulakshmi and Thaiyalnayaki (2019), SMEs maintain the number of employees, revenues, and assets below a given threshold. Each country may have its own definition of an SME and threshold level. For the current study, the researcher considered self-employed female entrepreneurs and those who own SMEs or large businesses with any number of employees and who have run their businesses for any duration.

In this study, the population of interest comprises female entrepreneurs in India. Given the broad scope of this study, the sampling method was designed to be inclusive and representative of various demographics, sectors, and geographical locations within India. To enable a wider range of female entrepreneurs to participate, an online data collection strategy was implemented without any geographic constraints within India. This approach ensured the inclusion of females with a diverse set of experiences and backgrounds involving various ages, educational levels, types of businesses, sectors, and regions. As a result, the sample comprised female entrepreneurs from various parts of India engaged in various business activities, thereby enhancing the representativeness of the population. This diversity in the sample provides a comprehensive overview of the myriad challenges female entrepreneurs face in the Indian context. The findings thus reflect a broad spectrum of experiences and challenges, offering valuable insights into the overarching barriers perceived by female entrepreneurs in India.

3.7.2 Sampling strategy and sample size

Since it would be very costly and nearly impossible to survey all female entrepreneurs in India, the researcher only worked with a small proportion, which constituted the sample.

A sample is the subset or proportion of the target population selected to participate in the study, while a sampling strategy is a plan used to select the sample (Bajpai, 2011).

According to Ariyaratne (2017), a sample should be highly representative of the target population to enable generalisation of the results across the population.

Moreover, it is important to explain how a sample representative of the target population was selected and how many respondents were considered an appropriate sample.

Strategies for selecting individuals as participants include probabilistic and nonprobabilistic (Lance and Hattori, 2016). While nonprobabilistic techniques are considered subjective, probability-based sampling techniques are considered objective, unbiased, and appropriate in studies where a researcher is independent of the subjects of the study (Groves, 2009). Probabilistic sampling strategies include cluster sampling, stratified sampling, systematic sampling, and simple random sampling (Shahrokh and Dougherty, 2014).

According to Bryman (2012), in nonprobabilistic sampling, not all members of the target population are given an equal chance to participate in the study. Sampling is instead based on the researcher's subjective judgement and does not involve randomness in the selection of the participants (Campbell, 2016). Examples include convenience sampling, voluntary response sampling, purposive sampling, and snowball sampling.

To determine the most suitable sampling strategy for the current research, it was important to examine the existing situation. Given the size of India and the lack of data, it was not possible to determine the accurate population of SME female entrepreneurs, which limits the use of the probability sampling technique. Therefore, in the current study, the nonprobability-based sampling technique was used to select participants.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, it was not possible to physically visit the female entrepreneurs for data collection. Furthermore, the study was based in India, which covers a wide area, and meeting each research participant would have been too costly and time-consuming. Based on the need to collect data from female entrepreneurs from India only, the convenience sampling method was used to select the study participants.

Convenience sampling ensured that valid and reliable data was collected from the participants to facilitate addressing the research questions.

Questionnaire participants selection criteria– To select participants for the online survey, the researcher used a nonprobability technique known as convenience sampling.

According to Claybaugh (2020), in a convenience sampling strategy, the researcher only includes members from a sample of the target population who are most accessible and willing to participate. The strategy is inexpensive and provides the researcher with an easy way of collecting data. However, it is not easy to determine whether the sample selected is representative of the entire research population (Campbell, 2016). Using the convenience sampling strategy, the researcher distributed the research instrument (questionnaire) through online platforms and requested female business owners in India to take part in the survey.

Thus, the questionnaire was distributed to female entrepreneurs who have financially invested in and were actively running a business in any sector in India for any duration of time. To ensure that only female entrepreneurs actively running a business were included in the survey, the researcher included a question in the demographics section in the survey questionnaire (Appendix D: Research Questionnaire, Question 6) asking how long they have been in business. There are six options for this question, and the participants were allowed to choose only one option. The first option for this (Question 6) was not in business, and the other five options provided were for the duration of their business in years (Less than 2 years, 3-5 years, 6-9 years, 9-10 years and Above 10 years). All the respondents who chose option 1 (Not in business) for Question 6 were excluded from the survey to ensure that only active female entrepreneurs were included. There were 118 respondents who chose option 1 (Not in business) and hence these respondents were excluded from the survey as they were not in business.

The female entrepreneurs were contacted via social media platforms like Facebook, LinkedIn, and WhatsApp. The survey was open for one month. The researcher received 466 responses by the end of the month. Of these 466 remaining responses, 38 were deleted due to missing outcome variable (Years in business) responses. Five of the remaining 428 responses were deleted as the respondents had not given consent but still answered a few questions. The total number of responses left was 423. Of these 423 responses, females in business were filtered out (*they were filtered out by applying the 'if condition' in SPSS). Therefore, respondents who were not in business (118 respondents, as explained in the previous paragraph) were removed from the study. Finally, a total of 161 responses were excluded from the 466 responses during the data

cleaning process for various reasons such as missing outcome variable responses, lack of consent, and respondents not being in business. Further information on data cleaning is provided in Chapter 4, Section 4.1.1. After the data-cleaning process, 305 of the 466 responses were included in the analysis. Of these 305 responses, some incomplete responses contained missing values of less than 3% of the sample. However, these responses were still included in the final analysis to make maximum use of the data available (Pallant, 2016).

The evaluation of the demographic details in Table 3.1 revealed that most of the female entrepreneurs in the study were between the ages of 26 and 45, 68.9% were married, most had a good education level with at least a bachelor’s degree, and most had at least one child. The insights also indicated that most of them had operated their businesses for a period between less than two and five years.

Table 3.1 Demographic Profile of Participants

Demographics	Number	Percentage
Age		
18–25	53	17.4
26–35	117	38.4
36–45	111	36.4
46 or older	22	7.2
Marital Status		
Single	76	24.9
Married	210	68.9
Divorced	14	4.6
Widowed	3	1
Highest Education Level		

High School or Less	42	13.8
Diploma	66	21.6
Bachelor's Degree	116	38
Master's Degree	73	23.9
Doctoral Degree	7	2.3
Years in Business		
Less than 2 years	116	38
3–5 years	115	37.7
6–8 years	49	16.1
9–10 years	10	3.3
Above 10 years	15	4.9
Number of Children		
No Children	79	27.8
1 Child	93	30.5
2–3 Children	98	32.1
4–5 Children	14	4.6

3.8 Data collection tools

In the current research, the data were quantitative and from primary sources. As such, the researcher used a self-administered questionnaire as the core instrument.

3.8.1 Self-administrated questionnaire

A structured questionnaire was used to collect data through online surveys, which enabled the researcher to collect numerical data aligned with the adopted quantitative research methodology. Furthermore, the choice of closed-ended questions enabled the respondents to select answers from a list instead of writing them out to motivate their participation in the research. Wilson (2010) highlighted the advantages of using

questionnaires, including their economic advantages, wide coverage, ease and rapidity of data collection, and high validity for research findings.

3.8.1.1 Questionnaire response format

According to Collis and Hussey (2014), when constructing the questionnaire, three possible formats can be considered: closed-ended, open-ended, or a combination of the two. In this study, a combination of open-ended and closed-ended questions was used, though most questions were developed using the closed-ended format. Only one open-ended question was used, asking respondents to describe the kind of training they completed before initiating their businesses. The closed-ended format was chosen because, as explained by Claybaugh (2020), it makes it easier to analyse the data, especially using statistical tools. However, it has the disadvantage of limiting the responses, and the researcher may fail to obtain all possible answers. The closed-ended format was presented on a five-point Likert rating scale where participants could choose their level of agreement concerning different statements. Additionally, other closed-ended questions in Part A regarding, for example, their marital status or the number of children they had, allowed the respondents to select responses from a list of given options.

3.8.1.2 Construction of the questionnaire

The questionnaire consisted of two parts, A and B. Part A contained nine questions, and Part B contained 11 questions.

Part A provided information on the demographic characteristics of the participants, which included elements such as age, marital status, number of children, highest education level

achieved, years in business, whether they had an interest in starting a business, whether they had any training related to their business before the business was established, and the kind of training undertaken. A total of nine questions were presented, eight of which were in a closed-ended format with options to select from; the ninth question was open-ended and asked respondents to describe the kind of business training they completed.

Part B provided measures of the included research variables.

Question 10 in Part B measured the perceptions of female entrepreneurs regarding family support and female entrepreneurial success. Family support measures were adapted according to the context of this study from an FS scale designed by Uddin and Bhuiyan (2019). In the original questionnaire, Uddin and Bhuiyan (2019) used 20 items to measure FS. In the current study, which focused on perceptions of family support, five items were included after the validity test (using factor analysis) and reliability test (inter-item correlation and Cronbach's alpha test) and presented in a five-point Likert scale format.

Question 11 measured perceptions of the social support (SS) of female entrepreneurs. To measure SS, an instrument was adapted from the original 25-item scale by Sahban, Kumar, and Sri Ramalu (2015) examining the dimensions of SS. The original questionnaire was presented on a 10-point Likert scale. In the current study, a five-point scale was used, and four questions were included regarding perceptions of SS.

Question 12 was designed to assess the extent to which female entrepreneurs perceived the business knowledge (BK) to be important for entrepreneurial success. No validated questionnaire scale for measuring entrepreneurship or BK was available; therefore, the

items in this section were self-developed for this study, with a focus on providing measures of the extent of participants' perceptions of the importance of business management skills, technical know-how, and workshops and training. Four items were self-developed to measure the perceptions of BK among female entrepreneurs.

Question 13 measured female's perceptions of the importance of risk-taking behaviour (RB). To measure RB, the Entrepreneurial Orientation Scale by Bolton (2012) was adapted to this study's context. In the original questionnaire, Bolton (2012) provided five items for measuring RB, which were used in this section. The items focused on assessing perceptions of the importance of risk-taking ability, unique approaches and activities, difficulties due to high risks in the market, and taking higher risks than men.

Question 14 assessed perceptions of negative gender stereotypes (GS) affecting female entrepreneurs. As mentioned, no validated scale for measuring GS in business or entrepreneurship was available. Thus, all items for measuring GS were self-developed for this study. The main consideration was presenting questions that provided an indication of the perceptions of the level of gender stereotyping in entrepreneurship. Five items were self-developed, and they mainly focused on gendered perception, perceptions of gendered inequality in access to resources, gendered biases in opportunities, and challenges in patriarchal societies.

Question 15 measured female entrepreneurs' perceptions of EI using five items were self-developed based on literature on EI using a five-point Likert Scale: interpersonal skills, confidence, emotional resilience, the ability to build interpersonal relationships, and the empathic nature of female (Alsos and Ljunggren, 2016; Baassiri, 2018; Agustoni, 2019).

Question 16 provided measures of perceptions of technological advancements (TA). As mentioned, no validated scale for measuring TA in business or entrepreneurship was available. Therefore, all items for measuring TA were self-developed for this study. Five items focused on measuring the extent to which female entrepreneurs perceived using technology as important for their business activities. The items were drafted and presented in a five-point Likert scale format.

Question 17 included items for measuring perceptions of government policies (GP) in relation to entrepreneurship. No validated scale for measuring GP in business or entrepreneurship was available, so all items for measuring GP were self-developed for this study and presented in a five-point Likert scale format. The items focused on measuring females' perceptions of the availability of government funding, direct subsidies, high insurance rates, taxes and duties, government department coordination, and regulatory environment (Belwal, Belwal and Fatema, 2014).

Question 18 examined perceptions of the role of traditional challenges in the success of female entrepreneurs. The questionnaire examined two dimensions related to this variable, including the traditional roles of females in the family and traditional perceptions about females increasing business risk. The dimensions were self-developed for this study, and a five-point Likert scale was used based on findings from the literature.

Question 19 focused on perceptions of modern challenges in relation to the success of female entrepreneurs. Eight items were self-developed and presented on a five-point Likert scale. The dimensions ranged from perceptions of unequal pay for working

females to perceptions of the high cost of living, the increasing expense of childcare, globalisation, social media perception, and recent government policies.

Lastly, Question 20 evaluated perceptions of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the success of female entrepreneurs. Three items were presented on a five-point Likert scale and self-developed. These items measured perceptions of whether COVID-19 provided opportunities to businesses, whether it affected businesses, and whether it increased the barriers to success for female entrepreneurs in India.

For all the variables, the overall score was determined by calculating the average of the different items (factors) that were included. The final questionnaire constructed is attached in Appendix D: Research Questionnaire. Table 3.1 in Appendix A summarises the main constructs and items considered when constructing the questionnaire, as discussed in the above paragraphs.

3.9 Research validity and reliability

3.9.1 Validity of the questionnaire

Validity establishes the extent to which the research instrument (the questionnaire) measures the envisaged perceptions of factors as intended by the scholar. It is important to discover how appropriate the research instruments are and how likely they are to enable the researcher to assess the main variables. For questionnaires, various types of validity can be considered, including construct validity, content validity, and criterion validity. Each of these validity types ensures that constructs in a study precisely measure what they are intended to measure (Campbell, 2016). For this research, focus was placed on construct validity, and the researcher relied on the feedback given by their supervisor

as to what extent the data collection instrument could be relied on in answering the research questions. In addition to the supervisor's feedback, factor analysis was employed to validate the questionnaire.

This statistical technique was utilised to ensure that the questionnaire items effectively measure the underlying constructs they are intended to capture. The steps and results are summarised in this section, with detailed factor loadings in Appendix A: Table 3.2 Factor analysis. Data were collected through a survey instrument targeting female entrepreneurs in India. The survey included items related to various personal and environmental factors and challenges perceived to influence their entrepreneurial success. These items were measured on a five-point Likert scale, from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Factors were extracted using principal component analysis (PCA), with eigenvalues greater than 1 considered significant (Kaiser, 1960). The cumulative eigenvalues reaching 100% indicated that the factors extracted explained the total variance in the data. Factor loadings were examined, and items loading 0.4 or higher were considered significant. Sample size is important when interpreting factor loadings (Hair *et al.*, 2010). For a sample size exceeding 300, Hair *et al.* (2010) recommend a minimum threshold of 0.3, but a higher threshold of 0.4 provides more robust results and confidence in the stability and reliability of the loading values. Additionally, loadings of 0.4 indicate a moderate to strong relationship, ensuring that included items are meaningful contributors to the factor. Analysing the communalities and the total variance (Appendix A: Table 3.3 Total variance for all the factors in the appendices explained by the extracted components confirmed that the selected variables are well-represented by the underlying factors. High communalities indicated that a significant portion of the variance in each variable is

explained by the extracted components, demonstrating the questionnaire's reliability and further supporting the instrument's validity by showing that much of the information in the data is captured by these components (Field, 2018). This validation process ensures that the questionnaire is a reliable and valid tool for assessing factors and challenges influencing female entrepreneurial success (Hair *et al.*, 2010; Campbell, 2016; Field, 2018).

The factor analysis revealed that perceptions of various personal and environmental factors and challenges significantly influence the success of female entrepreneurs in India. Each factor identified through the factor analysis suggests that the items are aligned with the underlying constructs in the study, contributing to the validity of the questionnaire. Detailed factor loadings are provided in the appendices (Appendix A: Table 3.2 Factor analysis and Table 3.3 Total variance for all the factors), ensuring transparency and allowing for further reference.

3.9.2 Questionnaire reliability

A reliability test was performed on the questionnaire to determine the extent to which outcomes in the study could be replicated or be similar if the same instruments were reused. Research reliability is the degree to which an instrument produces stable and consistent results (Bajpai, 2011). There are four types of reliability to examine to ascertain this consistency: test-retest reliability, parallel form reliability, inter-rater reliability, and internal consistency reliability. For this research, the internal consistency reliability of the questionnaire was evaluated, and the researcher relied on the Cronbach's alpha ratio test, in which a minimum of 0.7 is accepted, as recommended by Creswell (2014). The construct in this study has items ranging from 2 to 8. If the number of items

in the scale is low, then Cronbach's value for this scale can be small, indicating lower reliability. Hence, using the inter-item correlation for scales with fewer items is better. Thus, for the reliability analysis, inter-item correlation was also conducted for each construct examined in the study to ensure the reliability of the study findings. Results of both Cronbach's alpha and Inter-item correlation have been presented in Chapter 4, Section 4.1.3, Table 4.1 Reliability Statistics.

3.10 Pilot Study

Before the actual primary data collection exercise was carried out, the researcher tested the suitability of the research instrument for gathering data. To achieve this, the researcher used two methods.

1. The researcher revised the questionnaire several times based on the supervisor's feedback.
2. The researcher distributed the instrument to 20 respondents, and the feedback obtained from these respondents was used to revise the questionnaire and make it simple and easy to answer.

The respondents to this pilot survey exercise were friends or acquaintances of the researcher. The respondents in the pilot test were not included in the final test to avoid subjective responses since they knew the research questions in advance. Conducting a pilot test was an important step in refining the questionnaire and enhancing its effectiveness. The feedback obtained during this phase was very helpful. Respondents highlighted specific areas of difficulty, such as complex language and redundant or unclear questions. They also indicated that due to the overall length of the questionnaire,

the time taken to complete the survey was around 15–20 minutes or more, which made it burdensome to complete. Based on the feedback of the respondents, the researcher carefully revised the questionnaire. Questions that were ambiguous, unclear, or difficult to understand by the respondents were reframed to simplify the language, ensuring they were easy to understand and respond to, and the overall structure was streamlined. These modifications improved the clarity and the flow of the questionnaire. As a direct result of these improvements, the time required to complete the survey was reduced from its initial duration to approximately 8–10 minutes. This reduction enhanced the likelihood of obtaining accurate and reliable responses, as participants were less likely to experience fatigue or disengagement.

3.11 Distribution of the questionnaire

At the time this research was undertaken, the world was facing challenges due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which limited the ability to meet people physically and undertake paper-based surveys in person. Therefore, the researcher chose to use online surveys. An online account and the questionnaire were created using Google Forms. The link to the survey instrument (questionnaire) was shared on social media platforms like Facebook, LinkedIn, and WhatsApp, targeting female entrepreneurs in India on their social media pages and groups for female entrepreneurs in India, along with a brief description of the research and the eligibility criteria for participants. Once the respondents clicked the link, they were directed to the questionnaire page. The page explained the research topic and eligibility criteria for the participants and provided the necessary information regarding voluntary participation, ethical considerations, and the time required to answer the survey before requesting consent.

In the first question, respondents were required to provide consent that they were willing to share their opinions and information to facilitate knowledge creation for the research. The respondents had one month to complete the questionnaire to make it possible to gather sufficient data. At the end of the one-month period, 466 responses had been gathered, and the survey was closed. Once the survey was terminated, the researcher accessed the platform and downloaded the data. The data were then cleaned and sorted to be ready for analysis using the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS).

3.12 Data analysis techniques

Since the questionnaire collected quantitative data, the researcher used statistical methods for analysis. The researcher used SPSS software to synthesise the collected data, as it is reliable and provides high-accuracy results, which can be beneficial for predicting the key challenges faced by female entrepreneurs in this study. It offers basic and advanced statistical analysis, which makes it a suitable choice for this research. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used. The descriptive statistics included the demographic profile of the participants, such as age, marital status, education level, years in business, and number of children. It also includes the frequency and percentage of the participants. The evaluation of the demographic details of the respondents is provided in Table 3.1. The inferential statistics included multinomial logistic regression to establish whether the models used in the study were reliable. It also aided in making inferences to confirm the descriptive analysis results.

Multinomial logistic regression techniques were the main statistical tool for modelling and predicting the outcome variable. The use of multinomial logistic regressions allowed the research to predict how years in business (a proxy measure for the success of female

entrepreneurs) can be predicted from perceptions of personal factors (business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence) and perceptions of environmental factors (family support, social support, gender stereotypes, technological advancements, and government policies). It also allowed to predict the outcome variable based on perceptions of traditional and modern challenges. The model made it possible to identify the significant predictors for the outcome variable that guided the study based on the research objectives. The outcomes from this analysis were used to accept or reject the study hypotheses.

Justification for using multinomial logistic regression (MLR)

There are two main types of statistical techniques.

1. Parametric statistical techniques
2. Non-parametric statistical techniques

Based on the research objective and the research questions, parametric statistical techniques were chosen for this study, as they help to explore the relationships among the independent and dependent variables rather than compare groups in the non-parametric statistical techniques (Pallant, 2016). Although parametric tests are more powerful than the non-parametric tests, they have stricter criteria about the data and their assumptions (Pallant, 2016, p. 115). Different types of parametric tests include correlation, partial correlation, multiple regression, and logistic regression. To further decide which parametric test should be used depends on many factors such as distribution of the data, the type of the variables and the research questions. For this study, considering the distribution of the data, which is not normally distributed; the type of the variables,

categorical variables; and the research questions that aim to predict the outcome variable (Years in business) from the set of predictors, multinomial logistic regression (MLR) is the most appropriate test for this study.

Multinomial logistic regression (MLR) was chosen because it is designed to model relationships between a set of independent variables (Predictors) and a categorical dependent variable (Outcome variable) with more than two categories. Further discussion on the choices made in this context has been provided in chapter 4, section 4.2.2, page 134. Unlike linear regression, which assumes a continuous dependent variable, multinomial logistic regression (MLR) accommodates situations where the outcome variable is nominal and unordered, such as categorical responses. This makes it ideal for the dataset used in this study, where the outcome variable (Years in business) has multiple categories (Pallant, 2016; Field, 2018).

Other statistical techniques were considered, such as ordinal logistic regression. Ordinal logistic regression was deemed inappropriate because it assumes an inherent order among the categories of the dependent variable, which was not applicable to this study (Pallant, 2016). Discriminant analysis, while suitable for categorical outcomes, relies on assumptions about the normal distribution of predictors within each group, which the data did not meet (Field, 2018). Multinomial logistic regression (MLR) was more appropriate given the dataset's size and characteristics. It can handle moderate to large sample sizes effectively and provides interpretable coefficients for each category of the dependent variable relative to a reference category. This ensures a robust analysis that aligns with the study's objective of understanding the predictors of categorical outcomes (Schneider *et al.*, 2010; Pallant, 2016; Field, 2018).

3.13 Ethical considerations

First, consent was gained from the potential respondents via a declaration they had to agree to before taking part in the study and responding to the questions. Second, the researcher ensured that participants were allowed to freely withdraw from the survey process at any time. Third, efforts were made to strictly abide by anonymity and privacy provisions, ensuring that the respondents' details and personally identifiable information, such as names and contact addresses, would not be disclosed. Fourth, the research was conducted in strict adherence to the beneficence principle, with efforts made to minimise any physical and psychological harm to respondents but maximise any potential benefits. Fifth, the researcher ensured that the sources of information used for the study were properly acknowledged through in-text citations and an updated reference list based on the provisions of the university. Moreover, the researcher ensured that integrity was observed in data collection, analysis, and presentation. Only data collected through the proposed instruments were analysed and included in inference-making. The researcher ensured that the findings of the study were used only for the intended academic purposes. Finally, the study was conducted under strict conformity with the principle of avoiding any form of exaggeration or deception.

3.14 Chapter Summary

This chapter has provided a detailed presentation and justification of the approaches and methods used in this research. The areas discussed include the research philosophy, research strategy, research design, target research population, sampling techniques and sample size, nature and source of the data, data collection tools, data analysis techniques, pilot study, validity tests, reliability tests, research limitations, and ethical considerations.

Chapter 4 Results and Analysis

This chapter is divided into two parts:

<p>Part A</p> <p>4.1 Data Preparation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Data Cleaning➤ Missing Data➤ Data Reliability Analysis	<p>Part B</p> <p>4.2 Testing the Hypotheses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Verifying Assumptions for Multinomial Regression Analysis➤ Hypothesis Testing➤ Model 1 – Personal Factors➤ Model 2 – Environmental Factors➤ Model 3 – Challenges
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These sections provide a comprehensive narrative of the findings, which will help in interpreting the results for meaningful scholarly contributions.

Part A

4.1 Data preparation

Before presenting the hypothesis testing, this section screens the data to ensure its validity and reliability. It is divided into two subsections. The first section focuses on data cleaning, a critical process that ensures the accuracy and consistency of the dataset, and data reliability, which examines the strength and reliability of the measurement tools.

4.1.1 Data cleaning

Data collected from the questionnaire were downloaded into a CSV file and then uploaded to SPSS software. The data were coded, and the variables were defined in SPSS. Following this, the data were screened and cleaned to check for errors before starting the analysis to ensure reliable research outcomes. The following section outlines the procedures used in the current

study to clean up the data. Alotaibi, Pardede, and Tomy (2023) described data cleaning as removing any corrupted, missing, incomplete, or incorrect data from a given dataset. The process is important to ensure the analysed data are accurate and high-quality.

4.1.1.1 Initial screening

The questionnaire yielded 466 responses. Of these 466 remaining responses, 38 were deleted due to missing outcome variable responses. Five of the remaining 428 responses were deleted as the respondents had not given consent but still answered a few questions. The total number of responses left was 423. Of these 423 responses, female in business were filtered out (*they were filtered out by applying the 'if condition' in SPSS). Therefore, all respondents who did not yet own businesses were removed from the study. After the data-cleaning process, 305 responses were included in the final analysis. Of these responses, some incomplete responses contained missing values of less than 3% of the sample. However, these responses were still included in the final analysis via pairwise exclusion of missing data (Pallant, 2016) to make maximum use of the data available.

4.1.1.2 Further screening

To assess for errors, the data were screened for any values that fell outside of the expected range by inspecting the frequency statistics and descriptive statistics for each variable. The minimum and maximum values were checked to ensure they were within the range. In addition, the number of valid and missing cases was checked to identify any errors in the data. No out-of-range values were spotted during the dataset inspection.

4.1.2 Missing data

Any items that had not been answered were removed when the data were cleaned. However, some incomplete responses contained missing values of less than 3% of the sample. Pallant (2016, p. 58) suggested using pairwise exclusion of missing data unless addressing cases that

need the whole results. Hence, for this study, the option of pairwise exclusion of missing data was chosen to maximise the use of the data available. Additionally, Kline (2016) argued that missing data of less than 5% in a large sample is less of an issue. Therefore, the responses with the missing values of less than 3% were retained for further analysis.

4.1.3 Data reliability analysis

The reliability of the constructs in this study was assessed using internal consistency reliability to ensure that all items on the scale measured the same construct. Cronbach's alpha is commonly used to measure the scale's reliability, with values ranging from 0 to 1. It mainly relies on the number of items in the scale. If the number of items in the scale is low, then Cronbach's value for this scale can be small, indicating lower reliability. Hence, using the inter-item correlation for scales with fewer items is better. The values for these scales, according to Briggs and Cheek (1986), range from 0.2 to 0.4 (Pallant, 2016). The construct in this study has items ranging from 2 to 8. Thus, for the reliability analysis, inter-item correlation was considered for each construct examined in the study. Additionally, Cronbach's alpha was also calculated for each construct to ensure that the variables were consistent. The constructs in the study were the predictors, which included perceptions of the following:

1. Family Support
2. Social Support
3. Business Knowledge
4. Risk-Taking Behaviour
5. Emotional Intelligence
6. Gender Stereotypes
7. Technological Advancements

8. Government Policies
9. Traditional Challenges
10. Modern Challenges
11. Impact of COVID-19

Table 4.1 outlines Cronbach's alpha and the mean inter-item correlation for the scales. Inter-item correlation for all the constructs ranges from .119 to .619, and Cronbach's alpha ranges from .235 to .898.

Table 4.1 Reliability Statistics

Scale Name	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha	Mean Inter-Item Correlation
Family Support	5	.685	.353
Social Support	4	.765	.458
Business Knowledge	4	.748	.464
Risk-Taking Behaviour	5	.891	.619
Gender Stereotypes	5	.844	.534
Emotional Intelligence	5	.729	.383
Technological Advancements	5	.639	.321
Government Policies	5	.898	.635
Traditional Challenges	2	.788	.658
Modern Challenges	8	.868	.458
Impact of COVID-19	3	.235	.119

No negative values are seen in the Inter-Item Correlation Matrix for all the scales, which indicates that the items measure the same underlying construct and have been properly reverse scored. Although Cronbach's alpha value is less than the recommended 0.7 value in the Family Support (.685) and Technological Advancements scales (.639), the inter-item correlation value of all the scales (except the Impact of COVID-19 scale) falls in the recommended range. Hence, 10 out of 11 scales were retained for further analysis and considered reliable. However, the obtained results for the impact of COVID-19 indicate a low

level of internal consistency, as reflected by Cronbach's alpha (.235) and average inter-item correlation (.119). The low Cronbach's alpha suggests a potential lack of coherence among the items within this scale, and the average inter-item correlation further supports this observation.

In light of these reliability indicators, it was determined that the Impact of COVID-19 variable does not meet the requisite standards for internal consistency. As a result, this variable was excluded from further analyses to ensure the overall robustness and reliability of the study findings. By exploring the remaining variables, each proven internally consistent, the study endeavours to unveil insights into the intricate relationships and patterns within the dataset. This selective inclusion of variables ensures that the subsequent analyses are founded on a solid and reliable empirical basis, contributing to the overarching research objectives.

Part B

4.2 Testing the hypotheses

Before testing the hypotheses using multinomial logistic analysis, the data were checked to determine whether they fulfilled assumptions regarding sample size, multicollinearity, and outliers.

4.2.1 Verifying assumptions for multinomial regression analysis

4.2.1.1 Sample size

Tabachnick and Fidell (2013, p. 123) provided a formula to calculate the required sample size based on the number of independent variables (Pallant, 2016, p. 151). The formula for calculating the sample size is

$$N > 50 + 8m$$

Where m is the number of independent variables or predictors.

In the study, there were 10 predictors. Thus, the calculation was as follows:

$$305 > 50 + 8 (10)$$

$$305 > 130$$

Therefore, the sample of 305 participants was considered valid.

Three tests were conducted for three different models using the 10 predictors for the same outcome variable.

For test 1, perceptions of personal factors such as business knowledge (BK), risk-taking behaviour (RB), and emotional intelligence (EI) were the three predictors of the years in business (YIB) outcome variable.

For test 2, perceptions of environmental factors such as family support (FS), social support (SS), gender stereotypes (GS), technological advancements (TA), and government policies (GP) were the five predictors of the years in business (YIB) outcome variable.

For test 3, perceptions of challenges such as traditional (TC) and modern challenges (MC) were tested for the years in business (YIB) outcome variable.

4.2.1.2 Multicollinearity

Regression is sensitive to multicollinearity. It is about the relationship between two independent variables. If these variables are highly correlated, then multicollinearity exists. Multicollinearity can be checked using collinearity diagnostics from the regression output. Two values are important in determining multicollinearity among the independent variables. These values are tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and can be found in Table 4.2. A tolerance value smaller than .10 indicates multicollinearity. The VIF value is the inverse of the tolerance value. VIF values above 10 suggest multicollinearity.

Table 4.2 presents the collinearity diagnostics. The tolerance values are higher than .10 for all the constructs in the study and range from 0.342 to 0.749. The VIF values are under 10 for all the variables and range from 1.335 to 2.922. Both the tolerance values and the VIF values indicate that the assumption of multicollinearity has not been violated and there is no multicollinearity between the variables.

Table 4.2 Tolerance and VIF Values

	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Family Support	.623	1.605
Social Support	.576	1.736
Business Knowledge	.601	1.664
Risk-Taking Behaviour	.677	1.478
Gender Stereotypes	.391	2.555
Emotional Intelligence	.638	1.566
Technological Advancements	.647	1.545
Government Policies	.432	2.313
Traditional Challenges	.749	1.335
Modern Challenges	.342	2.922

4.2.1.3 Outliers

Outliers can be a bigger concern than normality because they can drastically impact the power of significance tests in an analysis (Field, 2018, p. 236). There are many statistical tests which are sensitive to outliers. According to Pallant (2016, p. 64), outliers are ‘cases with values well above or well below the majority of other cases’.

Not all outliers are errors. Some outliers can also be genuine scores or responses given by respondents. It is crucial to decide how such outliers should be handled. They can either be (a) removed if they are errors, (b) transformed to less extreme values, or (c) used if they are not distorting the results (Pallant, 2016).

Outliers were detected using a box plot (see Figure 4.1), and no extreme outliers were observed.

Figure 4.1 Boxplot for all the Variables (Author)

Additionally, information in the descriptive statistics regarding the mean and the trimmed mean can help determine whether outliers cause concern. If the trimmed mean differs notably from the mean, this suggests that the dataset may contain outliers or be heavily skewed, necessitating a more in-depth analysis (Wilcox, 2012). While there is no universal threshold for how different these values should be to warrant further investigation, a significant discrepancy often prompts further examination. According to Wilcox (2012), if the difference between the mean and the trimmed mean is more than 5%, the data warrants further investigation for potential outliers. In the table below, the mean and trimmed mean values are not too different from each other, and the difference between them is less than 5%, which indicates that the dataset does not need to be investigated further (Wilcox, 2012; Pallant, 2016). Hence, the outliers were considered genuine responses of the female entrepreneurs and were retained for further analysis.

Table 4.3 Means and Trimmed Means

Variables	Mean	Trimmed Mean
Family Support	1.56	1.52
Social Support	1.99	1.96
Business Knowledge	1.42	1.35
Risk-Taking Behaviour	2.54	2.50
Gender Stereotypes	2.04	2.00
Emotional Intelligence	1.49	1.45
Technological Advancements	1.60	1.56
Government Policies	1.72	1.66
Traditional Challenges	1.68	1.61
Modern Challenges	1.94	1.90

The data has been confirmed to meet the assumptions for multinomial logistic regression through these diagnostic steps, encompassing outlier detection, sample size adequacy, and multicollinearity. This methodical approach ensures that the foundations of the regression model are statistically sound, supporting the validity of the inferences drawn.

4.2.2 Hypothesis testing

Multinomial logistic regression analysis was undertaken using SPSS software to test the hypotheses. This analysis method was employed based on its suitability for characterising the relationship between dependent and independent variables (Schneider *et al.*, 2010). This method is also suitable for predicting a categorical outcome variable with more than two categories. The predictor variables can be continuous, categorical, or both (Pallant, 2016). In this study, the dependent variable (Years in Business) is a proxy used to measure the success of female entrepreneurs. This outcome variable (Years in Business) is a categorical variable with six categories in the survey questionnaire. Of these, the first category, which was Not in Business, was removed as the study is focused on females who are in business. The remaining five categories were reduced to two by recoding the variable into a new variable

for the outcome variable (years in business). Even after reducing the categories to two, multinomial logistic regression was employed as it helps to understand the influence of predictors across both categories, providing more insight into which predictor is important for which category. The complexity of the data warranted a multinomial approach to capture nuances that a binary model might miss. Categorising years in business into ‘less than 5 years’ and ‘more than 5 years’ highlights significant differences in challenges, growth trajectories, and survival rates between early-stage and established businesses. The first few years are critical for survival and growth, with businesses facing higher risks and unique challenges during this period (Aldrich and Auster, 1986; Headd and Kirchhoff, 2009). Female entrepreneurs in particular encounter distinct barriers, such as limited access to capital and networks, which can differ markedly between early-stage and more established businesses (Brush *et al.*, 2009; Robb and Watson, 2012). Firms surviving beyond five years typically exhibit more stability and better access to resources (Coad *et al.*, 2013), suggesting a significant threshold for business development and sustainability (Carter *et al.*, 2003). These distinctions support the relevance of this categorisation for studying female entrepreneurial success in India.

The two categories for the outcome variable are

1. Less than 5 years
2. More than 5 years

Out of the 11 predictors specified in Part A, one variable (Impact of COVID-19) was removed from further analysis because reliability was not met. Hence, there are 10 predictors and one outcome variable, Years in Business, for the analysis. The 10 predictors were divided into three factors: perceptions of personal factors, perceptions of environmental factors, and perceptions of challenges. Perceptions of personal factors include variables such as

perceptions of business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence.

Perceptions of environmental factors include variables such as perceptions of family support, social support, gender stereotypes, technological advancements, and government policies.

Perceptions of challenges include perceptions of traditional and modern challenges. Three tests were conducted for these variables using multinomial logistic regression. The following three tests were conducted for these variables using three different models.

Model 1: Multinomial logistic regression for perceptions of personal factors

Model 2: Multinomial logistic regression for perceptions of environmental factors

Model 3: Multinomial logistic regression for perceptions of challenges

Model 1 – Perceptions of Personal Factors

Multinomial logistic regression for perceptions of personal factors (Business Knowledge (BK), Risk-Taking Behaviour (RB), and Emotional Intelligence (EI))

The hypotheses formulated for this model are as follows.

Research hypotheses for perceptions of personal factors:

H1: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of personal factors (BK, RB, and EI) significantly predict years in business.

H1a: Perceptions of business knowledge (BK) significantly predict years in business.

H1b: Perceptions of risk-taking behaviour (RB) significantly predict years in business.

H1c: Perceptions of emotional intelligence (EI) significantly predict years in business.

Model 1 Results:

Multinomial logistic regression was performed to assess the impact of perceptions of personal factors on the outcome variable (years in business). Model 1 contained three predictors, namely perceptions of business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence, and one outcome variable (Years in Business).

The likelihood ratio tests for Model 1 in Appendix A: Table 4.1 shows a Chi-squared value of 32.620, a significant p-value less than .001, and 3 degrees of freedom, indicating that the predictors in the analysis have a statistically significant relationship with the outcome variable. This model significantly improves fit over the model with no predictors.

The goodness of fit tests suggest that Model 1 in Appendix A: Table 4.2 is an overall fit. The Pearson p-value is .291, and the deviance test p-value is .235. Both these values are greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), indicating the statistical significance of the overall model.

Pseudo R-Square tests in Appendix A: Table 4.3 for Model 1 indicate the explanatory power of the multinomial logistic regression for the perceptions of personal factors and explain the variance in the outcome variable. The Cox and Snell score (R-Squared = .107) indicates that Model 1 explains approximately 10.7% of the variance in the outcome variable (Years in Business) and the explanatory power of Model 1. The Nagelkerke score (R-Squared = .161) indicates higher explanatory power at 16.1%. Lastly, the McFadden score (R-Squared = .103) indicates an explanatory power of 10.3%. Model 1 thus explains between 10.3% and 16.1% of the variance in the outcome variable based on perceptions of personal factors, suggesting that the model is informative and explains a small but significant portion of the variance in the outcome variable.

An interpretation of the key statistics in parameter estimates Appendix A: Table 4.4 and Table 4.5 are as follows.

Perceptions of all three personal factors are statistically significant as the p-value is less than 0.05.

Business Knowledge (B = 1.372, p < .001): Perceptions of business knowledge significantly predict businesses for more than five years (Exp[B] = 3.942) as compared to the likelihood of predicting businesses less than five years (Exp[B] = 0.254).

Risk-taking Behaviour (B = 0.682, p < .001): Perceptions of risk-taking behaviour significantly predict businesses for more than five years (Exp[B] = 1.978) as compared to the likelihood of predicting businesses less than five years (Exp[B] = 0.505).

Emotional Intelligence (B = 0.941, p = .014): Perceptions of emotional intelligence significantly predict the early-stage businesses in the initial five years (Exp[B] = 2.563) compared to the likelihood of predicting businesses more than five years (Exp[B] = .390).

Figure 4.2 Model 1 Results of Personal Factors (Author)

Model 1 Summary:

Multinomial logistic regression analysis examined Indian female entrepreneurs’ perceptions of personal factors such as business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence in terms of their impact on entrepreneurial success, as measured by how many

years they have been in business. All three predictors perceptions of business knowledge (BK), risk-taking behaviour (RB), and emotional intelligence (EI) significantly improved the model's fit compared to models without these variables. These results suggest that all three variables are important for Model 1 and should be retained to predict the outcome variable. Model 1 indicates that perceptions of business knowledge and risk-taking behaviour significantly predict businesses exceeding five years. Perceptions of emotional intelligence significantly predict early-stage businesses in their initial five years. These results imply that when considering interventions or policies aimed at female entrepreneurial success, perceptions of personal factors such as business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence should be considered as they have been statistically validated as important predictors of longevity in business.

Model 2 – Perceptions of Environmental Factors

Multinomial logistic regression for perceptions of environmental factors, such as family support (FS), social support (SS), gender stereotypes (GS), technological advancements (TA), and government policies (GP).

The hypotheses formulated for this model are as follows.

Research hypotheses for perceptions of Environmental Factors (FS, SS, GS, TA, and GP):

H2: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of environmental factors (FS, SS, GS, TA, and GP) significantly predict years in business.

H2a: Perceptions of family support (FS) significantly predict years in business.

H2b: Perceptions of social support (SS) significantly predict years in business.

H2c: Perceptions of gender stereotypes (SS) significantly predict years in business.

H2d: Perceptions of technological advancements (TA) significantly predict years in business.

Model 2 Results:

Multinomial logistic regression was performed to assess the impact of perceptions of environmental factors on the outcome variable (years in business). Model 2 contains five predictors of perceptions of family support (FS), social support (SS), gender stereotypes (GS), technological advancements (TA), and government policies (GP), as well as one outcome variable (years in business).

Based on Appendix A: Table 4.1 of likelihood ratio tests for Model 2, a Chi-squared value of 26.445, a significant p-value less than .001, and 5 degrees of freedom indicate that the predictors in the analysis have a statistically significant relationship with the outcome variable (years in business). Model 2, therefore, significantly improves the fit of the model compared to the model with no predictors.

The goodness of fit tests in Appendix A: Table 4.2 suggests Model 2's overall fit. The Pearson p-value is .324, and the deviance test p-value is .300. Both values are greater than 0.05, indicating the statistical significance of the overall model.

Appendix A: Table 4.3 of Pseudo R-square indicates that Model 2 explains the explanatory power of the logistic regression model. The Cox and Snell score (R-Square value = .092) indicates that the model explains approximately 9.2% of the variance in the outcome variable. The Nagelkerke score (R-Square = .139) indicates higher explanatory power at 13.9%. Lastly, the McFadden score (R-Square = .088) indicates an explanatory power of 8.8%. Model 2 explains a small but significant portion of the variance in the outcome variable (ranging from 8.8% to 13.9%).

Appendix A: Tables 4.4 and 4.5 of parameter estimates for Model 2 in the appendices indicate the following.

Family Support ($B = .998$, $p = .014$) increases the likelihood of predicting early-stage businesses ($\text{Exp}[B] = 2.712$) as compared to businesses over five years. It is a statistically significant predictor.

Social Support ($B = 0.211$, $p = .459$) is not a statistically significant predictor as the p-value is more than .05, implying that social support does not have a significant effect on the odds of longevity in business for Model 2. However, despite being insignificant, it predicts early-stage businesses ($\text{Exp}[B] = 1.235$) compared to businesses over five years.

Gender Stereotypes ($B = 0.412$, $p = .144$) is not a statistically significant predictor as the p-value is more than .05, implying that social support does not have a significant effect on the odds of longevity in business for Model 2. Although it is not a significant predictor, it predicts businesses over five years ($\text{Exp}[B] = 1.510$) compared to the early-stage businesses.

Technological Advancement ($B = 0.424, p = .227$) is not a statistically significant predictor as the p-value is more than .05, implying that social support does not have a significant effect on the odds of longevity in business for Model 2. Despite being insignificant, it predicts early-stage businesses ($\text{Exp}[B] = 1.527$) compared to businesses over five years.

Government policies ($B = 1.265, p < .001$) is statistically significant as a predictor.

Perceptions of government policies significantly predict businesses for more than five years ($\text{Exp}[B] = 3.544$) compared to the likelihood of predicting businesses for less than five years ($\text{Exp}[B] = .282$).

Figure 4.3 Model 2 Results of Environmental Factors (Author)

Model 2 Summary

Multinomial regression analysis findings indicate that perceptions of both family support and government policies significantly predict the outcome variable (Years in business). Of the five predictors, only two, namely perceptions of family support (Chi-squared = 6.362, $p = .012$) and perceptions of government policies (Chi-squared = 14.400, $p < .001$), significantly improve model fit. Perceptions of family support significantly predict early-stage businesses

(Initial five years). Perceptions of government policies significantly predict businesses exceeding five years of operation. These results suggest that these two variables are important for Model 2 and should be retained to predict the outcome variable. Other factors, such as perceptions of social support, gender stereotypes, and technological advancements, did not yield a statistically significant impact in predicting business duration. These results imply that when considering interventions or policies to study female entrepreneurial success, perceptions of environmental factors such as family support and government policies should be considered as they have been statistically validated as important predictors. These findings provide useful insights in guiding interventions to support the growth and success of female entrepreneurs in India, highlighting the importance of family support in the early stages of business and the role of government policies in long-term business survival.

Model 3 – Perceptions of Challenges

Multinomial logistic regression for perceptions of challenges, such as traditional challenges (TC) and modern challenges (MC).

The hypotheses formulated for Model 3 are as follows.

Research hypotheses for perceptions of Challenges (TC and MC):

H3: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of challenges (TC and MC) significantly predict years in business.

H3a: Perceptions of traditional challenges (TC) significantly predict years in business.

H3b: Perceptions of modern challenges (MC) significantly predict years in business.

Model 3 Results:

Multinomial logistic regression was performed to assess the impact of challenges on the outcome variable (years in business). Model 3 contains two predictors, perceptions of traditional challenges and perceptions of modern challenges, as well as one outcome variable (years in business).

From Appendix A: Table 4.1 of likelihood ratio tests for Model 3 in the appendices, a Chi-squared value of 19.671, a significant p-value less than .001, and 2 degrees of freedom indicate that the predictors in the analysis have a statistically significant relationship with the outcome variable.

The goodness of the fit tests in Appendix A: Table 4.2 suggests Model 3's overall fit. The Pearson p-value is .160, indicating the statistical significance of the overall model, and the deviance test p-value is .015, indicating the model's insignificance. Both values are different. However, the Pearson value supports the likelihood ratio test, and hence the model can be treated as statistically significant.

Appendix A: Table 4.3 of Pseudo R-square indicates that the Cox and Snell score (R-squared value = .065) explains approximately 6.5% of the variance in the outcome variable. The Nagelkerke score (R-squared = .099) indicates higher explanatory power at 9.9%. Lastly, the McFadden score (R-squared = .063) indicates an explanatory power of 6.3%. Model 3 explains a small but significant portion of the variance in the outcome variable, with pseudo-R-squared values indicating explanatory power between 6.3% and 9.9%.

Traditional challenges (Chi-squared = 4.147, $p = .042$) and modern challenges (Chi-squared = 7.378, $p = .007$) significantly improve the model's fit. These results suggest that these two variables are important for Model 3 and should be retained to predict the outcome variable (years in business).

Appendix A: Tables 4.4 and 4.5 of parameter estimates for Model 3 in the appendices indicate the following.

Traditional Challenges ($B = 0.484, p = .040$): Perceptions of traditional challenges significantly predict businesses exceeding five years ($\text{Exp}[B] = 1.623$) as compared to the likelihood of predicting businesses less than five years ($\text{Exp}[B] = .616$).

Modern Challenges ($B = 0.687, p = .008$): Perceptions of modern challenges significantly predict businesses exceeding five years ($\text{Exp}[B] = 1.198$) as compared to the likelihood of predicting businesses less than five years ($\text{Exp}[B] = .503$).

Figure 4.4 Model 3 Results of Challenges (Author)

Model 3 Summary

Multinomial logistic regression analysis findings indicate that perceptions of both traditional and modern challenges significantly predict years in business. Both predictors significantly improve model fit. Perceptions of traditional and modern challenges significantly predict businesses exceeding five years of operation. These results suggest that these two variables are important for Model 3 and should be retained to predict years in business. These results imply that when considering interventions or policies to study female entrepreneurial success,

perceptions of traditional and modern challenges should be considered as they have been statistically validated as important predictors. The findings provide useful insights in guiding interventions aimed at supporting the growth and success of female entrepreneurs in India, highlighting the potential impact of the perceptions of these challenges in predicting longevity in the business.

The summary of the hypothesis tests undertaken is outlined in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4 Hypothesis Tests Summary

Model 1		
H1: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of personal factors (BK, RB, and EI) significantly predict years in business.		
Personal Factors	Result	Final result
H1a: Perceptions of business knowledge (BK) significantly predict years in business.	P < 0.05	Accept
H1b: Perceptions of risk-taking behaviour (RB) significantly predict years in business.	p < 0.05	Accept
H1c: Perceptions of emotional intelligence (EI) significantly predict years in business.	P < 0.05	Accept
Model 2		
H2: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of environmental factors (FS, SS, GS, TA, and GP) significantly predict years in business.		
Environmental Factors	Result	Final Result
H2a: Perceptions of family support (FS) significantly predict years in business.	P < 0.05	Accept
H2b: Perceptions of social support (SS) significantly predict years in business.	p > 0.05	Reject
H2c: Perceptions of gender stereotypes (GS) significantly predict years in business.	P > 0.05	Reject
H2d: Perceptions of technological advancements (TA) significantly predict years in business.	p > 0.05	Reject
H2e: Perceptions of government policies (GP) significantly predict years in business.	p < 0.05	Accept
Model 3		
H3: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of challenges (TC and MC) significantly predict years in business.		

Challenges	Result	Final Result
H3a: Perceptions of traditional challenges (TC) significantly predict years in business.	$p < 0.05$	Accept
H3b: Perceptions of modern challenges (MC) significantly predict years in business.	$P < 0.05$	Accept

4.3 Chapter Summary

In Part A of this chapter, data were prepared by cleaning and addressing the missing data, and the reliability of the data was checked using both Cronbach's alpha and inter-item correlation.

In Part B, the important assumptions for multinomial regression, such as sample size, multicollinearity, and outliers, were first verified; then, the hypotheses regarding the perceptions of personal factors were tested in Model 1, the perceptions of environmental factors in Model 2, and perceptions of challenges were tested in Model 3.

All the hypotheses for Model 1(Personal Factors) and Model 3 (Challenges) were accepted, while for Model 2 (Environmental Factors), only two of the five hypotheses, family support and government policies, were significant.

Chapter 5 Discussion

5.1 Introduction

This thesis examines the perceptions of female entrepreneurs, investigating how personal and environmental factors and challenges shape their longevity in business. By quantifying these impacts through the lens of years in business, this research has taken a quantitative approach to the investigation. This approach sheds light on how perceptions of specific personal and environmental factors influence female entrepreneurial success, offering valuable insights into this complex field.

Perceptions of personal factors, including business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence, are pivotal to female entrepreneurial success (Basit *et al.*, 2020). For female entrepreneurs, these factors may uniquely intersect with traditional and modern challenges, potentially altering their impact on female entrepreneurial success. Perceptions of environmental factors such as family support, social support, gender stereotypes, technological advancements, and government policies play critical roles (Basit *et al.*, 2020). These elements do not operate individually; rather, they form a complex ecosystem that can either bolster or hinder the entrepreneurial journey.

The investigation in this study was guided by a literature review, which underscored a significant gap in understanding the specific challenges faced by female entrepreneurs in India, with its rapidly changing economic landscape, deeply ingrained patriarchal and societal norms, and limited access to entrepreneurial training and education that disadvantages females and positions them behind men (Dixit *et al.*, 2022).

Although previous studies have recognised obstacles to female's advancement as entrepreneurs, such as the absence of familial support and gender prejudices, there remains a necessity for thorough investigation in this area (Goyal *et al.*, 2022). Literature on female

entrepreneurs highlights a crucial need to investigate how various factors, such as social, economic, environmental, and psychological barriers that restrict females' involvement in business, are responsible for such outcomes and to propose corrective measures (Rajamani, 2022). Studying female entrepreneurs' perceptions regarding the factors influencing their success is important for understanding barriers and challenges, policy development, resource allocation, and female empowerment. By studying females' perceptions, researchers and policymakers can better identify these challenges and develop targeted interventions to address them (Brush *et al.*, 2009). Insight into the specific needs and experiences of female entrepreneurs can inform the creation of more effective policies and support programmes. These programmes can promote gender equality in the business landscape by developing a more inclusive entrepreneurial environment (Kelley *et al.*, 2017). Identification of the most influential perceived factors by female entrepreneurs can also help in the efficient allocation of resources. For instance, if access to finance is seen as a major hurdle, efforts can be directed toward improving financial services and support for female-owned businesses (Robb and Coleman, 2009).

Hence, understanding these perceptions contributes to female empowerment by highlighting successful strategies and role models. It can inspire potential female entrepreneurs by illuminating how others have navigated and overcome challenges (Minniti and Naudé, 2010). This study therefore focuses on females' perceptions of specific elements influencing their success within the Indian context, providing insights that are relevant locally as well as within the realm of developing nations.

This discussion chapter aims to contribute to understanding the perceptions of factors and challenges specific to female entrepreneurs in India by contextualising the findings within the broader literature and reflecting on their implications. This exploration is relevant not only for academics and policymakers but also for practitioners and entrepreneurs themselves,

particularly female entrepreneurs, who may find the insights helpful in navigating their entrepreneurial paths. Through this dual approach, the discussion aims to provide a multifaceted view of the landscape of female entrepreneurship in India, paving the way for action that more effectively addresses the identified barriers and challenges.

5.2 Research hypotheses and results

This study tested three main hypotheses as well as their sub-hypotheses using data collected from questionnaire respondents.

H1: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of personal factors such as business knowledge (BK), risk-taking (RB), and emotional intelligence (EI) significantly predict years in business (YIB).

Perceptions of all three personal factors, business knowledge (BK), risk-taking behaviour (RB), and emotional intelligence (EI), are important and significantly predict the years in business of female entrepreneurs in India. Hypotheses (H1) and all the sub-hypotheses (H1a, H1b and H1c) for the perceptions of personal factors are accepted and statistically significant. The findings reveal a complex interplay between perceptions of personal factors and longevity in the business of Indian female entrepreneurs. The following section discusses the findings for each factor in relation to the hypothesis and literature.

H1a: Perceptions of business knowledge (BK) significantly predict years in business.

This hypothesis has been accepted. Perceptions of business knowledge (BK) significantly predict years in business (YIB) beyond five years. In fact, perceptions of business knowledge have emerged as the most influential factor predicting female entrepreneurial success, as measured through years in business. Hence, perceptions of business knowledge are crucial to sustaining business operations over time. This finding coincides with Rastogi, Baral, and

Banu (2022) and Arafat *et al.* (2020). Business knowledge is universally acknowledged and empirically supported as crucial for the initial and sustained phases of entrepreneurship.

Arafat *et al.* (2020) determined that female entrepreneurs' perceived capabilities influenced their decision to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Additionally, Rastogi, Baral, and Banu (2022) discovered that female entrepreneurs in India were successful when they had family support and access to advanced skills and abilities. The perceived capabilities of female entrepreneurs increase with relevant business knowledge, which will in turn increase their involvement in entrepreneurial activities and provide them access to advanced skills and abilities. Eventually, access to advanced skills and abilities will make them successful and sustain their business over time.

H1b: Perceptions of risk-taking behaviour (RB) significantly predict years in business.

This hypothesis is accepted. The study findings show that perceptions of risk-taking behaviour (RB) significantly predict years in business (YIB) beyond five years. This discussion critically evaluates whether the literature supports this hypothesis. Basit *et al.* (2020) asserted that female entrepreneurs tend to be more risk-averse, and this behaviour can directly influence their entrepreneurial success. Gautam and Khurana (2018) supported this view, reporting that female entrepreneurs are generally more risk-averse compared to their male counterparts. This substantial gender difference in approaching business risks implies that female entrepreneurs' perceptions of risk-taking significantly impact their business decisions and, consequently, their longevity in business.

According to Baassiri (2018), females tend to react more emotionally to uncertainties, which inhibits their risk-taking behaviour. This emotional inhibition can adversely affect their evaluation and decision-making processes in business. Gehlot *et al.* (2022) supported Baassiri's (2018) findings, positing that many Indian female entrepreneurs have a lower

capacity to bear risks, leading to less business success. Female's perceptions of risk and their emotional reactions to it can result in more conservative decision-making, potentially limiting their businesses' longevity.

Female entrepreneurs' risk-averse behaviour may be associated with lower levels of self-confidence (Basit *et al.*, 2020). This reduced confidence may shape how female entrepreneurs perceive risks and their willingness to engage in competitive business activities (Batoool and Ullah, 2017; Boermans and Willebrands, 2017). Batoool and Ullah (2017) elaborated that these perceptions impact female entrepreneurs' competitiveness. Eib and Siegert (2019) demonstrated that females often perceive risk as a threat and avoid taking on challenges, which can hinder their business growth and sustainability. Hence, perceptions of risk-taking behaviour, influenced by confidence, significantly impact the success and longevity of female-owned businesses.

Gaur, Vijay, and Ravi (2018) found a negative connection between high-risk propensity behaviour and business profits, indicating that excessive risk-taking might be detrimental. Conversely, Basit *et al.* (2020) argued that there is a positive connection between high-risk perception and business profits, suggesting that perceiving risks positively and taking calculated risks can lead to better outcomes. These contradictory findings indicate that the impact of perceptions of risk-taking behaviour on business success and longevity may depend on various factors, such as the individual entrepreneur's ability to manage risk and the specific business context.

The arguments by different scholars (Batoool and Ullah, 2017; Boermans and Willebrands, 2017; Baassiri, 2018; Gautam and Khurana, 2018; Eib and Siegert, 2019; Basit *et al.*, 2020; Gehlot *et al.*, 2022) as discussed above on Hypothesis H1b suggest that while risk aversion can protect female entrepreneurs from potential losses, it can limit their opportunities for

significant growth and long-term sustainability. Encouraging female entrepreneurs to develop a more balanced perception of risk-taking could enhance their business success and longevity. Targeted interventions to boost confidence and provide support in risk management could help female entrepreneurs perceive risk-taking more positively, thereby improving their business outcomes.

In conclusion, the literature (Batool and Ullah, 2017; Boermans and Willebrands, 2017; Eib and Siegert, 2019; Basit *et al.*, 2020) supports the hypothesis that perceptions of risk-taking behaviour among female entrepreneurs significantly predict years in business. Female entrepreneurs' perceptions of risk-taking—influenced by emotional reactions, confidence levels, and competitiveness—play a critical role in determining their business longevity. Encouraging a balanced approach to risk-taking and improving confidence in managing risks could enhance the sustainability and success of female-owned businesses.

H1c: Perceptions of emotional intelligence (EI) significantly predict years in business (YIB).

The study findings highlight that perceptions of emotional intelligence (EI) significantly predict the years in business (YIB) of early-stage businesses (less than 5 years). This discussion critically evaluates whether existing literature supports this hypothesis, with a focus on how perceptions of EI influence female entrepreneurial success and business longevity. Emotional intelligence (EI) is often cited as a critical factor for entrepreneurial success. Female entrepreneurs tend to be less optimistic and self-confident, which can negatively impact their entrepreneurial abilities (Gautam and Khurana, 2018). Indeed, Hossain and Rahman (2018) indicated that lower levels of EI, characterised by less optimism and self-confidence, can impede female entrepreneurs' success; this is particularly relevant in the early stages of business, when challenges are frequent and require strong emotional

resilience. Female entrepreneurs often exhibit a high fear of failure and lack self-confidence, further exacerbating the challenges faced in the early years of business (Abu-Saifan, 2012; Kaur and Sharma, 2019). Alison (2017) further noted that a higher fear of failure is associated with reduced performance in business activities, suggesting that low EI can negatively impact business success. Franzke *et al.* (2022) reinforced this view, attributing the lack of self-confidence among female entrepreneurs to societal gender norms, which can lead to high failure rates in entrepreneurship.

However, Kabote (2018) provides a contrasting view, arguing that there are no direct performance measurements associated with levels of EI, particularly for female entrepreneurs. Thus, further research is needed to establish a clearer link between EI and entrepreneurial success. Nevertheless, many studies suggest a significant relationship between EI and business longevity, especially in the critical early years. Gautam and Khurana (2018) emphasised that EI improves entrepreneurial self-efficacy, which is crucial for business success. Their study suggests that the ability to effectively regulate and utilise emotions is essential for female entrepreneurs. Kaur and Sharma (2019) also argued that EI has a strong impact on entrepreneurs' innovativeness, which is vital for sustaining and growing a business. These findings support the hypothesis that perceptions of EI can predict years in business, as higher EI can lead to better self-management and innovative capabilities. Emotional intelligence makes entrepreneurs more competitive, particularly in business negotiations (Chaudhary, 2015). EI helps entrepreneurs develop leadership skills and improve customer relations, both of which are crucial for early-stage business success (Gautam and Khurana, 2018). Females who achieve self-realisation through EI are more satisfied with their ventures, enhancing overall business success (Gódány and Mura, 2021).

The hypothesis that perceptions of EI significantly predict years in business (YIB), particularly for early-stage businesses, is largely supported by the literature. The studies

reviewed indicate that higher levels of EI, characterised by optimism, self-confidence, and effective emotional regulation, are associated with better business performance and longevity. However, the presence of contradictory findings suggests that further research is needed to solidify the relationship between EI and entrepreneurial success.

All the above hypotheses for the perceptions of personal factors were accepted.

H2: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of environmental factors such as family support (FS), social support (SS), gender stereotypes (GS), technological advancements (TA), and government policies (GP) significantly predict years in business.

Perceptions of only two environmental factors, family support (FS) and government policies (GP), out of the five are statistically important and significantly predict the duration female entrepreneurs in India stay in business. Thus, two sub hypotheses (H2a and H2e) for the perceptions of environmental factors are accepted, while the other hypotheses (H2, H2b, H2c, and H2d) are rejected.

H2a: Perceptions of family support (FS) significantly predict years in business (YIB).

Empirical evidence supports the hypothesis that perceptions of family support (FS) significantly predict years in business (YIB) of early-stage (less than five years) female-owned businesses. Studies have indicated that females who perceive strong family support are more likely to overcome entrepreneurial challenges and sustain their businesses over time. This support mitigates the adverse effects of family-work conflicts, enabling females to focus more on their entrepreneurial endeavours. For example, Charulakshmi and Thaiyalnayaki (2019) and Chhabra, Singh, and Mehdi (2022) both concluded that family support enhances the likelihood of entrepreneurial success. This support provides a buffer against the demands of household chores and childcare, allowing females to dedicate more time and energy to their businesses. Consequently, females who receive robust family support

are more likely to have longer business tenures, supporting the hypothesis that perceptions of family support significantly predict years in business.

The perception of family support is as important as the actual support received. Female entrepreneurs who perceive their families as supportive are more likely to experience positive psychological outcomes, such as reduced stress and increased motivation, further contributing to business longevity (Werbel and Danes, 2010). Studies have identified a positive correlation between perceived family support and business success among female entrepreneurs. For example, Powell and Eddleston (2008) found that females who perceived higher family support reported better business performance and greater satisfaction with their entrepreneurial endeavours.

Research has provided empirical evidence supporting the hypothesis that perceptions of family support significantly predict years in business. In a study of female entrepreneurs in developing countries, familial support was a significant predictor of business survival and growth (Bruni, Gherardi, and Poggio, 2004). Similarly, a study conducted by Madichie and Nkamnebe (2010) in Nigeria revealed that family support played a critical role in the success and longevity of female-owned businesses. Therefore, the literature reveals that perceptions of family support play a crucial role. Consistent findings across various studies underscore the significant impact of both perceived and actual family support on female's entrepreneurial longevity and success. Family support not only alleviates the pressures of balancing family and business responsibilities but also enhances female's confidence and access to necessary resources, ultimately contributing to the sustained success and longevity of their businesses.

The findings for this hypothesis build on existing literature by highlighting the role of family support in the entrepreneurial success of early-stage female business entrepreneurs, mainly through its influence on longevity in business. While prior studies have shown that family

support can help mitigate work-family conflicts and improve business outcomes, this research draws attention to the importance of the perceptions, indicating that perceptions of family support can influence the experiences and outcomes of female entrepreneurs. The findings contribute to the literature by shedding light on the stage-specific importance of family support, particularly the role of perceived family support during the early stage (initial five years) of business. While prior studies have emphasised the general benefits of family support for female entrepreneurs, they have not explored how its relevance may vary across different business stages. This study examines the influence of the perceptions of family support on two distinct stages (initial five years and more than five years) of female entrepreneurs' longevity in business. The findings add to the extant literature that perceptions of family support predict female entrepreneurs' early-stage longevity in business.

H2e: Perceptions of government policies (GP) significantly predict years in business (YIB).

This hypothesis is accepted, and the findings from both the empirical analysis and the literature review shed light on the complex landscape of government support for female entrepreneurship in India. Despite the employment of laws and programmes by the Indian government aiming to promote female entrepreneurship (Saranya and Chandrasekar, 2023), the challenges females face persist. Gender-based obstacles in accessing markets, financing, social capital, and state resources remain prevalent, underscoring the need for deeper gender sensitisation and equal access to technology and the internet (Kumar and Singh, 2021b).

Moreover, the literature emphasises the importance of continuous efforts to develop policies that not only encourage females to pursue entrepreneurship but also address the multifaceted barriers they encounter (Abrar ul Haq, Victor, and Akram, 2020). According to Amrita *et al.* (2022), individual, familial, infrastructure, and policy and legal barriers are critical

constraints, with government support and motivation for marginalised groups emerging as influential strategies. However, societal norms and a male-dominated sociological setup pose additional challenges, necessitating dialogue between policymakers and stakeholders to foster innovation and support networks for female-owned enterprises (Tyagi, Sharma and Jain, 2021). Despite the introduction of policies such as the National Skill Development Policy and Mission, challenges persist, indicating the need for stakeholder involvement beyond government efforts (Kaviarasu, Ruban and Francis, 2018).

In summary, while government support through policies and programmes plays a vital role in facilitating female entrepreneurial success in India, persistent challenges necessitate a multifaceted and inclusive approach to policy formulation and implementation. Gender-sensitive policies, stakeholder engagement, and targeted interventions are essential to creating an enabling environment where female entrepreneurs can thrive, contribute to economic development, and overcome systemic barriers to their success.

The finding that perceptions of government policies (GP) significantly predict years in business (YIB) for female-owned businesses beyond five years adds to the extant literature on female entrepreneurship in India by suggesting the potential long-term benefits of supportive government policy perceptions. While previous studies have highlighted the importance of government initiatives in promoting female entrepreneurship, they do not sufficiently highlight the stage-specific influence of such perceptions on longevity in business. This research underscores the role of perceived government support in terms of policies in predicting longevity in businesses over five years, emphasising that the effectiveness of policies extends beyond their existence to how female entrepreneurs perceive them. The findings indicate the need for continuous and adaptive policy measures that consider the perspectives of female entrepreneurs, helping to ensure that government support is provided at the stage in business when it may actually be required by female entrepreneurs

in India. By addressing these concerns and enhancing support mechanisms, policymakers can create a more conducive environment for female entrepreneurship and economic empowerment. However, further research may be needed to better understand the underlying factors driving these associations and to inform more targeted policy interventions.

H3: Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions of challenges (TC and MC) significantly predict years in business (YIB).

H3a: Perceptions of traditional challenges (TC) significantly predict years in business (YIB).

This hypothesis (H3) and the sub hypotheses (H3a and H3b) are significant, and the perceptions of traditional challenges (TC) predicting years in business (YIB) beyond five years for female entrepreneurs reflect their resilience, adaptability, and resourcefulness in overcoming these obstacles. The literature review elucidates the influence of traditional challenges on female entrepreneurship, particularly within the Indian context. In Indian society, females are traditionally confined to domestic roles due to gender discrimination and limited opportunities for education and economic participation (Gautam and Khurana, 2018; Hossain and Rahman, 2018; Kikula, 2018). This is further supported by Panda (2018), Gehlot *et al.* (2022), Komal and Sharma (2023) who underlined the pressure on females to adhere to established gender roles, thereby discouraging their engagement in entrepreneurial activities. Boermans and Willebrands (2017) add that Indian culture often places low value on female's work and entrepreneurship.

Despite the perception of traditional challenges as a barrier, these entrepreneurs have demonstrated the ability to navigate these barriers successfully. Their sustained longevity in business underscores their resilience and persistence in defying societal expectations and gender biases. Moreover, with the experience they have accumulated, these entrepreneurs

likely leverage extensive networks and resources, including mentorship and support networks, to mitigate the impact of traditional challenges. Additionally, their established market presence and reputation may contribute to their capacity to overcome traditional obstacles and sustain business operations. The longer business survival beyond five years may also signify broader societal changes, including advocacy efforts aimed at challenging traditional gender norms and fostering a more supportive environment for females in entrepreneurship. These changes could be due to the efforts of government initiatives and policies, which have been instrumental despite the hindrances to skills training and vocational education due to societal and economic disparities (Gupta and Kaur, 2023). Additionally, the shift could be due to the increasing educational status and aspirations for a better life among Indian females (Singh, Shekhawat, and Singla, 2022).

Collectively, these studies highlight the effect of traditional challenges on the success of female entrepreneurs and reveal the need for efforts to challenge traditional roles and perceptions about female entrepreneurs, foster supportive environments for them, and provide resources and opportunities to facilitate their success in business ventures. Overall, these findings underscore female entrepreneurs' capacity to transcend traditional challenges, leveraging their resilience, adaptation, and community support to achieve long-term success in entrepreneurship.

H3b: Perceptions of modern challenges (MC) significantly predict years in business (YIB).

Perceptions of modern challenges (MC) significantly predict years in business (YIB) for female owned businesses beyond five years. Prior research highlights the adverse effects of challenges such as financial constraints and societal expectations on female's entrepreneurial endeavours (Gaur, Vijay, and Ravi, 2018; Panda, 2018; Eib and Siegert, 2019). Past studies

underscore the formidable barriers that females encounter in navigating the contemporary business environment, including stiff competition and conflicting work-family roles (Chaudhary, 2015; Gaddefors and Anderson, 2017; Giusta, Marina, and Razzu, 2019).

The finding (Perceptions of female entrepreneurs in India regarding modern challenges (MC) significantly predict years in business (YIB) beyond five years) from this study regarding the perceptions of modern challenges aligns with the literature by Gaur, Vijay, and Ravi, 2018; Panda, 2018; Eib and Siegert, 2019, which emphasizes female's capacity to overcome barriers and thrive in entrepreneurship despite adversities. The finding for the perceptions of modern challenges suggests that female entrepreneurs who have longevity in business beyond five years have adapted to modern challenges and successfully navigated them, leading to longer business tenures. This suggests that female entrepreneurs may have developed resilience and adaptive strategies to navigate modern challenges (Chaudhary, 2015; Gaddefors and Anderson, 2017; Giusta, Marina, and Razzu, 2019). This shift in female perspective could be attributed to increasing educational status and aspirations for a better life among Indian females (Singh, Shekhawat, and Singla, 2022).

The findings related to the significant factors and the hypotheses that were supported in influencing female entrepreneurs' longevity in business have been discussed in the previous sections, providing insights into the key elements that influence their success. These discussions highlighted the importance of personal and environmental factors that were supported by the data. In the following paragraph, hypotheses that were not supported will be discussed with an explanation of these findings and their implications for understanding the broader context of female entrepreneurship.

H2b: Perceptions of social support (SS) significantly predict years in business (YIB).

Hypothesis H2b was not supported in this study. The multinomial logistic regression analysis revealed a coefficient $B = 0.211$, odds ratio $\text{Exp}(B)=1.235$, and $p = 0.459$. Although the B value and odds ratio suggest a slight association between perceptions of social support and a greater likelihood of longevity in businesses for less than five years, the high p -value indicates that this relationship is not statistically significant.

One possible explanation for the lack of statistical significance can be the changing role of social support as businesses progress. While social support from family, friends, and entrepreneurial communities boosts self-confidence, self-efficacy, and resilience among female entrepreneurs (Sehgal and Khandelwal, 2020), its impact may diminish as businesses mature, with structural and market-oriented factors becoming important for business sustainability (Harshitha, Chidananda, and Varghese, 2023). This study's findings suggest that social support may be more relevant during the initial five years but less influential on long-term business longevity. Cultural and societal dynamics may also limit its effectiveness, as highlighted by Charulakshmi and Thaiyalnayaki (2019), who emphasised the importance of moral support from friends and family.

Notably, perceptions of family support (FS) were statistically significant in predicting YIB during the first five years in this study, underscoring its significant role in predicting early-stage businesses. Social support may provide indirect benefits like motivation or advice but may overlap with family support, diluting its distinct impact. This overlap might explain why perceptions of family support emerged as significant while perceptions of social support did not. Although perceptions of social support did not significantly predict YIB in this study, the B -value and odds ratio indicate a subtle role, especially for businesses under five years old. Further research is needed to explore how perceptions of social and family support evolve across different stages of YIB and their respective impacts on entrepreneurial longevity.

H2d: Perceptions of technological advancements (TA) significantly predict years in business (YIB).

Hypothesis H2d was not supported in this study. The multinomial logistic regression analysis revealed a coefficient $B = 0.424$, odds ratio $\text{Exp}(B) = 1.527$, and $p = 0.227$. Although the B-value and the odds ratio suggest an association between perceptions of technological advancements and a greater likelihood of predicting longevity in businesses for less than five years compared to the other category (more than five years), the high p-value indicates that this relationship is not statistically significant.

Varying access and technology adoption levels may explain the lack of statistical significance among female entrepreneurs in India (Ughetto *et al.*, 2020). As Kumar and Singh (2021b) highlighted, gender-based obstacles such as unequal access to technology, limited digital literacy, and restricted internet connectivity can undermine the perceived benefits of technological advancements. This variability may reduce the impact of technological advancements perceptions on the outcome. Also, for some businesses, especially those in traditional or low-tech sectors, technology may play a secondary role compared to other factors, such as market access and financial stability (Harshitha, Chidananda, and Varghese, 2023). Female entrepreneurs in such sectors may not perceive technological advancements as critical to their success, leading to an insignificant statistical relationship. Additionally, technological advancements require training and resources to be fully leveraged, and systemic barriers often prevent female entrepreneurs from integrating technology effectively into their operations (Ughetto *et al.*, 2020; Kumar and Singh, 2021b; Tyagi, Sharma, and Jain, 2021). This gap between perceptions of technological advancements and practical application could weaken the predictive power of perceptions of technology on YIB.

H2c: Perceptions of gender stereotypes (GS) significantly predict years in business (YIB).

Hypothesis H2c was not supported in this study. The multinomial logistic regression analysis revealed a coefficient $B = 0.412$, odds ratio $\text{Exp}(B)=1.510$, and $p=0.144$. Although the positive B and odds ratio suggest a potential association between perceptions of gender stereotypes (GS) and longevity in business beyond five years, the high p -value indicates that this relationship is not statistically significant.

Perceptions of gender stereotypes are not fixed; they can evolve over time and may vary depending on the context (Amrutha, Santhi, and Nalini, 2022). For example, as businesses mature, societal perceptions may shift, and the direct impact of gender stereotypes may diminish, making it harder to detect a statistically significant relationship with business longevity. This could explain why the hypothesis was not supported. The perceptions of gender stereotypes may be influenced by other factors, such as education, industry type, or access to social networks (Kaushik, 2013; Alsos and Ljunggren, 2016; Basit *et al.*, 2020). The lack of statistical significance for H2c in this study may reflect the interplay of such variables. For example, the participants in the sampled population may operate in industries traditionally associated with women, such as fashion, beauty, or childcare, where they may not have encountered significant gender-based stereotypes or biases, thereby reducing the variable's predictive power in the context of this study. While the hypothesis was not supported, this does not diminish the broader relevance of gender stereotypes in entrepreneurship. Instead, it suggests that their impact may be indirect or contingent on other factors.

Summary of the study findings

This summary presents the key findings of the study, highlighting the significant predictors of female entrepreneurial success in India, measured using years in business as a proxy. The results indicate that perceptions of personal factors, environmental factors, and traditional and modern challenges as factors all play an important role in determining business longevity of female entrepreneurs in India.

The multinomial logistic regression results show that perceptions of all three personal factors—business knowledge (BK), risk-taking behavior (RB), and emotional intelligence (EI)—significantly predict the years in business (YIB) for female entrepreneurs in India. Perceptions of BK and RB are significant predictors of longevity in business beyond five years, while EI is significant predictor for early-stage businesses (within the first five years).

Among environmental factors, only perceptions of family support (FS) and government policies (GP) significantly predict longevity in business. Perceptions of FS predicts early-stage businesses, while perceptions of GP plays a key role in predicting businesses beyond five years. Perceptions of other environmental factors, such as social support (SS), gender stereotypes (GS), and technological advancements (TA), do not show a significant impact in predicting longevity in business for female entrepreneurs in India. Additionally, perceptions of both traditional (TC) and modern challenges (MC) significantly predict longevity in business beyond five years.

5.3 Theory of planned behaviour and study findings

The TPB provides a useful framework for understanding the study's findings. The TPB posits that an individual's behaviour is driven by their intentions, which are influenced by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. However, this study includes two components of TPB, attitudes and subjective norms, as explained in the literature review

(Section 2.4.1, p. 64). Applying TPB unearths insights into how perceptions of personal and environmental factors, as well as challenges, influence the success of female entrepreneurs.

Perceptions of personal factors

Perceptions of Business Knowledge: Female entrepreneurs with positive attitudes towards acquiring and utilising business knowledge will likely persist and succeed in their entrepreneurial activities (Koellinger, Minniti, and Schade, 2013). This aligns with this study's finding that business knowledge is essential for longevity in business for more than five years.

Perceptions of Risk-Taking Behaviour: Entrepreneurs with a favourable attitude towards risk-taking are crucial for moving beyond the nascent stages of business and sustaining growth. The willingness to take risks is driven by the belief that it will lead to business success (Shinnar, Giacomini, and Janssen, 2012; Basit *et al.*, 2020).

Perceptions of Emotional Intelligence: The emotional intelligence of female entrepreneurs plays a crucial role in their attitudes towards the behaviour (Years in business). Females who believe in their ability to manage emotions and relationships effectively are more likely to persist through initial difficulties (Bandura, 1997). Perceptions of emotional intelligence significantly predict years in business, particularly for early-stage businesses; this is largely supported by Gautam and Khurana (2018), Kaur and Sharma (2019), and Górány and Mura (2021).

Perceptions of environmental factors

Perceptions of Family Support: Social norms and expectations around family support can significantly influence entrepreneurial success. In cultures where family support is valued and female entrepreneurs have a positive attitude towards this support, they may feel more encouraged to start, sustain, and grow businesses (Charulakshmi and Thaiyalnayaki, 2019;

Chhabra, Singh, and Mehdi, 2022). Family support, or lack of family support, can shape attitudes towards female entrepreneurial success. Positive reinforcement from this support and a positive attitude towards it can increase confidence and commitment to business endeavours by providing emotional and financial backing (Shelton, 2006).

Perceptions of Government Support: Favourable attitudes towards supportive government policies can influence long-term business sustainability (Marlow and McAdam, 2013).

Entrepreneurs who believe in these policies are more likely to succeed in their entrepreneurial journeys as perceptions of supportive governmental policies enhance their attitude and influence their entrepreneurial success.

Perceptions of Traditional and Modern Challenges

The subjective norms component of the TPB explains external influences and their normative beliefs on the intentions of female entrepreneurs towards the behaviour (Female entrepreneurial success). Traditional gender roles and perceptions prescribe specific actions and responsibilities for females, often limiting their participation in business (Carter *et al.*, 2007). Negative attitudes and social norms related to these roles can lower entrepreneurial intentions and affect females' success (Brush, 1992). According to the TPB, addressing these roles requires fostering positive attitudes and supportive social norms. Females who challenge traditional gender roles and perceive greater control over their business activities are more likely to succeed. Positive attitudes towards resilience and adaptability can drive entrepreneurs to overcome challenges. Believing in their capacity to adapt and being resourceful helps female entrepreneurs persist (Bandura, 1997). Positive attitudes towards modern challenges can enhance entrepreneurial behaviour, while negative perceptions can create barriers. As the TPB suggests, a positive attitude towards a behaviour increases the likelihood of engaging in that behaviour (Ajzen, 1991).

The TPB can help explain the findings that are not statistically significant using the intention-behaviour gap (Sheeran, 2002).

Regarding social support, female entrepreneurs may have positive attitudes toward receiving this support, but this support might not translate into significant entrepreneurial success.

Similarly, even if females perceive social support as helpful, it may not enhance their business outcomes if it does not address specific business needs, such as professional networks or business skills. This discrepancy arises because the perceived value of social support might not align with its actual utility in business contexts. While social support can influence the intention to pursue entrepreneurship, it may not significantly impact business success if it does not translate into actionable help, such as mentorship or financial assistance (Shinnar, Giacomini, and Janssen, 2012).

Regarding gender stereotypes, female entrepreneurs might recognise and intend to overcome these negative attitudes, but systemic barriers can create an intention-behaviour gap. Societal norms around gender roles might hinder actual behaviour, such as obtaining financing, even if females intend to defy these norms (Jennings and Brush, 2013). Overcoming stereotypes, especially in male-dominated industries, can prevent intentions from translating into successful outcomes (Gupta *et al.*, 2009).

Regarding technological advancements, female entrepreneurs might have positive attitudes toward adopting new technologies, but practical barriers such as a lack of resources or skills can prevent these intentions from becoming actions (Kautonen *et al.*, 2013). Societal expectations that successful entrepreneurs utilise the latest technologies can create pressure, but if females lack access to training or infrastructure, they may struggle to meet these expectations, resulting in an intention-behaviour gap (Henry *et al.*, 2016). Thus, practical barriers and struggles to meet the societal expectations may limit their control over

effectively adopting and integrating technologies and may hinder the realisation of their intentions.

In conclusion, the TPB highlights the complexity of translating intentions into actual behaviour, particularly when external factors create barriers (Ajzen, 1991). The intention-behaviour gap can explain why factors like social support, gender stereotypes, and technological advancements were not statistically significant in the study. Female entrepreneurs may have positive attitudes and strong intentions regarding these factors, but practical limitations, systemic barriers, and limited control can hinder translating these intentions into successful entrepreneurial outcomes (Kautonen *et al.*, 2013). Recognising and addressing these gaps is crucial for developing interventions and policies that effectively support female entrepreneurs, helping to bridge the gap between their intentions and their business achievements (Jennings and Brush, 2013).

5.4 Limitations of the research

This study examined how the perceptions of personal and environmental factors and of traditional and modern challenges predict the success of female entrepreneurs. However, it did not encompass all potential variables; several additional factors, such as political, economic, legal, religious, and technological factors, might also predict female entrepreneurs' success. The primary justification for excluding other pertinent factors was to maintain a clear and manageable scope for the study. Focusing on specific variables, such as perceptions of personal and environmental factors and challenges, allows for a better analysis. Expanding the study to include all possible variables would make it overly broad and dilute the focus, potentially leading to a superficial analysis of each factor. Additionally, research projects often face limitations in terms of time, funding, and resources. Including every potential factor would have required more extensive data collection, longer analysis periods, and

additional resources. Prioritising certain factors ensured that the research would be completed with the available resources.

Although the selected techniques and methodologies were deemed appropriate for the researcher to gather sufficient data and make inferences, methodological limitations exist. The collection of only quantitative data was a limitation, as participants might have falsified their responses, and the researcher had limited control over how the respondents answered the questionnaires. Additionally, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the researcher relied on online platforms to collect primary data, which often have a very low response rate. Despite these challenges and potential limitations, the researcher remained focused on meeting the study objectives.

The study collected data only once and employed a cross-sectional design. However, using this method, it is not possible to derive cause-and-effect relationships between variables or account for changes over time. Longitudinal or experimental designs may provide more robust evidence of causal relationships and temporal dynamics between personal, environmental, and challenge factors and female entrepreneurs' success.

The results and analysis are based on a specific sample of female entrepreneurs recruited online to ensure diversity, but the sample may not fully capture the range of female entrepreneurs from different regions, sectors, industries, and backgrounds, limiting the study's applicability to broader populations. The reason the sample may not fully capture the range of female entrepreneurs is because the researcher collected data using convenience sampling, which, if not properly conducted, could lead to the collection of data from a single area or region and not be a true representation of the target population.

The study's findings may have limited external validity beyond the specific context and sample population studied. India is a vast and populous country, and factors such as cultural

differences, regional variations, and industry-specific dynamics may influence the relevance and applicability of the findings to other contexts. Therefore, caution should be exercised when generalising the results to other contexts.

The study's findings are contingent upon the availability and reliability of the data collected through quantitative research methods. Data limitations, such as missing data or measurement errors, may introduce biases and affect the accuracy of the results. Additionally, the study may not have fully captured the complexity of the variables under investigation as it predicts the success of female entrepreneurs based on only one variable, which is years in business.

While efforts were made to analyse and interpret the data, there may be alternative explanations or unmeasured variables that could influence the observed relationships between perceptions of personal and environmental factors and challenges and female entrepreneurs' success. Interpretation of the findings should be cautious and considerate of these potential confounding factors. For example, there could be an impact of other demographic factors such as respondents' age, educational qualifications, marital status, or other factors.

Addressing these limitations requires future research endeavours employing more comprehensive research methods, integrated models, and advanced statistical tools and research designs to better understand perceptions of the factors influencing female entrepreneurs' success.

5.5 Future research directions

While the quantitative methods used in this study provided valuable insights into the perceptions of factors and challenges influencing the success of female entrepreneurs, incorporating qualitative research or mixed-method research in future studies can offer a deeper, more nuanced understanding of their perceptions. By conducting in-depth interviews with active female entrepreneurs regarding their perceptions of factors and challenges,

contextual influences, hidden barriers, and the impact of policies, qualitative research can uncover insights that quantitative methods alone may miss. These insights can advance discussion on the perceptions of factors influencing female entrepreneurial success. To evaluate the effectiveness of policies and interventions designed to support female entrepreneurs, qualitative research can provide detailed feedback on their implementation and impact. Interviews and focus groups with successful female entrepreneurs can assess how these initiatives are perceived and whether they meet the actual needs of female entrepreneurs.

Future research could aim to develop integrated models that encompass personal, environmental, and other factors, such as social, cultural, political, technological, and legal influences. These models would provide a more comprehensive prediction of the success and longevity of female-led businesses. Incorporating these diverse factors into a unified framework can enhance our understanding of the complex interplay of influences on entrepreneurial success. Demographic factors such as age, education, and marital status can also be used as control variables in future research to examine their impact on the success of female entrepreneurs. By considering these variables, researchers can identify demographic trends and patterns that may influence business outcomes, offering a more nuanced perspective on the factors contributing to entrepreneurial success. In this study, the success of female entrepreneurs is measured using one variable: years in business. Future research could measure success using multiple variables, including financial performance, customer satisfaction, market expansion, and innovation. Employing a broader set of success indicators can provide a more holistic view of entrepreneurial achievement and resilience.

Quantitative studies employing structural equation modelling or other advanced statistical techniques could test the relationships between these perceived factors and years in business, providing a holistic understanding of the drivers of entrepreneurial success. Future studies

can use longitudinal or experimental designs to provide more robust evidence of causal relationships and the temporal dynamics between personal, environmental, and challenge factors and female entrepreneurial success. Longitudinal studies can track changes over time, while different experimental designs can isolate the effects of specific interventions, offering stronger insights into cause-and-effect relationships.

5.6 Chapter summary

In this chapter, the analysis findings were discussed in relation to existing literature, and their implications were thoroughly examined. Furthermore, the research's limitations were noted and potential avenues for future research outlined.

Chapter 6 Conclusion

6.1 Introduction

This study aimed to examine the perceptions of female entrepreneurs in India. A review of the literature identified a limited understanding of female entrepreneurship, with studies focused on a specific sector or region in India and limited use of conceptual frameworks, roadmaps, or recommendations to bolster female entrepreneurs in India. To address these gaps, this study set out to investigate the perceptions of which specific factors predict the success of Indian female entrepreneurs (measured as years in business) and to provide recommendations. This research has presented valuable insights into the perceptions of barriers and challenges faced by female entrepreneurs, as well as the opportunities that exist for fostering their sustained success in the business arena. Through quantitative research methods and positivist philosophy, these study findings seek to inform policies, programmes, and interventions that can support and empower female entrepreneurs, ultimately contributing to more inclusive and sustainable economic growth.

Building upon the foundation laid in the preceding chapters, this conclusion chapter serves as a synthesis of the research findings, implications, and contributions to knowledge and practice. This chapter reflects on the overarching research questions, summarises the main findings, discusses their theoretical and practical implications, and offers recommendations for policymakers aimed at advancing understanding of female entrepreneurship in India.

6.2 Research questions and study findings

The main research objectives sought to understand female entrepreneurs' perceptions of the personal factors, environmental factors, and challenges that influence their longevity in business and success. To achieve these objectives, three research questions were addressed.

The results of the multinomial logistic regression indicated that perceptions of all three specific personal factors, business knowledge (BK), risk-taking behaviour (RB), and emotional intelligence (EI), significantly predict years in business (YIB) for female entrepreneurs. These three predictors have been statistically validated to predict female entrepreneurial success as measured via years in business. Notably, perceptions of business knowledge and risk-taking behaviour significantly predict the longevity of female-owned businesses beyond five years, while perceptions of emotional intelligence significantly predict the longevity of early-stage businesses (initial five years).

Only two of the five perceived environmental factors, family support (FS) and government policies (GP), significantly predict years in business (YIB) for Indian female entrepreneurs. Other factors, such as perceptions of social support, gender stereotypes, and technological advancements, are not statistically significant predictors of female entrepreneurial success. Perceptions of family support and perceptions of government policies were statistically validated to predict female entrepreneurial success measured through years in business as a proxy. Perceptions of family support significantly predict the longevity of early-stage businesses (initial five years), and perceptions of government policies significantly predict the longevity of businesses beyond five years.

Perceptions of traditional (TC) and modern challenges (MC) significantly predict years in business (YIB) for Indian female entrepreneurs. Perceptions of both challenges have been statistically validated as significant predictors of female entrepreneurial success, as measured through years in business as a proxy. These predictors significantly predict the longevity of female-owned businesses beyond five years of their entrepreneurial journey.

6.3 Implications of the findings

Based on the findings from this study, it may be deduced that the perceptions of female entrepreneurs regarding the factors they believe affect their success can be extremely important in identifying the support they may need. Additionally, female entrepreneurs can benefit from support received by the relevant stakeholders according to the stages of their business (less than 5 years – early stage businesses, more than 5 years – established businesses). For the perceptions of personal factors (perceptions of EI, RB and BK), while perceptions of emotional intelligence (EI) can be helpful in the early stages of business—particularly within the first five years—perceptions of business knowledge (BK) and risk-taking behaviour (RB) can be important as the business grows over five years. Regarding perceptions of environmental factors, perceptions of family support may play an important role for early-stage entrepreneurs, and perceptions of favourable government policies may influence female entrepreneurs' long-term longevity in business. Additionally, perceptions of traditional and modern challenges can be helpful for long-term longevity in the business landscape.

6.4 Contribution to Knowledge

The current study advances knowledge on the perceptions of female entrepreneurs regarding the specific factors and challenges influencing the success of female entrepreneurs in India. Many studies have shed light on the challenges and opportunities influencing female entrepreneurial success, but there is scant literature, particularly in India, studying female entrepreneurs' perceptions of these factors and how they influence their success. According to Susiana, Yindrizar, and Ningrum (2022), understanding the perceptions of female entrepreneurs is crucial because it highlights the unique challenges and opportunities they face, such as balancing business with family responsibilities, which can influence their success and motivation in the business world. In addition, it helps identify the specific needs

and strengths of females in business, like their human capital and characteristics, which can inform tailored support and training programmes to enhance their entrepreneurial journey.

There is a lack of conceptual frameworks for this research topic, but this study has taken a step toward remedying this by providing a conceptual framework (Section 2.5.4, Figure 2.4, pg. 78) that synthesises the theory of planned behaviour and conceptualises the complex dynamics of female entrepreneurship in India. By integrating insights from diverse studies on the topic, the proposed conceptual framework (Section 2.5.4, Figure 2.4, pg. 78) offers a substantial understanding of the perceptions of factors and challenges female entrepreneurs face. Drawing upon empirical evidence from a quantitative survey, the framework identifies perceptions of key factors that female entrepreneurs believe influence females' entrepreneurial survival in business. Furthermore, by examining these perceptions and their impact on female entrepreneurial success, the study not only advances knowledge and understanding but also provides actionable insights for policymakers, practitioners, and scholars seeking to foster a more inclusive and supportive entrepreneurial ecosystem for females in India. Overall, this study's conceptual framework (Section 2.5.4, Figure 2.4, pg. 78) serves as a theoretical lens to analyse and address the complexities of female entrepreneurship, their success, and their perceptions of factors and challenges, thereby making a valuable contribution to knowledge.

This study not only introduces the role of perceptions of key factors that can predict years in business for female entrepreneurs in India, but it also explains perceptions of which factors are statistically significant and at which entrepreneurial stage (initial five years or beyond five years) they are important. For instance, the perceptions of female entrepreneurs regarding family support are significant for early-stage (initial five years) female entrepreneurs, but the perceptions of government policies are significant for businesses beyond five years. The study provides valuable insights into significant perceived factors, and

at which stage they are important for female entrepreneurs, which advances knowledge on this topic and can help to provide the right support by indicating when different types of support are needed during the entrepreneurial journey.

6.5 Practical contributions

The findings of this study offer useful insights into factors that may influence the longevity in business of female entrepreneurs in India, contributing to a practical understanding of the perceptions of female entrepreneurs in India. By examining perceptions of personal factors such as business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence, the study suggests the potential significance of these attributes at two stages (less than five years and more than five years). It also brings attention to perceptions of environmental factors, which are external factors like family support and government policies, which influence entrepreneurial longevity at two different stages. These insights can inform the development of interventions to support female entrepreneurs in addressing challenges and pursuing opportunities.

This study's practical contributions and potential benefits are further explored through a discussion focused on specific stakeholders. By categorising the findings according to their relevance to female entrepreneurs, training and development professionals, family and community networks, and government and non-government organisations, the study highlights how its insights can inform tailored interventions and initiatives. Each stakeholder's role in leveraging these findings to support female entrepreneurship is elaborated in the following sections.

Female entrepreneurs

As the study mainly focuses on female entrepreneurs in India and their perceptions, they are the main beneficiaries of the study findings. The research findings shed light on personal

factors, environmental factors, and traditional and modern challenges. Knowledge of the factors that influence female entrepreneurs' longevity in business can help female entrepreneurs to be aware of the potential challenges they may face and strategize or focus on factors that are under their control to improve their longevity in business. For instance, perceptions of all the personal factors, including business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence, are statistically significant according to the study findings. These personal factors are intrinsic to female entrepreneurs and are more under their control than environmental factors. Knowing which factors are important and at which stage may guide them to survive longer in their entrepreneurial journey.

Training and development professionals

This study's findings may contribute to developing and designing targeted training and development programmes for female entrepreneurs in India. The training and development professionals can design targeted programs based on the study's insights. For example, perceptions of business knowledge and risk-taking behaviour significantly predict long-term business success; training programmes can therefore be tailored to enhance these perceptions among female entrepreneurs. Workshops that emphasise the importance of self-perception in business knowledge and risk management can use practical exercises, role-playing, and case studies to help female entrepreneurs see themselves as knowledgeable and capable risk-takers. Mentorship programmes and platforms where successful female entrepreneurs share their stories and hear from peers who have successfully navigated the entrepreneurial journey can positively influence perceptions of personal capability and risk-taking.

Family and Community Support Networks

Family support is significant as per this study's findings, especially for early-stage female entrepreneurs. Females need family support in managing family and household

responsibilities, balancing their work and home life, and taking care of young children. Additionally, they need encouragement and moral support from friends and family and, most importantly, financial support. Family members should understand the importance of sharing responsibilities and encourage female entrepreneurs by being support pillars. Interventions can be designed to improve perceptions of family support by implementing programmes that involve family members and educating them on how their support can impact an entrepreneur's success. This could include family workshops and counselling sessions to foster a supportive home environment. Encouraging supportive family policies at the organisational and governmental levels, such as flexible work arrangements, parental leave policies, and affordable childcare services, can help entrepreneurs better balance their personal and professional responsibilities (Arora and Agarwal, 2019; Aggrawal *et al.*, 2022).

However, cultural shifts in family dynamics are not easy to implement. Resistance to change in traditional family structures can hinder progress. While the idea of family members sharing responsibilities is ideal, it assumes that family dynamics are inherently supportive and equitable, which may not be true in all cultures or households. In many traditional settings, gender roles are still rigid, and the redistribution of family responsibilities can be challenging to implement (Brush, De Bruin, and Welter, 2009). Changing deep-rooted cultural norms is a long-term process that requires sustained effort and commitment from all societal sectors.

Government and non-government organisations

This research can help the Indian government, private and public organisations, policymakers, practitioners, and female-led businesses to get important insights on female entrepreneurship, the role of female entrepreneurs' perceptions of government policies on their longevity in business and develop tailored support programmes. Given the significant impact of perceptions of government policies on long-term business success, targeted

awareness campaigns can be developed to improve awareness and perceptions of government policies. Multiple platforms should be used to inform female entrepreneurs about supportive government policies, grants, and financial incentives. This could involve online resources, informational seminars, and collaboration with local business associations. Workshops should be organised where government officials explain existing policies and how entrepreneurs can benefit from them. These sessions can help demystify the process and enhance perceptions of governmental support.

By translating the insights from this research into actionable strategies and initiatives, this study can make practical contributions that may support and enhance the growth and success of female entrepreneurs in India's entrepreneurial ecosystem. To support female entrepreneurs in India in the initial stage of business, organisations may create workshops and training sessions focused on emotional intelligence development, which could help entrepreneurs build interpersonal skills, confidence, and resilience; manage stress; and cultivate effective communication skills, enhancing their ability to navigate the emotional challenges they face during their initial entrepreneurial years. As businesses mature, initiatives could be started to develop strategic skills such as business knowledge and risk-taking among entrepreneurs. Training programmes, workshops, and mentorship opportunities focused on strategic decision-making and business planning could help female entrepreneurs to make informed decisions.

6.6 Recommendations based on study findings

6.6.1 To develop and promote comprehensive entrepreneurial education programmes.

The first recommendation is to develop and promote comprehensive entrepreneurial education programmes that enhance perceptions of business knowledge and risk-taking behaviour. As perceptions of business knowledge and risk-taking behaviour significantly

predict female entrepreneurs' longevity in business for more than five years, it is crucial to develop educational programmes that not only impart practical skills but also positively influence entrepreneurs' self-perceptions. These programmes should include a curriculum that covers essential business knowledge areas such as finance, marketing, and strategic planning, along with modules on risk assessment and management. Developing experiential learning programmes by incorporating experiential learning methods like simulations, case studies, and real-world projects will allow entrepreneurs to apply their knowledge and perceive their abilities as effective and reliable (Kansikas and Tarasanski, 2023; Ali *et al.*, 2024).

Workshops and sessions focused on building confidence and self-efficacy and highlighting successful female entrepreneurs as role models to reinforce positive self-perceptions should be organised (Bandura, 1997; Bosma *et al.*, 2012).

The impact of these perceptions on long-term success underscores the need for educational programmes beyond traditional teaching. Enhancing one's self-perceptions can lead to a more resilient entrepreneurial mindset, which is crucial for sustaining businesses over time (Susiana, Yindrizar, and Ningrum (2022)). However, implementing such programmes requires substantial resource investment and continuous updates to keep the curriculum relevant. Non-profit organisations like Dhriiti – The Courage Within, and the Self-Employed Female's Association (SEWA) can intervene and arrange the recommended entrepreneurial training programmes, experiential learning programmes, and workshops to help existing and potential female entrepreneurs.

6.6.2 To strengthen family support systems and emotional intelligence development

The second recommendation is to strengthen family support systems and emotional intelligence development for early-stage entrepreneurs. Initiatives should aim to foster a supportive environment at home; recognise that perceptions of family support are crucial for early-stage business success; and conduct workshops that educate family members on the

challenges and needs of female entrepreneurs, emphasising the importance of emotional and logistical support (Arora and Agarwal, 2019). Community-based networks should be established that provide a platform for the families of entrepreneurs to share experiences and strategies for offering effective support. To establish such community-based networks, platforms like WhatsApp groups or Facebook groups could be used. Perceptions of emotional intelligence can be enhanced through targeted programmes, such as by offering training that develops skills in self-awareness, empathy, and emotional regulation, all of which are crucial for navigating early-stage business challenges (Gautam and Khurana, 2018). Peer-support groups where female entrepreneurs can share experiences should be initiated to reinforce their perceptions of emotional intelligence and resilience. While these initiatives can significantly impact their entrepreneurial journey, females may face resistance due to traditional gender roles and family dynamics. Efforts must therefore be made to address and gradually shift these societal norms.

6.6.3 To improve awareness and accessibility of government policies

Perceptions of government policies significantly predict longevity in business for more than five years for female entrepreneurs in India, and therefore, targeted campaigns are needed to improve awareness and accessibility of these policies, thereby improving perceptions of government policies. Multiple platforms (social media, local media, workshops) should be used to disseminate information about government policies, grants, and support programmes specifically designed for female entrepreneurs. Additionally, regular workshops and seminars with government agencies should be established to educate female entrepreneurs on navigating and benefitting from existing policies. While improving perceptions of government policies can lead to better utilisation of available resources and long-term business success, reaching and educating a diverse and widespread population of female entrepreneurs is a significant challenge. Additionally, there needs to be a continuous effort to

simplify these policies and ensure they are genuinely supportive and accessible to females across different regions and backgrounds (Saranya and Chandrasekar, 2023).

The study highlights the importance of Indian female entrepreneurs' perceptions regarding traditional and modern challenges as factors influencing their longevity in business. Practical programmes can be designed by the relevant stakeholders, such as government or non-government organisations, to address these perceptions directly by conducting educational workshops focusing on strategies to overcome societal norms and gender biases. These strategies can help female entrepreneurs perceive themselves as capable of leveraging resilience and adaptability to overcome traditional and modern challenges; this can be achieved by creating a positive perception framework. Developing support systems that foster positive perceptions in multiple areas is crucial for entrepreneurial success and can be made possible by creating integrated support programmes that simultaneously address business knowledge, risk-taking, emotional intelligence, family support, and policy awareness. This holistic approach ensures that female entrepreneurs receive comprehensive support that enhances their self-perceptions.

There are several organisations, such as the National Small Industries Corporation (NSIC - Government Organisation), the Federation of Indian Chambers of Commerce and Industry (FICCI), the Self-Employed Female's Association (SEWA), Female's India Trust (WIT), and Dhriiti – The Courage Within (a non-profit organisation), that work for entrepreneurial development in India. To access these training programmes and workshops, female entrepreneurs can visit the website of the National Small Industries Corporation (NSIC), which is a government organisation. This organisation provides support to small-scale industries in India and offers various schemes and programmes specifically aimed at promoting female entrepreneurship. Female entrepreneurs can contact NSIC offices or use the contact details provided on their website to enquire about upcoming workshops and

registration procedures. Female entrepreneurs in India can send email inquiries to the contact addresses provided on these organisations' websites to ask for information on upcoming workshops and how to participate. They can also subscribe to the newsletters of these organisations to receive regular updates about workshops, training sessions, and events. Finally, they can follow these organisations on social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Instagram to stay updated with the latest announcements and workshop details.

Summary

The study highlights the critical role that perceptions play in the entrepreneurial success of female entrepreneurs in India. By identifying that perceptions of business knowledge, risk-taking behaviour, and emotional intelligence significantly predict female entrepreneurial success, this study underscores the importance of fostering positive self-perceptions among female entrepreneurs. Furthermore, the validation of perceptions of family support and perceptions of government policies as significant predictors of female entrepreneurial success emphasises the need for targeted initiatives that enhance these perceptions, especially in the context of the unique challenges faced by female entrepreneurs in India. These insights present clear directives for action. For example, the development of comprehensive educational programmes that improve business knowledge and confidence in taking risks should be created. So should initiatives that foster family support and emotional resilience, and campaigns to improve awareness and accessibility of supportive government policies be created. Creating an environment that empowers female entrepreneurs to not only start but also sustain and grow their businesses and become successful can be achieved by addressing these areas.

In conclusion, the pathway to enhancing female entrepreneurial success lies in transforming perceptions. Educators, policymakers, and community leaders must collaborate to implement programmes that build confidence, support systems, and awareness. This concerted effort will not only bridge the perception gap but also pave the way for a thriving entrepreneurial ecosystem where females can excel and contribute significantly to economic growth. The time to act is now—empowering female entrepreneurs is not just a matter of equity but a strategic imperative for inclusive and sustained economic development.

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Appendix A: Tables

Appendix A: Table 3. 1 Questionnaire Constructs and Items

Constructs	Items	Reference
FS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Family and household responsibilities ▪ Work life-family balance ▪ Having young children ▪ Lack of encouragement and moral support from friends and family ▪ Lacking financial support from family 	Agustoni (2019); Uddin and Bhuiyan (2019)
SS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of SS and help from other female ▪ Social discrimination against female ▪ Indian social culture constitutes a barrier ▪ Lack of role models to represent successful female entrepreneurs 	Alison (2017); Sahban, Kumar, and Sri Ramalu (2015)
EI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Interpersonal skills ▪ Confidence ▪ Emotional resilience ▪ Ability to build better business and interpersonal relationships than men ▪ Empathetic nature of female 	Alsos and Ljunggren (2016); Agustoni (2019); Baassiri (2018)
GS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stereotypes against access to crucial business opportunities ▪ Perception that entrepreneurship is a masculine activity ▪ Challenges with patriarchal social structures ▪ Challenges to gain finance for their business compared to men ▪ Most companies, individuals, and society prefers to deal with men than female 	Basit <i>et al.</i> (2020)
BK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of business management skills ▪ Lack of prior work experience 	Basit <i>et al.</i> (2020)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of industry-specific knowledge ▪ Lack of entrepreneurial training and education 	
RB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ RB ability compared to men ▪ Trying out new and unusual activities ▪ Project with unique approaches ▪ High risk in the market ▪ Taking higher risks than men and unsuccessful female 	Bolton (2012); Batool and Ullah (2017); Alsos and Ljunggren (2016)
GP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Inability of the government to provide funding and subsidies to support female entrepreneurs ▪ Lack of government support for female entrepreneurs in terms of law and regulations ▪ Lack of coordination between various government departments regarding business procedures that help female entrepreneurs ▪ Lack of laws protecting the investment of female ▪ High rates of insurance, taxes, and duties 	Belwal, Belwal and Fatema (2014)
TA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Aware of opportunities available in the digital economy ▪ Female entrepreneurs have been advantaged by advancements in technology ▪ Level of competency in the use of new technologies ▪ Use of ICT tools ▪ Adopted automatic transaction and other technologies 	Boermans and Willebrands (2017); Basit <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Traditional challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Traditional role of female in the family ▪ Traditional perceptions about female increase the business risk they face in entrepreneurial ventures 	
Modern challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High cost of living in modern society 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Expense towards child education and rearing ▪ Unequal pay for working female ▪ More barriers to female entrepreneurs than in the past ▪ Recent Government Policies ▪ Work and family roles are still evolving in India ▪ Social media has spread negative perception concerning female ▪ Globalisation 	
Covid-19 pandemic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Covid-19 pandemic has affected businesses run by female more than men ▪ Covid-19 has increased the barriers to the success of female entrepreneurs in India ▪ Covid-19 has provided opportunities to certain businesses by female entrepreneurs 	This variable was removed as it did not meet the reliability requirements.

Source : Author's Compilations

BK = business knowledge; EI = emotional intelligence; RB = risk-taking behaviour; FS = family support, SS= social support;; GS = gender stereotypes; TA = technological advancements; GP =government Policies; ICT = information and communication technology

Appendix A: Table 3. 2 Factor analysis

Factors	Variables	Items	Loading			
Personal Factors	Business knowledge	Business management skills	.728			
		Prior work experience	.721			
		Industry-specific knowledge	.895			
	Risk-taking Behaviour		Entrepreneurial training and education	.894		
			...they are not risk-takers as compared to men	.516		
			... they do not like trying out new and unusual activities and hence miss out on several business opportunities	.625		
			... they do not emphasise projects with unique approaches but emphasise rather tried and true approaches	.542		
			... high risk in the markets makes it more difficult for female entrepreneurs	.579		
			... successful female entrepreneurs have taken greater risk than men and unsuccessful female entrepreneurs	.537		
			Emotional Intelligence		Interpersonal skills	.695
					Confidence	.659
					Emotional resilience	.623
	Environmental Factors	Family Support	The ability to build better business and interpersonal relationships than men	.739		
			The empathetic nature of female	.638		
			Family and household responsibilities	.832		
Balancing family and work life			.548			
Having young children			.727			
Social Support			Lack of encouragement and moral support from friends and family	.646		
			Lacking financial support from family	.531		
			Lack of SS and help from other female	.739		
			Social discrimination against female	.816		
			Indian social culture constitutes a barrier	.847		
	Lack of role models to represent successful female entrepreneurs	.843				

Gender Stereotypes	GS affects their access to crucial business opportunities	.735
	The perception that entrepreneurship is a masculine activity	.728
	Challenges with patriarchal social structure	.469
	Challenges to gain finance for their business compared to men	.838
	Most companies, individuals, and society in general prefer to deal with men than female	.844
Technological Advancements	Female entrepreneurs are aware of opportunities available in the digital economy	.653
	Female entrepreneurs have been advantaged by advancements in technology	.686
	The success of female entrepreneurs depends on their level of competency in the use of new technologies	.675
	Female entrepreneurs who use ICT tools are more likely to succeed in business	.887
	Female entrepreneurs who have adopted automatic transaction and other technologies have enhanced the effectiveness and success	.900
Government Policies	The inability of the government to provide funding and subsidies to support female entrepreneurs	
	Lack of government support for female entrepreneurs in terms of law and regulations	.837
	Lack of coordination between various government departments regarding business procedures that help female entrepreneurs	.697
	Lack of laws protecting the investment of female	.860

		High rates of insurance, taxes, and duties	.824
Challenges	Traditional Challenges	The traditional role of female in the family	.856
		Traditional perceptions about female increase the business risk they face in entrepreneurial ventures	.856
	Modern Challenges	The high cost of living in modern society negatively affects their success	.520
		Increasing expense towards child education and rearing affect their success	.591
		The unequal pay that working female face is a potential limiting factor	.750
		There have been more barriers to female entrepreneurs than in the past	.545
		Recent GP increase the barriers to female entrepreneurs	.530
		As the work and family roles are still evolving in India, female are facing a challenging business environment	.482
		Social media has spread negative perception concerning female	.446
		Globalisation poses a challenge to female entrepreneurs	.493
Impact of Covid-19		Covid-19 pandemic has affected businesses run by female more than men	.657
		Covid-19 has increased the barriers to the success of female entrepreneurs in India	.676
		Covid-19 has provided opportunities to certain businesses by female entrepreneurs	.730

Appendix A: Table 3. 3 Total variance for all the factors

Perceptions of Business Knowledge						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.814	45.340	45.340	1.814	45.340	45.340
2	1.425	35.613	80.953	1.425	35.613	80.953
3	0.553	13.833	94.786			
4	0.209	5.214	100.000			
Perceptions of Risk-Taking Behaviour						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.799	55.986	55.986	2.799	55.986	55.986
2	0.958	19.152	75.138			
3	0.520	10.395	85.534			
4	0.427	8.545	94.079			
5	0.296	5.921	100.000			
Perceptions of Emotional Intelligence						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.157	43.142	43.142	2.157	43.142	43.142
2	1.197	23.930	67.072	1.197	23.930	67.072
3	0.635	12.693	79.764			
4	0.534	10.677	90.442			
5	0.478	9.558	100.000			
Perceptions of Family Support						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.256	45.119	45.119	2.256	45.119	45.119
2	1.029	20.574	65.694	1.029	20.574	65.694
3	0.882	17.638	83.332			
4	0.523	10.458	93.789			
5	0.311	6.211	100.000			
Perceptions of Social Support						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.057	51.426	51.426	2.057	51.426	51.426
2	1.188	29.706	81.133	1.188	29.706	81.133
3	0.465	11.614	92.747			
4	0.290	7.253	100.000			
Perceptions of Gender Stereotypes						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.206	44.126	44.126	2.206	44.126	44.126
2	1.409	28.173	72.299	1.409	28.173	72.299

3	0.727	14.540	86.839
4	0.372	7.450	94.289
5	0.286	5.711	100.000

Perceptions of Technological Advancements

Component	Initial Eigenvalues	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.798	55.965	55.965	2.798	55.965	55.965
2	1.003	20.061	76.026	1.003	20.061	76.026
3	0.516	10.311	86.338			
4	0.481	9.620	95.958			
5	0.202	4.042	100.000			

Perceptions of Government Policies

Component	Initial Eigenvalues	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.897	57.945	57.945	2.897	57.945	57.945
2	1.089	21.774	79.719	1.089	21.774	79.719
3	0.442	8.846	88.565			
4	0.308	6.168	94.733			
5	0.263	5.267	100.000			

Perceptions of Traditional Challenges

Component	Initial Eigenvalues	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.712	85.624	85.624	1.712	85.624	85.624
2	0.288	14.376	100.000			

Perceptions of Modern Challenges

Component	Initial Eigenvalues	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.356	54.452	54.452	4.356	54.452	54.452
2	0.895	11.181	65.634			
3	0.864	10.800	76.434			
4	0.604	7.551	83.985			
5	0.430	5.372	89.356			
6	0.321	4.016	93.372			
7	0.288	3.601	96.973			
8	0.242	3.027	100.000			

Impact of Covid-19

Component	Initial Eigenvalues	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.038	34.605	34.605	1.038	34.605	34.605
2	1.025	34.183	68.788	1.025	34.183	68.788
3	0.936	31.212	100.000			

Appendix A: Table 4. 1 Likelihood ratio tests

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Significance	.000	.000	.000
Chi-Square	32.620	26.445	19.671
df	3	5	2

Appendix A: Table 4. 2 Goodness of fit tests

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Pearson	.291	.324	.160
Deviance	.235	.300	.015

Appendix A: Table 4. 3 Pseudo R-Square

Pseudo R-Square	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Cox and Snell	.107	.092	.065
Nagelkerke	.161	.139	.099
McFadden	.103	.088	.063

Appendix A: Table 4. 4 Parameter Estimates (Reference Category, ‘More than 5 years’)

	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	B	Exp(B)	B	Exp(B)	B	Exp(B)
Personal Factors						
Business Knowledge	-1.372	.254				
Risk-taking Behaviour	-.682	.505				
Emotional Intelligence	.941	2.563				
Environmental Factors						
Family Support			.998	2.712		
Social Support			.211	1.235		
Gender Stereotypes			-.412	.662		
Technological Advancement			.424	1.527		
Government Policies			-1.265	.282		
Challenges						
Traditional					-.484	.616
Modern					-.687	.503

Appendix A: Table 4. 5 Parameter Estimates (Reference Category, ‘Less than 5 years’)

	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	B	Exp(B)	B	Exp(B)	B	Exp(B)
Personal Factors						
Business Knowledge	1.372	3.942				
Risk-taking Behaviour	.682	1.978				
Emotional Intelligence	-.941	.390				
Environmental Factors						
Family Support			-.998	.369		
Social Support			-.211	.810		
Gender Stereotypes			.412	1.510		
Technological Advancement			-.424	.655		
Government Policies			1.265	3.544		
Challenges						
Traditional					.484	1.623
Modern					.687	1.198

Appendix B: Participant Information Sheet

Appendix B: Participant Information Sheet 1

Participant Information Sheet

1. Research Project Title

Barriers and Challenges to Women Entrepreneurship in the Modern Business Environment

2. Invitation

You are being invited to take part in this research project. Before you decide to do so, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done, and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask if there is anything which is unclear or if you would like more information. Participation in the research is completely voluntary. Thank you for reading this.

3. What is the project's purpose?

The purpose of this study is to explore the specific problems and challenges that women have continued to experience in the business environment, and identify how best such challenges can be addressed to facilitate women involvement in business as a means of achieving economic growth and development..

4. Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to participate in this research because my research is on women who are already entrepreneurs and have started their business as well as also on women who are willing to start their business and become entrepreneur. The study has focused on establishing the challenges faced by women entrepreneurs and how these challenges can be solved

5. Do I have to take part?

No. It is up to you to decide whether to take part. If you decide to take part, you will be able to keep the copy of this information sheet and you should indicate your agreement to the online consent form. You are free to withdraw from the research at any time, without giving any reason.

6. What will happen to me if I take part?

If you are happy to take part, you will be required to sign a consent form to confirm your participation.

If you are taking part in questionnaire, you will be asked to complete a web-based questionnaire which I estimate will take about 10-15 minutes of your time.

7. What do I have to do?

There are no right or wrong answers in it. Please feel free to express your views and opinions and answer the questions in the questionnaire. There are no other commitments or lifestyle restrictions associated with participating.

8. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

Appendix B: Participant Information Sheet 2

Participant Information Sheet

Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any disadvantages or discomfort. The potential physical and/or psychological harm or distress will be the same as any experienced in everyday life.

9. What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Whilst there are no immediate benefits for those people participating in the project, it is hoped that this work will be of great relevance to female entrepreneurs who have continued to face challenges, who anticipate engaging in entrepreneurial activities, and those who are already established entrepreneurs. Precisely, the study will help them to identify the main challenges they face or expect to face, and potential ways in which they can face and handle them.

10. What happens if the research study stops earlier than expected?

Should the research stop earlier than planned and you are affected in any way, you will be informed and explained.

11. What if something goes wrong?

If you have any complaints about the project in the first instance, you can contact the researcher at any time. If you feel your complaint has not been handled up to your satisfaction, you can contact the University of the West of Scotland Registrar and Secretary to take your complaint further. (Please find the contact details below)

12. Will my taking part in this project be kept confidential?

All the information that we collect about you during the research will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be able to be identified in any reports or publications. Your name will not be mentioned anywhere in the study, but will be given a code, which will be identified only by the researcher. Your institution will also not be identified. Any data collected through web-based questionnaire will be stored online in a form protected by passwords and other relevant security processes and technologies.

13. Will I be recorded, and how will the recorded media be used?

You will not be recorded in any way other than your input to the questionnaire without separate permission being gained from you. No other use will be made of it without your written permission. All the information about you will be kept strictly confidential and anonymous.

14. What type of information will be sought from me and why is the collection of this information relevant for achieving the research project's objectives?

You will be asked in questionnaire about your opinion regarding the understanding of barriers and challenges to female entrepreneurs in the modern business environment. Your views and experience will help the researcher to understand the research topic and provide practical recommendation.

15. What will happen to the results of the research project?

Appendix B: Participant Information Sheet 3

Participant Information Sheet

If the results of the research will be published, you will not be identified in any report or publication. Your institution will not be identified in any report or publication. If you wish to be given a copy of any reports resulting from the research, please inform me.

16. Who is organising and funding the research?

The researcher is organising and funding the research.

17. Who has ethically reviewed the project?

This research has been granted ethical approval by the School of Business and Enterprise's Ethics Committee procedure and subsequently endorsed by the ethics procedures of UWS. The University of the West of the Scotland's Research Ethics Committee monitors the application and delivery of the University's Ethics Review Procedure across the University.

18. Contacts for further information

Khushboo Deraiya - School of Business and Enterprise, University of the West of Scotland, UK.

Email: [REDACTED]

Full address of the UWS London Campus:
Import Building, 2 Clove Cres, Poplar, London E14 2BE

Thank you for taking part in this research!

Appendix C: Ethical Approval Letter

20/01/2022

Dear Khushboo Deraiya,

Your application 16070: Barriers and Challenges to Women Entrepreneurship in the Modern Business Environment, submission 14751, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

Appendix D: Research Questionnaire

Appendix D 1: Research Questionnaire

Barriers and Challenges to Women Entrepreneurship in Business

Dear Participant,

You are being invited to participate in a doctoral research study. The purpose of this study is to explore the specific problems and challenges that women entrepreneurs have continued to experience in the business environment, and how best such challenges can be addressed.

Your participation in the research is entirely voluntary and please be assured that all the information collected will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be able to be identified in any reports or publications as only aggregates of data will be presented. Any data collected through a web-based questionnaire will be stored online in a form protected by passwords and other relevant security processes and technologies.

This questionnaire will take around 10 minutes of your time. There are no right or wrong answers in it. Please feel free to express your views and opinions and answer the questions in the questionnaire.

* Required

1. Please provide your consent if you are willing to share your opinion/information for this noble cause of knowledge creation? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

2. Age

Mark only one oval per row.

	18-25	26-35	36-45	56 or older
Row 1	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Appendix D 2 Research Questionnaire

3. Marital Status

Mark only one oval per row.

	Single	Married	Divorced	Widowed
Row 1	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4. Kindly indicate the number of Children.

Mark only one oval per row.

	No Children	1 child	2-3 children	4-5 children	More than 5 children
Row 1	<input type="radio"/>				

5. What is the highest level of education achieved?

Mark only one oval per row.

	High School or less	Diploma	Bachelor Degree	Master's Degree	Doctoral Degree
Row 1	<input type="radio"/>				

6. How long have you been in business? If not in business, kindly skip to next question below.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not in Business	Less than 2 years	3-5 years	6-8 years	9-10 years	Above 10 years
Row 1	<input type="radio"/>					

7. If not in business, have you ever thought of starting a business?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes	No	Maybe
Row 1	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Appendix D 3 Research Questionnaire

8. Did you take any training related to your business before you established it?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes	No
Row 1	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

9. If yes, which training did you take?

Part
B:Survey
Questions

This section asks you questions about different factors that influence the success of women entrepreneurs. For the questions that will follow, indicate your level of agreement to various statements. Use a scale of 1 to 5 in which 1=Strongly Agree, 2=Agree, 3=Neutral, 4=Disagree, and 5=Strongly Disagree respectively.

Lack of Family Support

10. Do you think that statements below regarding Lack of Family Support limits women's involvement in business and affect their entrepreneurial success?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Family and household responsibilities	<input type="radio"/>				
Balancing family and work-life	<input type="radio"/>				
Having young children	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of encouragement and moral support from friends and family.	<input type="radio"/>				
Lacking financial support from family	<input type="radio"/>				

Lack of Social Support

Appendix D 4 Research Questionnaire

11. Do you think that the statements below regarding lack of social support limits women's involvement in business and affect their success?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Lack of social support and help from other women	<input type="radio"/>				
Social discrimination against women	<input type="radio"/>				
Indian social culture constitutes a barrier	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of role models to represent successful women entrepreneurs	<input type="radio"/>				

Lack of Business Knowledge

12. Do you think that the factors in the following statements limit or affect women entrepreneurial success?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Lack of business management skills	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of prior work experience	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of industrial-specific knowledge	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of entrepreneurial training and education	<input type="radio"/>				

Lack of Risk-Taking Behaviour

Appendix D 5 Research Questionnaire

13. Women entrepreneurs are less successful because....

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
...they are not risk-takers as compared to men	<input type="radio"/>				
...they don't like trying out new and unusual activities and hence miss out on several business opportunities	<input type="radio"/>				
...they don't emphasis on project with unique approaches but emphasis rather on tried and true approaches	<input type="radio"/>				
...high risk in the markets makes it more difficult for female entrepreneurs	<input type="radio"/>				
Successful female entrepreneurs have taken greater risk than men and unsuccessful women entrepreneurs	<input type="radio"/>				

Gender Stereotypes

Appendix D 6 Research Questionnaire

14. Do you think that the following statements regarding Gender Stereotypes affect the success of women entrepreneurs?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Gender stereotypes affects their access to crucial business opportunities	<input type="radio"/>				
The perception that entrepreneurship is a masculine activity	<input type="radio"/>				
Challenges with patriarchal society structure	<input type="radio"/>				
Challenges to get finance for their business compared to men	<input type="radio"/>				
Most companies, individuals and society in general prefers to deal with men than women	<input type="radio"/>				

Emotional Intelligence

Appendix D 7 Research Questionnaire

15. Do you think that the factors of Emotional Intelligence of women in the following statements make them successful entrepreneurs?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Interpersonal skills	<input type="radio"/>				
Confidence	<input type="radio"/>				
Emotional resilience	<input type="radio"/>				
The ability to build better business and interpersonal relationships than men	<input type="radio"/>				
The empathetic nature of women	<input type="radio"/>				

Technological advancements

Appendix D 8 Research Questionnaire

16. Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements regarding technological advancements and entrepreneurial success.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Female entrepreneurs are aware of opportunities available in the digital economy.	<input type="radio"/>				
Female entrepreneurs have been advantaged by advancements in technology.	<input type="radio"/>				
The success of female entrepreneurs depends on their level of competency in the use of new technologies	<input type="radio"/>				
Female entrepreneurs who use ICT(Information and Communication Technology) tools are more likely to succeed in business than those that do not	<input type="radio"/>				
Women entrepreneurs who have adopted automatic transaction and other technologies have enhanced the effectiveness and success of their business.	<input type="radio"/>				

Government Policies

Appendix D 9 Research Questionnaire

17. Do you think that the statements below regarding government policies and procedures affect the success of female entrepreneurs?-

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The inability of the government to provide funding and subsidies to support women entrepreneurs	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of government support for women entrepreneurs in terms of law and regulations	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of coordination between various government departments regarding business procedures that help women entrepreneurs	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of laws protecting the investment of women	<input type="radio"/>				
High rates of insurance, taxes and duties	<input type="radio"/>				

Traditional Challenges

18. Do you think that the traditional challenges mentioned in the statements below affect the success of women entrepreneurship?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The traditional role of women in the family	<input type="radio"/>				
Traditional perceptions about women increase the business risk they face in entrepreneurial ventures	<input type="radio"/>				

Appendix D 10 Research Questionnaire

Modern Challenges

19. Do you think that the modern challenges described in the statement affect or limit women's involvement in business?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The high cost of living in modern society negatively affects their success	<input type="radio"/>				
Increasing expense towards child education and rearing affect their success	<input type="radio"/>				
The unequal pay that working women faces is a potential limiting factor	<input type="radio"/>				
There have been more barriers to female entrepreneurs than in the past	<input type="radio"/>				
Recent government policies increase the barriers to women entrepreneurs	<input type="radio"/>				
As the work and family roles are still evolving in India, women are facing a challenging business environment	<input type="radio"/>				
Social media has spread negative perception concerning women	<input type="radio"/>				
Globalization poses a challenge to female entrepreneurs	<input type="radio"/>				

Impact of Covid-19

This section asks you questions concerning the impact of Covid-19 on the entrepreneurial activities of women in business

Appendix D 11 Research Questionnaire

20. This section asks you questions concerning the impact of Covid-19 on the entrepreneurial activities of women in business

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Covid -19 Pandemic has affected businesses run by women more than men	<input type="radio"/>				
Covid-19 has increased the barriers to the success of women entrepreneurs in India	<input type="radio"/>				
Covid-19 has provided opportunities to certain businesses by women entrepreneurs	<input type="radio"/>				
